

Fakulta rybnářství
a ochrany vod
Faculty of Fisheries
and Protection
of Waters

Jihočeská univerzita
v Českých Budějovicích
University of South Bohemia
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Environmental drivers of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) population dynamics in a changing climate

Environmentální faktory ovlivňující populační
dynamiku candáta obecného (*Sander lucioperca*)
v měnícím se klimatu

Doctoral thesis

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Doctoral thesis by
Million Tesfaye Godana

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CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Over the past century, global environmental changes, including climate change, pollution, habitat fragmentation, have impacted many of the Earth's ecosystems (Carpenter et al., 2011; Hogue and Breon, 2022; IPCC, 2023; Roy et al., 2024). These impacts are particularly prevalent in freshwater environments, where many systems are isolated, fragmented, and exposed to multiple anthropogenic stressors (Cooke et al., 2016; Dudgeon, 2019). While these pressures have led to the degradation of many natural systems, they have also resulted in the creation of novel man-made environments such as reservoirs. These novel, human-created habitats function at the intersection of ecological processes and direct resource management, supporting complex aquatic food webs while also holding huge economic importance. Within these dynamic aquatic ecosystems, fish are integral functional and structural components that play a crucial role in maintaining ecosystem balance by regulating ecological processes such as nutrient cycling, energy flow, and trophic dynamics (Holmlund and Hammer, 1999; Allan et al., 2021). Their status in a given ecosystem has huge ecological (food web dynamics, ecosystem resilience, water filtration and carbon sequestration) and socio-economic implications (fisheries productivity and sustainability) (Amatucci et al., 2024; Stevenson et al., 2025). Understanding how freshwater fish respond to environmental changes is essential to predict the impact of environmental-driven and biological changes on populations, communities, and even ecosystems (Lee et al., 2023).

1.2 Population dynamics

Population dynamics is the basis for understanding the change in population patterns, and it helps to answer how, when, and why the changes occur and establish the link between environmental and biological changes (Ruiz-Navarro et al., 2016; Andersen, 2019; Spurgeon et al., 2020). Identifying the causes of changes (variation) in the population size and structure of a wide variety of freshwater fish has continued to be the focus of fish ecologists throughout the twentieth and twenty-first centuries (Beverton and Holt, 1957; Matthews, 2012; Jackson et al., 2001). Various freshwater fish across a wide range of ecosystem types (e.g., lakes, reservoirs, and rivers) (Argillier et al., 2004; Nunn et al., 2010; Danilov et al., 2018; Jarić et al., 2019; Souza et al., 2022; Watson et al., 2022) and climatic zones (e.g., tropical, subtropical, and temperate) showed different kinds of responses to the environmental changes, underscoring the variation in the magnitude of responses among different fish species (Ficke et al., 2007; Pörtner and Peck., 2010; Harrod, 2015; Woolway et al., 2021).

Top predators may play an important role in maintaining a healthy ecosystem by controlling prey densities and balancing the structure of the food web (Post, 2002; Estes et al., 2011; Kokkonen, 2022). However, their ability to control prey populations is highly context-dependent and varies among predators. For example, in complex aquatic ecosystems, the ability of piscivores like pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) to regulate abundant cyprinid prey can be limited, suggesting that bottom-up processes are often more critical in structuring these food webs (Vašek et al., 2013). Similarly, the resilience and life-history strategies of predators are not uniform. Contrary to the paradigm of slow-reproducing predators (some salmonid species), many successful piscivores, including pikeperch, are characterized by high fecundity. However, this high potential is realized only when environmental conditions align to support high survival through the vulnerable early life stages. Consequently, even for highly fecund species, annual recruitment success often represents the primary bottleneck regulating population size. This process remains highly sensitive to anthropogenic stressors such as overfishing and habitat degradation (Lehtonen et al., 2009; Psuty et al., 2023).

1.3 Pikeperch and its ecology

Pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) is a key predatory fish species distributed in most Eurasian coastal, brackish, and freshwater bodies (Figure 1A) (Arlinghaus and Mehner, 2004; Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024). It can be a top predator in many fish communities and is a popular and valuable commercial and recreational fish species. As one of the largest predatory fish, pikeperch also plays a crucial role in regulating the ecological system (Persson et al., 2014). Despite enormous efforts to support the pikeperch population through regular stocking measures in many countries, most pikeperch stocks are depleted (Figure 1B) (Mustamäki et al., 2014; Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024; FAO, 2025) or their status is uncertain (Olsson, 2019). Due to their multiple ecological and economic benefits, there is still a growing interest in protecting the populations of this species in Central Europe. However, its biological responses to various environmental changes are not yet fully understood, making it difficult to predict the dynamics of the populations in the face of future environmental changes.

Figure 1. (A) Native distribution of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*), spanning Europe and Asia, including the Caspian, Baltic, Black, and Aral Sea basins, and the Elbe (North Sea basin) and Maritza (Aegean basin) drainages, extending northward up to approximately 65°N in Finland (Froese and Pauly, 2025). Beyond the native range, pikeperch spread into the remaining European countries and into other continents. (B) Global capture fisheries of pikeperch, encompassing both commercial and recreational activities (top panel), and total biomass of pikeperch recorded from recreational fisheries in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia (bottom panel). Shaded areas highlight three distinct phases in the dynamics of the pikeperch fishery at Lipno Reservoir: (i) a pre-collapse period (1980–2005, shaded in light green), initially characterized by high and optimal catches followed by a steep decline after 2003; (ii) a period of collapse, recovery, and protection period (2006–2015, shaded in dark red); and (iii) a re-exploitation period (2016–2020, shaded in light blue), during which the pikeperch population began to recover, resulting in increased catches.

1.4 Key drivers of pikeperch population dynamics

Warming and increased variation in environmental temperatures are prime consequences of the ongoing climate change (Poesch et al., 2016). Temperature drives many physicochemical and biological processes (Jeppesen et al., 2012; Watson et al., 2022; Woolway et al., 2022) and has a strong effect on many biological rates, especially in ectotherms, including fish. It impacts demographic traits such as growth, mortality and reproductive success (MacKenzie et al., 2012; Harrod, 2015; Tao et al., 2018a,b), physiological performance (Dee et al., 2020; Kuczynski et al., 2017), and spatial distribution (Barbarossa et al., 2021; Souza et al., 2022) of many fish species. According to the Temperature Size Rule (TSR), warming of aquatic ecosystems is predicted to increase individual growth rates (larger initial size-at-age or size-at-life-stage and advances in the timing of maturation, potentially leading fish to reproduce at a younger age and smaller size) (Ohlberger, 2013; Lindmark et al., 2022). These direct temperature effects are frequently compounded by a critical secondary stressor: decreasing dissolved oxygen. As water warms, its capacity to hold oxygen diminishes while the metabolic demand of fish increases, creating a “habitat squeeze” that can restrict growth, reduce available habitat, and increase mortality, particularly during sensitive early life stages (Earhart et al., 2022).

Warming can also directly and indirectly affect environmental drivers such as nutrient and food availability, inter-specific interactions, and trophic status of the systems (Harrod, 2015; Frances and McCauley, 2018; Huang et al., 2021), with subsequent potential impacts on individuals. For example, increasing nutrient levels can positively affect food availability through bottom-up control. However, excessive nutrient loading can negatively affect the entire ecosystem (Harrod, 2015). Decreased water transparency due to higher nutrient loads can impair feeding efficiency and resource use by visual predators (Bramm et al., 2009). These processes ultimately impact the somatic growth, survival, fecundity, and reproductive success of individuals (Zamor and Grossman, 2007; Veneranta et al., 2011).

According to a recent report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the global surface temperature has increased by approximately 1.1 °C above pre-industrial levels (1850–1900), and their predictions suggest that the global air temperature across the continents will increase at a rate of 0.1 to 0.4 °C per decade or an increase of 1.1–6.4 °C by the end of the century (IPCC, 2023; Reilly et al., 2015). The maximum summer temperatures are likely to rise more than average in Southern and Central Europe, while minimum winter temperatures are likely to be higher than average in Northern Europe. Warmer temperatures in winter are causing ice cover duration to shorten, resulting in an earlier onset of spring stratification and a lengthening of the growing season, which could have both negative and positive impacts on aquatic organisms depending on the situation. As a case study, in the Lipno Reservoir, Czechia, over the past three decades, average winter water temperatures increased from 0.3 °C to 2.4 °C, average spring temperatures from 8.3 °C to 9.6 °C, average summer temperatures from 20.0 °C to 21.5 °C, and average autumn temperatures from 12.1 °C to 12.9 °C (Figure 2) underscoring the rapid warming of the reservoir.

Given this, understanding the impact of climate change and other environmental factors that play a key role in regulating the demographic characteristics (population dynamics) of pikeperch populations would help to describe and predict the changes in the dynamic ecosystem, which is essential for the effective conservation and management of fish populations.

Figure 2. Average seasonal surface water temperatures (°C) of Lipno Reservoir across three decades (1990s, 2000s, and 2010s). The panels illustrate seasonal variations (Winter: December to February, Spring: March to May, Summer: June to August, Autumn: September to November), with temperature values indicated in the upper right corner of each panel. The colour gradient represents temperature magnitude (0–22 °C). Data were sourced from historical monitoring records from the Institute of Hydrobiology, Biology Centre, Czech Academy of Sciences, and Vltava River Catchment Authority (organisation in charge of the reservoir- <https://www.pvl.cz/>).

1.4.1. Somatic growth of pikeperch

Somatic growth is a fundamental driver of population dynamics (Lorenzen, 2016) that responds to changes in both the population (e.g., environmental variation) and the individual level (Denechaud et al., 2020). Changes in somatic growth are linked to various individual-level processes (Lorenzen, 2016; Tao et al., 2018a). Even small changes in the growth of individuals can significantly affect population-level reproductive success, biomass production, predation success, and mortality (Ljunggren, 2002; Matta et al., 2018; Matthias et al., 2018).

Long-term data on individual growth patterns, also called “biochronologies” (Morrongiello et al., 2012), reflect population-level responses to environmental factors (Morrongiello and Thresher, 2015; Martino et al., 2019; Dennis et al., 2021). Investigating the sources of variation in somatic growth patterns can, therefore, reveal how and why population-level changes arise and help predict their future development (Andersen, 2019). Individual somatic growth patterns in fish can be obtained from calcified structures such as otoliths, as their growth is usually related to somatic growth (Campana and Jones, 1992; Ashworth et al., 2016; Souza et al., 2020a).

Many studies have investigated the intrinsic and extrinsic sources of somatic growth variation in different fish species (Smoliński, 2019; Denechaud et al., 2020; Morrongiello et al., 2021; Stewart et al., 2022). One of the early works in freshwater sclerochronology research was conducted by (Pereira, 1995), who examined somatic growth variations in long-lived freshwater fish. Several more recent studies have also developed freshwater otolith chronologies for various groups of freshwater fish (Black et al., 2013; Rypel, 2009; Spurgeon et al., 2020; Tao et al., 2023). In light of this, studying the somatic growth of pikeperch through a multi-year archive of otoliths can provide insight into how the population responds to different types of stressors and ultimately contributes to the effective management and conservation of the species.

1.4.2 Pikeperch recruitment

Recruitment is the addition of new individuals to the exploitable stock – i.e. the influx of young-of-years into the fishing stock (fishing ground) every year. Recruitment is measured and used differently in different studies and contexts and has to be defined in each instance (Skov and Nilsson, 2018). The reproductive behaviour of each fish species has an effect on the reproductive success or recruitment (Craig, 2008). Some species reproduce (spawn) more or less in groups or spawning aggregations; others spawn individually or in small groups and often exhibiting spawning competition, as several males may compete for females that spawn one after another (Pitcher and Hart, 1982). Species also differ in parental care behaviour (Magnhagen, 2015, Andersen, 2019). For instance, most cyprinid fish abandon their eggs after spawning, while other species, such as pikeperch, show at least basic parental care until the eggs hatch (Lappalainen et al., 2003; Craig, 2008).

Pikeperch spawning usually starts in February and June near its southern and northern distribution limits, respectively. Normally at a temperature of around 12 °C, but spawning can also take place at 8 °C. The faster the water warms, the earlier the time of spawning. Further detailed information about the spawning behaviour of pikeperch can be found in Craig (2008) and Lappalainen et al. (2003). In addition to the reproductive behaviour of pikeperch, the quality and quantity of female eggs can vary significantly, particularly in relation to body size and condition (Olin et al., 2022). The largest and highest-quality eggs are typically produced by females aged 5 to 7 years (Lappalainen et al., 2003; Olin et al., 2022). Furthermore, interannual variation in egg production has been observed even among similarly sized individuals, underscoring the crucial role of environmental and biological conditions during the spawning period in determining the overall reproductive success of pikeperch (Lappalainen et al., 2003).

Temperature is widely recognized as a key driver of recruitment success in many percid populations, including pikeperch (Craig, 2008). Furthermore, a range of abiotic and biotic factors act independently, simultaneously or through complex interactions, influencing the recruitment of pikeperch. Compared to other sympatric percid fish, the inter-annual variation in the recruitment is often higher in pikeperch, underscoring the interplay and complex

interaction of environmental and biological factors (Blabolil et al., 2019; Kokkonen et al., 2019). Rising water temperatures in spring (warming) and other related dynamic environmental and biological factors can lead to mixed results for pikeperch populations. One potential benefit of warming is that earlier spawning may extend the growing season, allowing the young pikeperch to shift to piscivory early. However, a possible risk is explained by the “match-mismatch” hypothesis (Hjort, 1914); If this earlier spawning (early due to premature warming) does not coincide with the peak abundance of essential zooplankton prey (the primary food for hatched larvae), it leads to starvation and will negatively impact the recruitment of the pikeperch population.

Several studies have identified the key abiotic and biotic factors influencing the recruitment of pikeperch. For example, biotic factors such as food availability (Ginter et al., 2012a; Blabolil et al., 2019), predation and competition (Blabolil et al., 2016; Dörner et al., 2007, 1999; Frankiewicz et al., 1999), and spawning stock demographics (Gröger et al., 2007; Heikinheimo et al., 2014; Olin et al., 2022), play a substantial role in determining the recruitment of YOY pikeperch. Abiotic factors, including temperature (Lappalainen et al., 1997, 2009; Mustamäki et al., 2014), water levels and nutrients (Ginter et al., 2012a; Blabolil et al., 2016; Danilov et al., 2018), turbidity (Pekcan-Hekim and Lappalainen, 2006), salinity (Ložys, 2004; Scott et al., 2008) and habitat quality (Sziráki et al., 2021), also have an indispensable role in determining the recruitment of pikeperch (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Biotic and abiotic factors influencing the recruitment of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*). Solid black arrows indicate positive effects, and dashed black arrows represent negative effects. Interactive or modifying effects are omitted for clarity.

Despite extensive studies dealing with biotic and abiotic factors influencing the recruitment of pikeperch, the relative importance of each factor is still poorly understood. These factors can vary spatially and temporally (Myers, 1997; Smoliński, 2018), making it difficult to develop consistent, broadly applicable relationships to describe and predict the recruitment of YOY pikeperch. Another challenge in understanding the influencing factors in the recruitment of fish is obtaining long-term biological and environmental datasets (Lindenmayer and Likens, 2009; Ludsin et al., 2014). These datasets are important for understanding year-class variability by tracking inter-annual patterns on the YOYs and their responses to changing environments.

It is imperative to use robust sampling and analytical methods to identify the most crucial drivers and understand their relative importance for variability.

Furthermore, previous studies documented variation in the reproduction periodicity and growth rate of YOY, resulting in a discontinuous size class distribution (creating two or more intra-annual cohorts) (Figure 4) at the end of the growing season (van Densen, 1985, 1996; Jůza et al., 2013). Young of the year pikeperch then consists of several intra-annual cohorts, which differ in their feeding and spatial distribution (Jůza et al., 2023; Frankiewicz et al., 1996) require different sampling methods and may impact recruitment success differently. To our knowledge, no study has attempted to investigate the drivers of each intra-annual cohort (multi-modal pikeperch cohorts) in deeper resolution and their role in shaping the year class strength (recruitment success) of pikeperch.

Figure 4. The three intra-annual cohorts of young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch in the Lipno Reservoir, Czechia: A) Extremely small YOY, B) Ordinary YOY, and C) Piscivorous YOY. Photo credit: Radka Symonová.

1.4.3. Trophic ecology of young-of-the-year pikeperch

Understanding the trophic ecology of fish is fundamental to clarifying their role in aquatic ecosystems, including aspects such as energy flow, nutrient cycling and community structure (Garvey and Whiles, 2016). Diet composition and trophic ecology in the early life stages substantially influence fish growth, survival and recruitment success of fish in a given population (Nunn et al., 2012). Several studies have shown that trophic ecology varies between species and individuals of the same species at different life stages (Costa-Pereira et al., 2018; Ru et al., 2022; Vejřík et al., 2023). The extent and nature of this variation in the early life stages of a single species and how this relates to the trophic level of an individual in the food chain is far less well-understood (Zhao et al., 2014; Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2022; Westrelin et al., 2022; Vejřík et al., 2023).

In the first year of life, pikeperch undergoes one or two distinct ontogenetic diet shifts during its early developmental stages, starting with zooplanktivory, switching to benthivory, and/or ending as piscivory (Specziár, 2005; Vašek et al., 2018; Westrelin et al., 2022). This ontogenetic shift is highly dependent on the size of the YOY, the availability of suitable prey, and environmental conditions and has implications for the overall population and ecological dynamics. The feeding ecology and ontogenetic diet shifts of YOY pikeperch have indeed been extensively studied (Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Persson and Brönmark, 2008; Ginter et al., 2012b). A number of studies also investigated mechanisms beyond the ontogenetic diet shift, resulting in individual size variation in related fish species, such as perch and

walleye (Heermann et al., 2007; Huss et al., 2008; Uphoff et al., 2019; Urbatzka et al., 2008). However, many of these studies lack empirical evidence and are primarily experimental, clearly suggesting the need for further investigation into their dietary adaptations, ontogenetic diet shifts, and intra-specific interactions among YOY individuals.

1.4.4. The role of stocking in enhancing pikeperch population

Globally, fish stocking, also known as supplementation, propagation, culture-based fisheries, or aquaculture-aided enhancements (Lorenzen et al., 2021), has been taking place in different inland water bodies with multiple objectives, from maintaining the natural population or increasing catches to the conservation and restoration of a particular species (Cowx, 1994, 2025; Arlinghaus et al., 2016). Several fish stocking programs have been implemented in many countries, spending hundreds of millions of dollars and euros to satisfy the angler's demands and/or prevent over-exploitation and to strengthen the quality and quantity of the spawning stock of a given species to improve the natural reproductive potential (Cowx, 1994; Lorenzen et al., 2012). However, introducing fish from exogenous sources into a wild stock (natural population) can alter the stock structure, given that stocked fish can be from single or multiple sources, being introduced at varying ages and sizes, reared under different conditions, and released in other locations and at various times (Specziár and Turcsányi, 2014, 2017; Barrow et al., 2021; Guillerault et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2021). This situation can generate complex and not easily comprehended consequences for the fish stock both in terms of ecological and socio-economic aspects (Trippel et al., 2018; Molnár et al., 2020; Morissette et al., 2020).

For effective fisheries management, it is important to monitor stocking programs to check whether they meet the intended goal and are cost-efficient (Cowx, 2025). Indeed, over the last century, different stock monitoring programs have applied various stock discrimination techniques and tools to evaluate the effectiveness of their stocking program, including genetic analysis (Dahle et al., 2018; Jensen et al., 2021), otolith shape analysis (Leguá et al., 2013; Canty et al., 2018; Souza et al., 2020b), otolith microchemical composition analysis (Campana, 1999; Campana and Thorrold, 2001), tagging (Goulette and Lipsky, 2016; Schloesser et al., 2021), fin clipping (McNeil and Crossman, 1979; Jůza et al., 2024), and even the presence and composition of parasites (Klapper et al., 2016; Marengo et al., 2017). It is important to note that each method has its limitations and advantages.

Otolith micro-chemical composition analysis has been becoming one of the most popular and widely used technique to discriminate fish stocks because of their ability to classify with high levels of accuracy, particularly using the micro-chemical composition of the core part of the otolith, which reflects the elemental signature of the natal environment (e.g., hatchery or spawning grounds) (Walther et al., 2017; Walther, 2019). These signatures are "locked in" the otolith and serve as a natal tag of origin even if the fish translocated or migrated to different water bodies (Campana, 1999). As briefly introduced earlier, in many temperate water bodies, the stocking of pikeperch has been taking place for decades to enhance the natural population, including in Lipno reservoir, Czechia. However, the contribution of stocked fish to the population is seldom investigated; hence, the effectiveness of this strategy is virtually unknown for many populations. Discriminating wild and stocked pikeperch using otolith micro-chemical composition analysis and assessing the contribution of stocked fish to the local population could provide a clear insight into effective and sustainable management of the pikeperch population.

1.5 Aims and objectives

Pikeperch populations in temperate water bodies face multiple challenges, including the impacts of climate change, such as rising temperatures and shifts in phenology (Jeppesen et al., 2012; Lappalainen et al., 1997, 2003; Pekcan-Hekim et al., 2011), habitat degradation (Olsson, 2019; Sundblad et al., 2020), alteration of spawning and nursery grounds (Arlinghaus and Mehner, 2004; Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024), and overfishing (Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024; Mustamäki et al., 2014). Therefore, it is important to understand the population dynamics of this species in response to a continuously changing environment. This cannot be achieved without a thorough and deep investigation of the demographic characteristics (biological responses) of pikeperch for various environmental and ecological factors.

The research summarised herein contributes to sustainable and effective fisheries management of pikeperch population in temperate water bodies and provides new insights that help fisheries managers and practitioners to predict fishery conditions.

The dissertation thesis aimed to study the population dynamics of pikeperch in relation to climate changes and other environmental factors. The aim of the study combines the following overarching objectives:

1. To study the somatic growth of pikeperch in relation to environmental conditions (temperature, chlorophyll-*a*, total phosphorus, and water transparency) (Chapter 2)
2. To study the impact of climatic conditions and food availability on bimodality size structure and density of YOY of pikeperch (Chapter 3).
3. To study the impact of biotic and abiotic factors influencing a piscivorous intra-annual cohort of YOY pikeperch and the role of multiple intra-annual cohorts in shaping the early-year class strength (Chapter 4)
4. To study the trophic ecology of distinct intra-annual cohorts of YOY pikeperch (Chapter 5)
5. To study the contribution of stocking for the overall local population of pikeperch (Chapter 6).

Long-term field activities and laboratory works in each chapter herein were conducted in Lipno reservoir, Czechia (Central Europe). The field activities were conducted at the end of August every year. Our model species in all the studies was pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*).

In **Chapter 2**, we investigated the impact of a) temperature and b) eutrophication on the somatic growth of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*). We reconstructed individual growth patterns of pikeperch using back-calculated lengths from cut otoliths. Environmental parameters such as temperature, chlorophyll-*a* concentration and transparency were collected during the growing period (April-November) during the study period. Using a linear mixed model, we investigated how individual state and environmental conditions affect the somatic growth of the local pikeperch population.

In **Chapter 3**, we studied the impact of climatic conditions and food availability on extremely small and ordinary fingerlings intra-annual cohorts. We collected biotic (spawning stock biomass, predator abundance, chlorophyll-*a* concentration and density of relevant taxonomic groups of zooplankton) and abiotic (mainly temperature and precipitation) parameters at monthly and annual intervals during the study period and analysed their effects on the density of extremely small and ordinary fingerlings intra-annual cohorts.

In **Chapter 4**, we studied the impact of the aforementioned biotic and abiotic factors in Chapter 3 on piscivorous sub-cohorts as well. We further investigated the role of all three intra-annual cohorts in structuring the early-year class strength (age 1+ pikeperch) in the subsequent years.

In **Chapter 5**, we investigated the trophic ecology (resource utilization) of the intra-annual cohorts of YOYs pikeperch using diet and stable isotope analysis. We sampled YOY pikeperch, examined the gut contents to the lowest taxonomic level and simultaneously conducted stable isotope analysis.

In **Chapter 6**, we assessed the contribution of stocking to the overall local population of pikeperch. We sampled stocked and wild pikeperch individuals during the study period and measured the micro-elemental composition at the core of otoliths to verify the natal origin of fish (wild and stocked individuals) and, more specifically, to confirm the origin of the fish sources (facilities). Using the trained dataset (known origin), we classified the fish of unknown origin and assessed the contribution of stocking to the overall local population.

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CHAPTER 2

SOMATIC GROWTH OF PIKEPERCH (*STIZOSTEDION LUCIOPERCA*) IN RELATION TO VARIATION IN TEMPERATURE AND EUTROPHICATION IN A CENTRAL EUROPE LAKE

Tesfaye, M., Souza, A.T., Soukalová, K., Šmejkal, M., Hejzlar, J., Prchalová, M., Říha, M., Muška, M., Vašek, M., Frouzová, J., Blabolil, P., Boukal, D.S., Kubečka, J., 2023. Somatic growth of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) in relation to variation in temperature and eutrophication in a Central Europe Lake. Fish. Res. 267, 106824. doi.org/10.1016/J.FISHRES.2023.106824

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My share of the publication Tesfaye et al. (2023) was about 65% (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing)

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Somatic growth of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) in relation to variation in temperature and eutrophication in a Central Europe Lake

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ABSTRACT

Global climate change has been altering freshwater ecosystems by impacting many ecological processes, including individual fish growth. Predictions of responses of local fish populations to future environmental change can draw inferences from past long-term biochronological data. In this study, we reconstructed individual growth pattern of one of the most valuable predatory species in European inland waters, pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*), using back-calculated length from their otoliths. Samples were collected at the Lipno reservoir (Czech Republic) between 2008 and 2020. We used linear mixed-effects models to investigate how individual state and environmental conditions affect the somatic growth of the local pikeperch population. We found that individual growth rates increased with temperature and tended to be higher when chlorophyll-*a* concentration was higher, and water transparency was lower. This suggests the species will likely benefit from the warmer waters predicted in future climate scenarios. However, the decreasing nutrient loading associated with efforts to curb eutrophication in Central Europe may offset these benefits. Together, these results provide a better understanding of how multiple environmental factors, directly and indirectly, influence the somatic growth of pikeperch in long term.

1. Introduction

Over the past century, global climate change has impacted many of the Earth's ecosystems (Ilari et al., 2022; Jeppesen et al., 2012; Tanner et al., 2019), with diverse effects on organisms, populations, and communities (Kuczynski et al., 2017; Parmesan and Yohe, 2003). These impacts are prevalent in freshwaters, where many systems are relatively isolated, fragmented and exposed to multiple anthropogenic stressors (Nickus et al., 2010; Woodward et al., 2010; Wootton et al., 2021). Climate change can interact with and amplify those stressors, affecting freshwater ecosystems in several ways, including altering hydrological patterns, primary and secondary production, nutrient availability, and predator-prey relationships (Boukal et al., 2019; Crozier and Hutchings, 2014; Dee et al., 2020; Frances and McCauley, 2018). Some populations are, therefore, likely to experience higher growth rates due to increased

habitat productivity, reduced competition or predation pressure, while others will experience low growth rates due to extreme temperatures, increased competition or higher mortality (Comte and Olden, 2017; Jarić et al., 2019; Mazumder et al., 2015; Poesch et al., 2016).

Warming and increased variation in environmental temperatures are prime consequences of ongoing climate change (Poesch et al., 2016). Temperature drives many physicochemical and biological processes (Kokkonen et al., 2019; Lappalainen et al., 2009; Huang et al., 2021; Jeppesen et al., 2012; Watson et al., 2022) and has a strong effect on many biological rates, especially in ectotherms. It impacts demographic traits such as population growth, mortality, reproductive success (Matta et al., 2018; Matthias et al., 2018; Morrongiello et al., 2021; Pankhurst and Munday, 2011; Tao et al., 2018a; Tao et al., 2018b), physiological performance (Dee et al., 2020; Kuczynski et al., 2017), and spatial distribution (Barbarossa et al., 2021; Poesch et al., 2016; Souza et al., 2022)

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of many fish species. According to the Temperature Size Rule, warming of aquatic ecosystems is predicted to increase individual growth rates (resulting in larger initial size-at-age or size-at-life-stage) but reduce the asymptotic body size of ectotherms (Lindmark et al., 2022; Ohlberger, 2013).

Warming can also directly and indirectly affect environmental drivers such as nutrient and food availability, inter-specific interactions, and trophic status of the systems (Frances and McCauley, 2018; Harrod, 2015; Huang et al., 2021), with subsequent potential impacts on individuals. For example, increasing nutrient levels can positively affect food availability through bottom-up control. However, excessive nutrient loading can negatively affect the entire ecosystem (Harrod, 2015; Kuczynski et al., 2017). Decreased water transparency due to higher nutrient loads can impair feeding efficiency and resource use by visual predators (Bramm et al., 2009; Diehl, 1988). These processes ultimately impact the somatic growth, survival, fecundity, and reproductive success of individuals (Filazzola et al., 2020; Veneranta et al., 2011; Zamor and Grossman, 2007).

Somatic growth is a fundamental driver of population dynamics (Lorenzen, 2016) that responds to changes at both the population (e.g., environmental variation) and the individual level (Denechaud et al., 2020). Changes in somatic growth are linked to various individual-level processes (Enberg et al., 2012; Lorenzen, 2016; Tao et al., 2018b). Even small changes in the growth of individuals can significantly affect population-level reproductive success, biomass production, predation success, and mortality (Ljunggren, 2002; Matta et al., 2018; Matthias et al., 2018; Morrongiello et al., 2012).

Long-term data on individual growth patterns, also called “bio-chronologies” (Morrongiello et al., 2012), reflect population-level responses to environmental factors (Dennis et al., 2021; Martino et al., 2019; Morrongiello and Thresher, 2015). Investigating the sources of variation in somatic growth patterns can reveal how and why population-level changes arise and help predict their future development (Andersen, 2019). Individual somatic growth patterns in fish can be obtained from scales, and calcified structures such as bones and otoliths, as the growth of these structures are related to fish somatic growth (Campana and Jones, 1992; Harvey et al., 2000; Vigliola and Meekan, 2009).

Many studies have investigated the intrinsic and extrinsic sources of somatic growth variations in different fish species (Denechaud et al., 2020; Morrongiello et al., 2021; Smoliński, 2019; Stewart et al., 2022). One of the early works in freshwater sclerochronology research was conducted by Pereira (1995), who examined somatic growth variations in long-lived freshwater fish. Several recent studies have also developed freshwater otolith chronologies for various groups of freshwater fish (Black et al., 2013; Rypel, 2009; Spurgeon et al., 2020; Tao et al., 2023).

In this study, we focus on pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*), a predatory freshwater fish species distributed in most Eurasian water bodies. The species can be a top predator in many fish communities and is also a popular target in sport fishing (Craig, 2008; Lappalainen et al., 2003; Mustamäki et al., 2014). Studies highlight that the population of pikeperch in central Europe showed a strong fluctuation since the beginning of this millennium (2000 s) (Jakubaviciūtė et al., 2022). Based on the annual catch data of the Czech Anglers Union (Jüza et al., 2023), the pikeperch stock status at the study site (Lipno Reservoir) falls into three distinct periods: i) before collapse (2002–2005), when the catch of pikeperch was higher but declined steeply; ii) catch collapse, recovery, and protection (2006–2015), during which the pikeperch stock collapsed, catches were meagre, and some protection measures implemented; iii) re-exploitation period (2016–2018), when the pikeperch stock started to recover and catches increased.

There is growing interest in protecting populations of this species in central Europe due to its multiple ecological and economic benefits (De Moraes et al., 2023). However, its responses to environmental change are not yet fully understood. This makes it difficult to predict the dynamics of local pikeperch populations under future climate change,

including their resilience to fishing pressure.

To fill this gap, we used a multi-year archive of otoliths collected during a series of scientific surveys in the largest Czech riverine reservoir to relate individual growth trajectories to environmental conditions (temperature, chlorophyll-*a*, total phosphorus, and water transparency) and population density that are considered to significantly influence the growth of pikeperch. We hypothesized that (i) warming and increase in productivity may increase individual growth and (ii) higher density of adult pikeperch may negatively affect individual growth.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site and species

The study was conducted in the Lipno Reservoir, a shallow, eutrophic, and large water body in the South Bohemian Region of the Czech Republic. The reservoir was built between 1952 and 1959 to provide multifunctional use: production of hydropower, flood protection, flow augmentation and recreation (Krolová et al., 2012). It has a water volume of 306 million m³, a surface area of 46.5 km², a maximum depth of 22 m, an average depth of 6.6 m, a shoreline length of 115 km, and a mean water residence time of 0.6 yr (Krolová et al., 2012; Krolová et al., 2013). Fish community in the reservoir is dominated by cyprinids (bleak, *Alburnus alburnus*, roach, *Rutilus rutilus*, and bream, *Abramis brama*) (De Moraes et al., 2023). The most abundant predatory species are perch, *Perca fluviatilis*, and pikeperch, *S. lucioperca* (Kratochvíl et al., 2010).

Pikeperch (*S. lucioperca*) is a temperate percid fish species that naturally occurs in shallow eutrophic lakes with low water transparency (Buijse and Houthuijzen, 1992; Kottelat and Freyhof, 2007). It is a top predator species that play an important ecological role in many water bodies (Kopp et al., 2009). Individuals can live up to 17 years (Kottelat and Freyhof, 2007) and reach up to 100 cm in length and 20 kg (Craig, 2008). They mature between 3 and 4 years at 32–46 cm (Kottelat and Freyhof, 2007; Lappalainen et al., 2003). Spawning begins in February and June near its southern and northern limits of distribution, respectively (Lappalainen et al., 2003). Like most piscivorous fish species, pikeperch goes through a phase of feeding on smaller food items such as zooplankton before switching to a fish diet; usually, pikeperch switches to piscivory during the first summer of its life (Van Densen, 1985). It is a popular target for recreational fishing in central and northern Europe (De Moraes et al., 2023; Vainikka and Hyvärinen, 2012). It has great economic value and often faces high exploitation rates (Jakubaviciūtė et al., 2022; Lehtonen et al., 1996).

2.2. Fieldwork and data processing

In this study, we use data on individual pikeperch ($N = 313$) collected during community-level surveys using European standard multi-mesh gillnets (CEN 2005) annually from 2008 to 2020 (with gaps in 2009–2011 and 2013–2015). Following gillnet retrieval and processing, we measured the standard length (S.L.) of each fish to the nearest 5 mm (fish > 100 mm in length) with a fishing ruler. Sagittal otoliths of individual fish were extracted from the cranial cavity using a pair of tweezers, with the otic chambers being exposed from below.

All otoliths were mechanically cleaned, air-dried, and stored inside paper envelopes with a unique fish code. Afterwards, fish were aged using cut otoliths (thin sections of otoliths) (Fig. 1) with an approximate thickness of 0.3–0.5 mm. The otoliths were embedded in epoxy resin (Epox G20) with silicon bullet moulds for cutting. When the resin was fully cured, they were removed from the silicon mould and cut using a Buehler Isomet low speed saw with a wafering diamond blade. Afterwards, the cut section was glued on glass with Crystalbond 509 thermoplastic resin and photographed in the laboratory using an Optikam B3 camera mounted on an STM stereomicroscope. Reading radius of each otolith was selected to optimize the visibility of the growth annuli

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Fig. 1. Pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) cut otolith; vertical line identifies the axis along which a measurement was taken, and dot the points identify where increments were annotated and measured.

that were measured to the nearest μm using the Optika View 7 software. Distances between the opaque zones of each otolith were measured and subsequently used to back-calculate the fish length at a given age (Fig. 1). To minimize error in age estimations, protocols and procedures described in Das (1994), including a confidence scoring system, were applied.

We applied different back-calculation methods to convert the measurements from otoliths into back-calculated length. We used the Dahl-Lea (Lee, 1910), Fraser-Lee (Fraser, 1916; Lee, 1920), Biological Intercept (Campana, 1990), Monastyrsky (Bagenal and Ricker, 1978), and Modified Fry (Vigliola et al., 2000). Based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC), the Modified Fry model was selected (Table S1). We confirmed that cut otoliths provide reliable descriptors of individual fish growth patterns in this population by regressing back-calculated fish standard length on otolith radius (Fig. S1). We found 99% agreement between the predicted fish length and measured fish size at age. Smoliński et al. (2020) state that large sample sizes are critical prerequisites for conducting biochronological studies. Throughout our sampled years, we had a minimum of 18 specimens per year (Table 1). Cross-dating the samples helps to control the age estimation error (Smoliński et al., 2020). However, in the case of most of our samples, the short lifespan of the individuals limited the utility of cross-dating. The readings resulted in 1125 data points on individual growth increments (one measurement from the cut otolith from the 313 pikeperch specimens), which were used to develop the final biochronology.

2.3. Growth predictors: environmental and individual-level variables

Despite exposure to identical conditions, individuals exhibit distinct somatic growth patterns. To address individual-level discrepancies, we incorporated the identification of each fish individual into our analysis, thus capturing expected age-related trends, potential biases, and selectivity (Morrongiello et al., 2012). Year (calendar year of increment formation) and cohort identity (calendar year of fish birth) were included to examine growth differences within and between cohorts.

Key environmental variables, such as water temperature, transparency, chlorophyll-*a* (hereafter referred to as Chl-*a*), and total phosphorus concentrations, are known to influence the physiology and somatic growth of fish (Brett, 1979; Harrod, 2015; Martino et al., 2019).

Table 1
Summary number of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) otoliths from Lipno reservoir (Czech Republic) used for the somatic growth estimations per year (2008–2020).

Year	Otoliths
2008	18
2012	41
2016	73
2017	48
2018	29
2019	66
2020	38
Total	313

Table 2

List of predictors used in the linear mixed effect model of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) growth (2002–2018) in Lipno reservoir (Czech Republic).

Model parameter	Description
Random effects	
FishID	Unique identification number for fish
Year	Calendar year of increment formation
Cohort	Calendar year of fish birth
Fixed effects	
Age	Fish age (years) at time of increment formation
Age at capture (AAC)	Fish age (years) at time of capture
Temperature	Annual average lake temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i>	Mean annual chlorophyll- <i>a</i> ($\mu\text{g. L}^{-1}$)
Transparency	Annual average transparency (m)
Total Phosphorus	Mean annual total phosphorus (mg. L^{-1})
CPUE	Catch Per Unit Effort

Samples of environmental parameters were collected at 2-week intervals from April–November (because fish growth is negligible during the winter) from Lipno reservoir (48.65 N, 14.16 E) from 2002 to 2018. The water temperature was measured at the surface by a calibrated thermometer. The transparency was measured by Secchi disk. For the determination of Chl-*a* and total phosphorus concentrations, samples were taken from the upper 4-m layer of the water column (composite samples from layers 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 m taken with a Mayer bottle), filtered through a 0.2 mm nylon sieve immediately after collection, and stored at -16°C until analysis. Total phosphorus was determined according to Kopáček and Hejzlar (1993). Samples for the determination of Chl-*a* were filtered in duplicate on 0.4- μm glass fiber filters (type GF-5, Macherey Nagel, Germany) and stored frozen on silica gel until analysis by a spectrophotometric method with acetone extraction (Lorenzen, 1967). The values for each parameter (water temperature, Chl-*a*, total phosphorus, and transparency) were averaged monthly and then annually to derive a single annual value. This value could be subsequently integrated with the individual fish growth data from 2002 to 2018. The averaged values of each parameter per year were tested among different periods (before the collapse, recovery and protection, and re-exploitation period) using non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's significance test.

Annual total catch and effort (number of angling visits obligatory recorded by every angler at each fishing trip) obtained from Czech Anglers Union used to compute catch per unit of effort (CPUE, grams of legal-size pikeperch per angling visit) of pikeperch which was used as a proxy for fish population density to consider the density dependence processes in the model.

2.4. Statistical modelling

Data on the pikeperch somatic growth were investigated using linear mixed-effects models to account for within-fish and within-year dependence of individual data points (Weisberg et al., 2010). Fish length increment (proxy of growth), age, and age at capture were log-transformed (\log_{10}) to linearise the relationship and meet model assumptions. Length increments of the first year of life (between age 0 and 1) were not considered. The final dataset contained only growth increments of pikeperch individuals when they were older than one year (i.e., age 2 and above), independently of their age at capture. For all fish older than 2, all increments except the increment between ages 0 and 1 were used. Models with individual-level random intercept and slope of the age dependence for each individual (hereafter, FishID) were compared (see below). These models were then extended to incorporate the effects of year, cohort, environmental and density-dependent variables.

We first identified the 'best' intrinsic base model by combining age with different random effect structures (combination of random slope and/or intercept of FishID, age, year, and cohort). Akaike's information criterion corrected for small sample sizes (AICc) was used to rank the

candidate models (Burnham and Anderson, 2004). If the difference in AICc (i.e., $\Delta AICc$) between the highest and the second-highest ranked model was smaller than 2, these two models were assumed to be equally supported (Burnham and Anderson, 2004). The selected 'best' model was then refitted with REML (Restricted maximum likelihood) to obtain unbiased estimates (Zuur et al., 2009). Growth synchrony between individuals from a given year was estimated by calculating the intra-class correlation coefficients (ICC) for optimal year-only and cohort-only models (Morrongiello and Thresher, 2015). These coefficients estimated the correlation of fish growth within year and year classes by measuring the relative similarity (variation) as proportions (Koch, 2006).

2.5. Influence of extrinsic factors on somatic growth of pikeperch

We developed linear mixed-effect models to investigate the influence of environmental factors on the pikeperch somatic growth by adding environmental factors as fixed-effect predictors. We examined the correlations of the environmental variables (Fig. S2) and found a significant relationship (Pearson's product-moment correlation $p < 0.05$) between total phosphorus, temperature, and transparency. Consequently, we have decided to exclude total phosphorus from the analysis. First, we investigated the influence of temperature on annual somatic growth by fitting the annual average temperature from 2002 to 2018 to the best intrinsic model. Second, we fitted the effect of other environmental factors, such as Chl- α and transparency. Finally, we incorporated environmental and density-dependent factor (pikeperch CPUE) into an extrinsic model. We ranked the best model, which included the full range of extrinsic factors, using AICc to determine the main drivers of fish growth. All analyses were performed in R (4.1.2) using packages lme4 (Bates et al., 2015), AICcmovag (Mazerolle, 2019), and effect (Fox, 2003).

3. Results

The growth trajectories of pikeperch in the Lipno reservoir reconstructed from the individual otoliths differed strongly among cohorts: cohorts born before 2010 grew significantly slower than the most recent cohorts (Fig. 2). Temporal growth synchrony across individuals in the same year or within a cohort was generally moderate ($ICC_{Year} = 0.37$;

$ICC_{Cohort} = 0.32$). Inter-annual variation was observed in a year- and cohort-specific growth time series (BLUP for the random year and cohort effect) (Figs. 3a and 3b). The growth increments were larger in 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, while they were lower in 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, and 2011.

3.1. Intrinsic sources of growth variation

The optimal intrinsic models for annual biochronology were composed of various combinations of fixed and random effects (Table S2). Calculated AICc values for the different model random structures indicated the strongest support for incorporating a random intercept and age slope for FishID and year and a random intercept for cohort. The age of the fish ranged between 2 and 14 years. Age has been proven to be the most significant influence on somatic growth, with increment in length strongly declining as fish aged (Fig. 4).

The associated conditional R^2 (0.86) for the optimal intrinsic base model indicated that random and fixed factors explained around 86% of the variance in fish somatic growth (Table S2).

3.2. Extrinsic sources of growth variation

The trends in extrinsic factors varied among different periods. Before (prior) collapse (between years; 2002–2005), protection and recovery period (2006–2015), and re-exploitation period (2016–2018) (Fig. 5). The re-exploitation period had the highest concentration of Chl- α and higher temperature. Transparency was the same as before the collapse period. Generally, extrinsic factors showed a significant variation during the three periods ($p < 0.05$), with the exception of transparency between before collapse and re-exploitation period, which was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

The inclusion of extrinsic factors in the optimal base model revealed significant effects on the somatic growth of pikeperch. The best driver of pikeperch somatic growth was identified by comparing the optimal model against individual and combined extrinsic factors (Table S3 & S4). The best extrinsic predictor for the annual somatic growth of pikeperch was temperature, accompanied by fish age (Table 3). Both age and temperature exhibited statistically significant effects, with age demonstrating a negative effect and temperature showing a positive effect.

Fig. 2. Average growth trajectories of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) cohorts through the last decades in Lipno reservoir, Czech Republic. Data points and lines in the graph represent specific age groups (1 years and above) and cohorts, respectively. The size of the points represents the number of fish in each age group.

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Fig. 3. Predicted time-dependent average annual growth variation (after accounting for intrinsic effects) for pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*). (a) Annual growth variation represented by Year random effect conditional modes (best linear unbiased predictors [BLUPs] \pm SE). (b) Cohort specific growth variation represented Cohort random effect conditional modes (best linear unbiased predictors [BLUPs] \pm SE). Dashed dark-green lines in each panel represent long-term average growth (fixed-effect intercept for models).

Fig. 4. Predicted annual length increment (95% CI) in relation to age of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) of Lipno reservoir (Czech Republic).

However, the difference in AICc between the top-ranked model and the second and third best-ranked models was less than 2. The second-ranked model included age, temperature, and Chl-*a*, while the third included age, temperature, and transparency. Hence, the inclusion of transparency, temperature, and Chl-*a* had statistically comparable support to the top-ranked model (Table 3 & S3).

On the other hand, the density (CPUE) of adult pikeperch (Fig. 6) did not show any effect on the somatic growth of the species (Table S4). Model predictions revealed a strong positive influence of temperature on the growth of pikeperch (Fig. 7a). Growth was also positively correlated with Chl-*a* (Fig. 7b). In contrast, high transparency negatively affected growth (Fig. 7c). Overall, the optimal best model explained 86% of the variance in fish growth (Table 3).

4. Discussion

Our results revealed that growth variation is strongly influenced by intrinsic factors (age) and environmental conditions. The applied mixed-

effects modelling approach enabled us to properly partition different sources of growth variation and assess fish ecological responses (Bates et al., 2015; Morrongiello and Thresher, 2015; Weisberg et al., 2010) to different intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

In our study, age was the most important intrinsic factor influencing the growth of pikeperch, and growth decreased significantly as fish got older, which was expected and observed in previous studies (e.g., Martino et al., 2019; Dennis et al., 2021; Morrongiello et al., 2021).

Growth synchrony based on intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) across individuals over the same year or within a cohort indicated moderate inter-individual variation in growth and differences in the increment-age relationship, suggesting the influence of extrinsic effects. Our study did not use cross-dating to control ageing errors, which could affect the accuracy of intra-class correlation and extrinsic factor-growth relationships. Previous biochronological studies have also reported variation in fish somatic growth due to fluctuations in extrinsic drivers (Black et al., 2011; Denechaud et al., 2020; Martino et al., 2019; Morrongiello et al., 2021; Smoliński, 2019). More specifically, in recent decades, several freshwater biochronological studies have highlighted the effect of climate change on the somatic growth of different freshwater fish species (Black et al., 2013; Rypel, 2009; Tao et al., 2023).

According to our results, temperature had the strongest positive effect on the somatic growth of pikeperch among the extrinsic variables analyzed. Pikeperch growth was significantly higher during conditions of warmer waters, which is consistent with our initial hypothesis that warming conditions positively influence somatic growth. Temperature directly influences fish growth by regulating biological processes such as metabolic rate, digestion rate, muscle activity, and reproductive allocation (Martino et al., 2019; Morrongiello et al., 2021). Indirectly, through changing the food quantity and quality, which in turn affect consumers and predators, competitive abilities (altering prey abundance distributions) and altering feeding rates, and top-down control (affecting prey) (Dee et al., 2020; Frances and McCauley, 2018), which are all linked to somatic growth rate in fish. In our case, the increased water temperature had a positive effect on fish growth, and in many cases, due to climate change, a similar effect can be observed in different fish populations (e.g., Denechaud et al., 2020; Martino et al., 2019;

Fig. 5. Difference in mean yearly values of environmental factors during the three periods (Before the collapse, Protection and recovery, and Re-exploitation period) in the Lipno reservoir (Czech Republic). Statistical comparisons were performed using non-parametric Kruskal Wallis test, with significant differences being denoted by different letters (Dunn’s significance test).

Table 3

Parameter estimates of random (a) and fixed (b and c) effects for the final optimal growth model of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) (M7d). Random age slopes are denoted by |.

(a)		
Random effects	Variance (± SD)	Correlation
FishID	0.006 (0.082)	
Age FishID	0.010 (0.100)	-0.19
Year	0.019 (0.137)	
Age Year	0.003 (0.055)	-0.73
Cohort	0.003 (0.055)	
Residuals	0.042 (0.206)	
(b)		
Intrinsic effects	Estimate (S.E.)	t value
Intercept	1.36 (0.040)	33.67
Age	-0.83 (0.026)	-31.50
(c)		
Extrinsic effects	Estimate (S.E.)	t value
Temperature	0.11 (0.032)	3.55
Chlorophyll	0.003 (0.101)	0.329
Transparency	-0.068 (0.277)	-0.247
R ² marginal	0.757	
R ² conditional	0.864	

Morrongiello et al., 2012; Morrongiello et al., 2014; Nolan and Britton, 2019). On the other hand, some fish populations can experience lower growth rates (e.g., Matthias et al., 2018; Michaletz et al., 2012), due to the fact that climate change can make temperature surpasses the optimal growth for part of the year in some populations.

Optimal temperatures for somatic growth vary by life stage and species (Souchon and Tissot, 2012). Based on theoretical and empirical studies, the thermal tolerance of pikeperch falls within a range of 7 and 33 °C. The optimum ranges fall between 12 and 20 °C for embryos, 25 and 30 °C for juveniles, and 10.4 and 26.9 °C for adults (Frisk et al., 2012; Souchon and Tissot, 2012). The increase in the temperature

Fig. 6. Catch per unit effort of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) harvested by anglers (a proxy for adult pikeperch density) of the Lipno reservoir (Czech Republic) during the three periods (Before the collapse: 2002–2005, Protection and recovery: 2006–2015, and Re-exploitation period: 2016–2018).

during the re-exploitation period (2016, 2017, and 2018) coincided with the recorded high growth rate in our study, clearly indicating the warm water preference of the species, which is consistent with earlier studies (Lappalainen et al., 2009; Lozys, 2004). The positive effect of temperature on the somatic growth of pikeperch has also been shown in studies by Lappalainen et al. (2003) and Nolan and Britton (2019); growth rates increase as temperature increases (latitude decreases). According to these studies, pikeperch populations in southern Europe grew faster than in northern Europe. Studies also reported that the growth of pikeperch in lagoon and sea is slower during cold summer and faster

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Fig. 7. Predicted effects of a) water temperature, b) Chl-a, and c) transparency with 95% confidence interval on the annual length increment of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) of the Lipno Reservoir (Czech Republic).

during warm summer conditions (Ložys, 2004). Climate models predict that climate change will increase air temperature (IPCC, 2018). Thus, a higher somatic growth response is likely to be expected for pikeperch population in Central Europe.

Our final models provided comparable statistical support for the inclusion of Chl-a and transparency, both of which emerged as significant factors influencing the somatic growth of pikeperch (see Table S3). Notably, our study revealed a negative correlation between transparency and pikeperch growth, indicating that as transparency increases, the somatic growth of pikeperch declines. This observation suggests that pikeperch exhibit more efficient feeding behavior in turbid and eutrophic water conditions. These findings align with prior investigations by Keskinen and Marjomäki (2003) and Lappalainen et al. (2003). It is also possible that the foraging success of pikeperch is better in waters with low transparency since they have visual adaptations enhancing their foraging capacity in turbid environments (Lappalainen et al., 2003). In addition, the species is adapted to feed under low light conditions through its well-developed visual and olfactory senses (Sonesten, 1991). A similar result has been reported for the related northern American species walleye (*Stizostedion vitreum*), where the species is adapted to feed under the conditions of high-water turbidity (Bruner and DeBruyne, 2021; Craig, 2008).

Interestingly, during the pikeperch stock protection and recovery period, the observed low growth rate coincided with a high level of water transparency (Figs. 3 and 5; Křolová et al., 2013). In the Curonian lagoon (Lithuania), increased turbidity and low transparency resulted in

a positive effect on the growth of pikeperch (Ložys, 2003). Nonetheless, for other fish species, a decrease in water transparency has been found to decrease the activity of visual predators, foraging efficiency, reactive distances, and feeding rates (Vogel and Beauchamp, 1999; Zamor and Grossman, 2007).

Transparency in aquatic ecosystems is closely linked to primary productivity, as an increase in transparency often indicates reduced primary productivity levels. Chl-a has been widely used as an indicator of system productivity and is typically positively associated with fish growth (Hoxmeier et al., 2009; Wagner et al., 2007). The observed positive influence of Chl-a on pikeperch growth in our study is probably not related to zooplankton consumption by the pikeperch itself but rather an indirect consequence of the high abundance of zooplanktivorous fish in the system, which can serve as prey. In many temperate reservoirs and lakes, the growth of primary producers, such as cyanobacteria, algae, and macrophytes, is constrained by nutrient availability. Consequently, the abundance of food available to fish is directly correlated with aquatic primary production, and it is expected that higher production levels will lead to increased fish growth (Downing et al., 1990; Leach et al., 1977). However, eutrophication can have a negative impact on pikeperch populations. For example, in Lake Balaton (Hungary), due to extreme nutrient loading from sewage and agriculture, a substantial decrease (40%) in the catch of pikeperch was observed (Bíró, 1985). In many cases, an excessively high level of nutrients can lead to degraded water quality, disrupting the ecological processes crucial for fish survival and potentially causing population

declines. Furthermore, it can diminish biodiversity, disrupt ecosystem dynamics, and create dead zones due to the generation of anoxic water masses in the environment (Correll, 1998; Huang et al., 2020).

It is well established that fish require food to maintain their physiological energy levels. As a result, the amount of prey availability in the system can considerably affect their growth via the density dependence process. Several ecological studies have demonstrated the importance of the density-dependent process in the somatic growth of fish due to its effect on enhancing competition for food and resources (Beverton and Holt, 1957; Denechaud et al., 2020; Lorenzen and Enberg, 2002). However, the extent of its effect on somatic growth varies across various fish species.

In most cases, the density of adult predatory fish, such as pikeperch, never exceeds the system's carrying capacity, which does not mean the effect is negligible. However, density dependence's impact on somatic growth might not be as strong as other extrinsic factors. For example, Saulamo et al. (2020) pointed out that the effect of extrinsic factors can be much stronger than density dependency on the somatic growth of pikeperch, which might be the case in our study as well, given that pikeperch density had insignificant effects on somatic growth (Table S4), contradicting previous findings (Lappalainen et al., 1996; Lappalainen et al., 2006; Saulamo et al., 2020).

As discussed earlier, pikeperch has a broad range of prey choices (Lehtonen et al., 1996). We believe that the density-dependent effect of prey species at least partially influences the somatic growth of pikeperch. However, due to a lack of complete data on the density of these prey species in all the years, we were unable to include their effect in the model. Additionally, we are aware that our proxy for the density dependence might be slightly biased because the anglers were mostly fishing other species (mainly common carp, *Cyprinus carpio*), so even a meticulous recording system of compulsory recording every fishing visit may not be the ultimate proxy for the angling effort for pikeperch and might have contributed to the undetected effect of density dependency in our study. Furthermore, the status of pikeperch stock in Lipno reservoir may have been unfavourable during most of the study period (Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2022), resulting in an overall lower population density compared to historical levels (Jůza et al., 2023). As a result, we were unable to detect any density-dependent effects on pikeperch growth in our study.

Fishing mortality is probably an important factor affecting pikeperch somatic growth that we could not include in our models. Fishing mortality may have a negative effect on the somatic growth of fish by reducing the proportion of large fish in the population. A high frequency of large and sexually mature individuals indicates a healthy structure of fish stocks. Size at first sexual maturity is under strong evolutionary selection pressure in fish, and possible evolutionary changes toward a smaller maturation size due to high selective fishing pressure have been widely detected in heavily exploited pikeperch populations (Vainikka and Hyvärinen, 2012; Mustamäki et al., 2014; Lappalainen et al., 2016).

The pikeperch population in Lipno is actively managed through annual stocking of aquacultured individuals. Recent research by Souza et al. (2020) highlighted significant changes in otolith shapes between allochthonous (stocked) and autochthonous (wild) individuals from Lipno reservoir, which could impact growth studies depending on the contribution of stocked fish to the adult population. In our study, we did not investigate the growth trajectories of these two groups separately, but we acknowledge that this factor may influence our assessment and could be further investigated in future studies.

The partial collapse of pikeperch population at the beginning of this millennium (2005–2006) may have been caused by oligotrophication (in which the total phosphorus concentration fell by a quarter) together with overfishing by recreational fishermen (Jůza et al. (2023)). Despite the limitation of our study due to i) not accounting for ageing errors in our dataset which could decrease the level of growth synchrony observed among individuals and lead to underestimates in the strength of climate-growth relationships (Smolínski et al., 2020), ii) limited

length of individual growth trajectories which probably underestimated the effect of extrinsic factors on the somatic growth of pikeperch, we provided evidence on the indispensable role of environmental factors in shaping pikeperch's somatic growth. In addition, the impact of fishing mortality on somatic growth must not be overlooked, and further future studies are needed to address this issue.

5. Conclusions

The analysis of archival otoliths applied in this study allowed for identifying the long-term changes in the somatic growth of pikeperch associated with multiple environmental drivers. The results showed the strong positive influence of warming on the somatic growth of pikeperch. Primary productivity and transparency have also been shown to influence somatic growth. The expected increase in warming may positively impact the somatic growth of the species until the optimum limit. Furthermore, our study highlighted the importance of bio-chronological archives in identifying the most often neglected extrinsic drivers of somatic growth. These results have important implications for managing heavily exploited pikeperch stock in Central Europe. Finally, it will help to understand the current state of the fishery and anticipate future changes.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.fishres.2023.106824.

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CHAPTER 3

THE IMPACT OF CLIMATIC CONDITIONS AND FOOD AVAILABILITY ON BIMODALITY SIZE STRUCTURE AND DENSITY OF YOY PIKEPERCH (*SANDER LUCIOPERCA*)

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The impact of climatic conditions and food availability on bimodality size structure and density of YOY pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*)

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Abstract Understanding inter-annual variation in the density of young-of-the-year fish is an important tool for assessing stock status and guiding management decisions. We analyzed data spanning from 2003 to 2022 collected at Lipno Reservoir in Czechia. The study aimed to identify factors influencing the density of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*), a valuable predatory fish species in European waters. A bimodality test for the size class distribution has revealed the existence of two distinct YOY cohorts: extremely small (ES) and ordinary fingerlings. Using the Bayesian horseshoe prior method with 37

potential predictors, followed by linear regression, we observed that certain environmental factors similarly influenced both cohorts. Higher temperatures during spring and summer, coupled with increased densities of large and medium-sized cladocerans, positively affected the density of both cohorts. However, distinct influences were observed: for ordinary fingerlings, increased summer precipitation and a lower abundance of predators were beneficial, whereas, for ES fingerlings, summer copepod density emerged as an additional positive factor. This study emphasizes the importance of a detailed investigation of factors influencing pikeperch recruitment. Examining these drivers provides a clearer insight into the causes of variations in the early life stage, which is crucial for monitoring and managing populations in temperate reservoirs.

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Introduction

Various factors, such as recruitment, growth, mortality, and migration, can trigger changes in population dynamics over time (van Kooten et al., 2010; Fogarty & Siskey, 2019). These processes can cause fluctuations in size, age structure, and other characteristics of a population affecting its overall stability and long-term viability (Jones, 1990; Genovart et al., 2018; Lorenzen & Camp, 2019).

Understanding the biotic and abiotic drivers that regulate the recruitment (i.e. the addition of new individuals in the population) in fish populations has been the focus of several studies (Blabolil et al., 2019; Sharma et al., 2019; Marcek et al., 2021; Souza et al., 2022). These studies have identified key biotic and abiotic factors that promote or inhibit fish recruitment in different water bodies. For example, the availability of prey to the young-of-the-year (hereafter YOY) has been recognized as a crucial biotic factor affecting recruitment. This was explained by the mismatch hypothesis, which proposes that the timing of larval hatching and food availability are crucial for survival, growth, and, ultimately, for determining the recruitment success (Cushing, 1974, 1990; Marcek et al., 2021). Predation on fish eggs, larvae and juveniles has also been suggested as a key biotic factor affecting fish recruitment success (Carreon-Martinez et al., 2014; DeBruyne et al., 2017; Šmejkal et al., 2017; Donadi et al., 2020). Inter- and intra-specific competition (Ward et al., 2006; Gleason et al., 2018), availability of suitable habitats (Sabetian et al., 2021), and spawning stock biomass (Olin et al., 2022) also play decisive roles in determining recruitment success.

In addition to biotic factors, abiotic factors, including temperature, precipitation, nutrient inputs, and water turbidity, can also influence the density of YOY, ultimately affecting future catches (Sandström & Karås, 2002; Souza et al., 2018; Ćmiel et al., 2020). As climate patterns change globally, associated changes in recruitment dynamics due to environmentally driven alterations in spawning success and the growth and mortality of YOY fish can be reasonably expected. Temperature has a strong effect

on recruitment during early life stages (i.e., eggs, larvae, and juveniles) through both direct effects (e.g., impacts on spawning phenology, hatching success, metabolism, development, and growth rates) (Huang et al., 2021; Woods et al., 2022) and indirect effects (prey production and vulnerability to predation) (Pankhurst & Munday, 2011). Precipitation, nutrient inputs, and water turbidity may also indirectly regulate recruitment dynamics by creating suitable spawning grounds, altering prey availability, and either promoting or impeding predation mortality on larvae and juveniles (Ficke et al., 2007; Harrod, 2015).

Despite extensive studies dealing with biotic and abiotic factors influencing the density of YOY fish (Hansen et al., 2015; Blabolil et al., 2019; Gutowsky et al., 2019), the relative importance of each factor is still poorly understood. These factors can vary spatially and temporally (Myers, 1997; Smoliński, 2018), making it difficult to develop consistent, broadly applicable relationships to describe and predict the density of YOYs. Another challenge in understanding the influencing factor in recruitment success of the fish is obtaining long-term biological and environmental datasets (Lindenmayer & Likens, 2009). These datasets are important for understanding year-class variability by tracking inter-annual patterns on the density of YOY and their responses to changing environments. It is imperative to use robust sampling and analytical methods to identify the most crucial drivers and understand their relative importance for variability in the density of YOY.

In this study, we focus on pikeperch (*Sander luciperca*), an ecologically, economically and culturally important species distributed in most Eurasian water bodies (Lappalainen et al., 2003; Freyhof & Kottelat, 2007; Jüza et al., 2023). This species is highly valued by both commercial fisheries and recreational anglers (Arlinghaus & Mehner, 2004). In recent decades, pikeperch stocks has declined in some temperate water bodies, promoting concern among managers and stakeholders (Moraes et al., 2023; Tesfaye et al., 2023). As with many other predatory fishes, the density of YOY pikeperch is highly variable and can be influenced by numerous factors. For example, biotic factors such as food availability (Ginter et al., 2012; Blabolil et al., 2019), predation (Dörner et al., 1999, 2007; Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Blabolil et al., 2016), and spawning stock demographics (Heikinheimo et al., 2014; Olin et al., 2022) are pivotal in

determining the density of YOY pikeperch. Abiotic factors, including temperature (Lappalainen et al., 1997, 2009; Pekcan-Hekim et al., 2011; Mustamäki et al., 2014; Olin et al., 2023), level of nutrients (Ginter et al., 2012; Danilov et al., 2018), and habitat quality (Blabolil et al., 2023) also play indispensable role in influencing the density of fingerlings.

Indeed, several studies have attempted to identify the drivers that cause variability in the size and density of pikeperch in temperate water bodies. For example, some studies emphasized the effect of abiotic factors on the density of YOY pikeperch (Lappalainen et al., 1997; Kjellman et al., 2001; Lappalainen, 2001; Jüza et al., 2013; Blabolil et al., 2019; Kokkonen et al., 2019), while others focused also on biotic factors including prey availability and the size of the spawning biomass (Ginter et al., 2012; Heikinheimo et al., 2014). Previous studies documented variation in the growth rate of YOY, resulting in a discontinuous size class distribution (creating two and more cohorts) at the end of the growing season (van Densen et al., 1996; Jüza et al., 2013). YOY pikeperch then consist of several cohorts which differ in their feeding and spatial distribution (Frankiewicz et al., 1996; Jüza et al., 2023) and may have different impact on the population recruitment. To our knowledge, no study attempted to investigate the drivers of density of these multi-modal pikeperch cohorts in deeper resolution. Considering the most relevant biotic and abiotic factors causing variability in the density of pikeperch and identifying their relationship could provide valuable information about

the population dynamics of this important game fish, guiding its effective management.

In this context, we used 12 years of data collected during scientific surveys in the largest Czech riverine reservoir to explore the relationship between biotic and abiotic conditions believed to, a priori, influence the density of YOY pikeperch significantly. This study aimed to identify the drivers for the successful recruitment of pikeperch and to understand what are the conditions that favor the appearance of extremely small (hereafter ES) and ordinary fingerlings by the end of a growing season. Towards that end, we have investigated the possible effects of food availability, predation pressure, spawning stock, and the impact of abiotic conditions during critical periods on the success of pikeperch recruits using a formalized statistical approach and employing both empirical and expert (a priori) knowledge.

Materials and methods

Study site and species

The study was conducted at Lipno Reservoir, a shallow, eutrophic, and large water body in the South Bohemian Region, Czechia (Fig. 1). The reservoir was built between 1952 and 1959 to provide multi-functional use: production of hydropower, flood protection, flow augmentation and recreation (Krolová et al., 2012). It has a water volume of 306 million m³, a surface area of 46.5 km², a maximum depth of

Fig. 1 Position of Lipno Reservoir within Europe, Czechia, along the longitudinal profile

22 m, an average depth of 6.6 m, average water transparency of 1.1 m, a shoreline length of 115 km, and an average water residence time of 0.6 year (Krolová et al., 2012, 2013). The average concentrations of total phosphorus (TP) and chlorophyll-*a* are 25 µg/L and 18 µg/L, respectively (Jůza et al., 2023). Fish community in the reservoir is dominated by cyprinids (white bream *Blicca bjoerkna*, bleak *Alburnus alburnus*, roach *Rutilus rutilus*, and freshwater bream *Abramis brama*). The most abundant predatory species are adult European perch *Perca fluviatilis* and pikeperch, followed by European catfish *Silurus glanis*, asp *Leuciscus aspius*, northern pike *Esox lucius* (Moraes et al., 2023).

Pikeperch is a temperate percid fish species that occurs in shallow eutrophic lakes with low water transparency (Buijse & Houthuijzen, 1992; Freyhof & Kottelat, 2007). It is a top-predator species fulfilling a key ecological role in many water bodies (Kopp et al., 2009). Individuals can live up to 17 years (Freyhof & Kottelat, 2007) and can reach up to 100 cm in length and 10–12 kg in weight (Craig, 2008). They mature between 3 and 4 years at a length of 32–46 cm, but this vary among populations (Lappalainen et al., 2003). Spawning usually starts in February and in June near its southern and northern distribution limit respectively (Lappalainen et al., 2003).

Density estimates

We used the density of YOY pikeperch at the end of the first growing season as dependent variable or annual recruitment success. The density of YOY pikeperch was monitored during several nights of the last week of August between 2003 and 2022 (specifically, in 2003, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2012, 2016–2022) along the entire longitudinal axis of the reservoir (Fig. 1). We employed a pelagic sampling, using fixed-frame pelagic trawl with a 3×3-m square mouth opening (Jůza & Kubečka, 2007; Jůza et al., 2018). The mesh size of the trawl was 6.5 mm knot to knot in the trawl body and 4 mm in the cod end. The lower part of the frame was equipped with two 15 kg iron slides to keep the trawl weighted down and protect it from potential contact with the bottom. A polystyrene float was attached to the upper rim to ensure the trawl remained in the desired depth. For deeper tows, rope was attached between the float and the frame so the depth layers of 0–3, 3–6, 6–9 and 9–12 m were

sampled. The trawl was towed 100 m behind the boat at a speed of approximately 1 m s⁻¹. The trawling distance (*L*) was recorded using a GPS device (Garmin 60 CSx), and the volume of water sampled was determined by multiplying the distance by the area of the trawling mouth opening (9 m²) (*A*) using the equation $V_w = L \times A$ (where *L* is trawling distance and *A* is the area of the mouth opening of the trawl). The haul lasted 10 min, giving *L* of approximately 600 m. 26–53 hauls were done in different years alternating all the available depths at a particular site and using almost the same depth stratification in all sampled years. To avoid sampling areas disturbed by the towing boat, the trawl was kept on a slightly curved path during all hauls. To precisely determine the overall density of pikeperch in the reservoir, we considered the volume of each layer (VOST method, Tesfaye et al., 2022) and estimated density as the number of individuals per whole reservoir.

As explored by previous studies, at the end of the growing season, size class distributions of YOY pikeperch exhibit two or more cohorts in specific years (van Densen, 1985b; Jůza et al., 2013, 2023). Based on these studies, individuals with a modal size class of ~ < 40 mm standard length, SL were called “extremely small—ES fingerlings” (Jůza et al., 2013), and those with modal size class of ~ > 40 mm SL were referred to as “ordinary fingerlings”. The predictors of density of ES and ordinary fingerlings were assessed separately. Accordingly, we applied bimodality test to distinguish the size class distribution of cohorts (groups) in specific years using Hartigan’s dip test for unimodality or multimodality with dip test function available in diptest package (Maechler, 2021). Bimodality coefficient (*β*) greater than 0.555 indicates bimodal size structure (identifying the two cohorts ES and ordinary fingerlings); less than 0.555 indicates unimodal size structure (Maechler, 2021). Then we computed the overall density of each cohort in the whole reservoir. The age of pikeperch was checked by otolith readings.

Predictor variables

We compiled data describing 37 variables that might explain variation in ES and ordinary fingerlings of pikeperch and hence might serve as explanatory variables in a regression model for density of YOY. These potential covariates included biotic (parental

stock size, predation, food availability) and abiotic (temperature, precipitation, chlorophyll-*a*) drivers of recruitment. Below, we describe how we calculated or derived these covariates as well as rationale for including them (Table S2, together with a priori weight to be used in the formalized Bayesian horse-shoe preselection procedure, Piironen & Vehtari, 2017).

Biotic variables

We used the abundance of pikeperch spawning stock as a proxy for parental stock size and the catch per unit effort (CPUE) (ind. /1000 m² of gillnets) of predatory fish as a proxy for predation pressure. The values for these predictors were derived from adult fish sampling conducted once during the same time periods as sampling of juvenile fish in both benthic and pelagic habitats throughout the study period. Multimesh gillnets encompassing twelve mesh sizes according to European standard EN 14757 and four additional larger mesh sizes (Šmejkal et al., 2015) were used for sampling. All gillnets were set before sunset and lifted after sunrise to cover the maximal peaks of fish activity (Prchalová et al., 2010). The fish caught were identified to species level, and their SL was measured to the nearest millimeter for fish under 100 mm and to the nearest 5 mm for larger fish. The fish were also weighed to the nearest gram. Gillnet catches were standardized and expressed as individuals per 1000 m² of net area (for details of the gillnet sampling, see Šmejkal et al., 2015; Vašek et al., 2016).

We calculated the size at maturity of pikeperch individuals based on the relationship between asymptotic length, length at first maturity, and growth rate (Froese & Binohlan, 2000) and 313 mm was used as the size at the first maturity. Growth data were taken from Tesfaye et al. (2023). The CPUE of individuals with a standard length (SL) greater than 313 mm corresponds to pikeperch at least three years old (the approximate mean length/age at maturity for pikeperch in central Europe; Lappalainen et al., 2003; Nolan, 2020) was computed. The calculated CPUE values of mature pikeperch individuals were used as a proxy for parental stock size (Fig. S1). Likewise, the CPUE of all adult predatory fish (asp, northern pike, pikeperch, perch, and European catfish) was computed. Due to their low abundance, these were pooled

together and used as a proxy for predation pressure on density of YOY (Fig. S2).

To quantify the seasonal dynamics of planktonic food availability and its impact on density of ES and ordinary sized fingerlings, we analyzed the density of relevant taxonomic groups of zooplankton and their body sizes (Figs. S3 and S4). For this purpose, samples provided by the Vltava River Catchment Authority (organization in charge of the reservoir-www.pvl.cz) were used. The samples were collected near the dam area of the reservoir during daytime once a month from May to August using vertical hauls from the depth of 15 m to the surface, using an 85 µm Apstein plankton net. The samples were preserved, sorted, and determined to the species, genus, or higher taxonomic level as far as possible regarding the ontogenetic stage (Table S1). This resulted in a dataset for each of the following five groups and for each sampled month: rotifers, calanoids, cyclopoids, harpacticoids, and cladocerans. Within these groups, for each species, genus and recorded developmental stages, an average size was obtained from literature (Błędzki & Rybak, 2016). Namely, the size range for females was averaged and rounded to the nearest 100 µm value. Subsequently, the density of zooplankton in individuals per decimeter squared of each size class and taxa was calculated for each month during the study period, starting at assumed hatching period and continuing throughout post-spawning period (May–August) (Figs. S3 and S4).

In 2003 and 2008, zooplankton samples were not collected. Therefore, we imputed the missing values using a random forest machine learning algorithm, specifically with the 'impute_rf' function from the 'simputation' package (Mark van der, 2022).

Abiotic variables

We included water temperature, precipitation, and concentration of chlorophyll-*a* as potential abiotic drivers of density of YOY pikeperch. Water temperature was recorded every day by the Vltava River Authority from the surface water of dam part of the reservoir using a calibrated thermometer during the study period, and mean temperature for pre-spawning, spawning, and post spawning was calculated by averaging daily values of each month (Fig. S5).

Variations in precipitation can influence water levels, temperature, and nutrient availability in aquatic

ecosystems. Daily precipitation records were obtained from the nearest meteorological station, approximately 5 km north of the site (Černá v Pošumaví), and mean precipitation relevant periods was calculated by averaging daily values of each month (Fig. S6).

The chlorophyll-*a* concentration was estimated from samples taken at 2-week intervals from the reservoir (48.658N, 14.163E). The samples were taken from the upper 4 m of the water column (composite samples from layers 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 m with a Mayer bottle), filtered through a 0.2 mm nylon sieve immediately after collection, and stored at -16°C until analysis. Samples for the determination of chlorophyll-*a* were filtered in duplicate using 0.4- μm glass fiber filters (type GF-5, Macherey Nagel, Germany) and stored frozen on silica gel until analysis by a spectrophotometric method with acetone extraction (Lorenzen, 1967). Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations were calculated for the spring and summer months by averaging monthly values (Fig. S7).

Precipitation, temperature and chlorophyll-*a* in March to August were selected as variables because they cover the pre-spawning, spawning, and post-spawning periods (Jepsen et al., 1999; Saulamo, 2018), can significantly affect the density of ES and ordinary sized fingerling. The computed average monthly temperature, precipitation, and chlorophyll-*a* concentration can provide valuable insight into how the environmental variables vary over time and describe the overall environmental condition of the study site (Figs. S5, S6, S7).

Statistical analysis

We used a Bayesian explanatory variables selection procedure to identify the most important biotic and abiotic drivers of the density of YOY out of potential candidates. We conducted the analysis separately for ES and ordinary fingerlings as the response variable. In particular, we used the Bayesian Horseshoe Prior (Piironen & Vehtari, 2017) in the process of explanatory variable selection. The main idea is to use this prior for regularization of the (notoriously difficult) selection problem. The horseshoe prior is a particular multivariate normal scale mixture that leads to sparse posteriors (promoting full selection or non-selection) and robustness with respect to outliers (Carvalho et al., 2009). Regularization is brought by

employing a particular form of shrinkage when using global shrinkage parameters while allowing informative parameters (outstanding regression coefficient) to escape shrinkage through additional local shrinkage parameters. By including the biologically motivated expert-supplied inclusion weights of individual covariates (Table S2) and regression coefficient priors with support on either positive or negative half line imposing the coefficient sign congruent with a priori expert knowledge, we pool two information sources: (i) empirical data, and (ii) biological background knowledge. This is important to utilize the relatively scarce data effectively. This approach can be also viewed as a regularization and robustification through shrinkage (Komaki, 2006). Subsequently, we employed a Bayesian linear regression model to analyze the relationship between density of YOY and the preselected covariates, quantitatively, enabling a better understanding of the relative importance of these variables. In both preselection and actual regression with selected variables, we enforced expert-prior on the signs of variables' effects (Table S2) while keeping flat priors on the coefficients and intercept totally unrestricted.

All data processing, visualization (Wickham et al., 2019), and statistical analyses were conducted using the R software (R Core Team, 2023). The Bayesian computations (both for horseshoe covariate preselection and for Bayesian regression with selected covariates) were done via Hamiltonian Monte Carlo posterior simulations in rstan (Carpenter et al., 2017), as an implementation of probabilistic programming language Stan (<https://mc-stan.org/>).

Results

Our bimodality test revealed that the size class distribution of the YOY pikeperch exhibited both a unimodal and bimodal size distribution during the study period. In half of the years (6/12) 2008, 2009, 2016, 2017, 2019 and 2020, we had a significant bimodal size structure distribution (bimodality coefficient $\beta > 0.555$) (Fig. 2). Based on the size class distribution, the calculated density of ES and ordinary fingerlings showed considerable variation, with peaks in 2016, 2017, 2018, and 2020 for ES fingerlings and higher densities in 2003, 2016, 2020, and 2022 for ordinary fingerling (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2 Size class (mm SL or standard length (SL) mm) distribution of the young-of-the-year pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) at the end of August sampling, based on the bimodality test during the study period (2003–2022) Lipno Reservoir, Czechia

Biotic and abiotic drivers of density

Among the biotic and abiotic parameters thought to influence the density of ES fingerlings, the density of large and medium-sized cladocerans (> 1700 μm) in July, small copepods (500–1000 μm) in July, and large and medium copepods (1001–3000 μm) in July and August were identified as the most important biotic factors (Table 1). In addition, abiotic factors such as water temperature in April were found to be essential for ES fingerlings YOY. In comparison, biotic factors, such as the abundance of predators, the density of large and medium-sized cladocerans (> 1700 μm) in June, along with abiotic factors, such

as the amount of precipitation in June and temperature in March, May, June, and July, were identified as the most important for the density of ordinary fingerling.

The relationship between selected biotic and abiotic predictors and density of ES and ordinary fingerlings were identified (Figs. S8 and S9). The Bayesian credible intervals (lower and upper limit CI; 95%) of the parameters were estimated from the linear regression model (Tables 1 and 2). The model intercepts for the density of ES and ordinary fingerlings corresponding to a slope of 0, are 0.0025 and 0.0040, with 95% credible interval (– 0.27, 0.28 and – 0.23, 0.25, respectively). For ES fingerlings, the predicted

Fig. 3 The density of young-of-the-year pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) individuals per hectare during the study period (2003–2022), Lipno Reservoir, Czechia

Table 1 List of prior selected horseshoe covariates for the density of extremely small young-of-the-year fingerlings (ES) of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) (2003–2022)

Predictors	Estimate	Posterior SD	LL of 95%CI	UL of 95%CI
$\beta_{intercept}$	0.0025	0.1379	- 0.2706	0.2816
$\beta_{eta 1}$ (Temperature in April)	0.3116	0.1606	0.0289	0.6407
$\beta_{eta 2}$ (Cladocerans > 1700 μm in July)	0.3940	0.1573	0.0768	0.7023
$\beta_{eta 3}$ (Copepods 1001–3000 μm in July)	0.2424	0.1398	0.0217	0.5507
$\beta_{eta 4}$ (Copepods 1001–3000 μm in August)	0.1544	0.1130	0.0076	0.4292
$\beta_{eta 5}$ (Copepods 500–1000 μm in July)	0.2064	0.1505	0.0089	0.5626
σ	0.4556	0.1355	0.2754	0.7893

LL lower limit, UL upper limit

Table 2 List of prior selected horseshoe covariates for the density of ordinary young-of-the-year fingerlings of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) (2003–2022)

Predictors	Estimate	Posterior SD	LL of 95%CI	UL of 95%CI
$\beta_{intercept}$	0.0040	0.1144	- 0.2253	0.2435
$\beta_{eta 1}$ (Predators)	- 0.2484	0.1552	- 0.0150	- 0.5894
$\beta_{eta 2}$ (Precipitation in June)	0.9933	0.1841	0.6042	1.3406
$\beta_{eta 3}$ (Temperature in March)	0.3007	0.1616	0.0438	0.6761
$\beta_{eta 4}$ (Temperature in May)	0.1791	0.1466	0.0096	0.5474
$\beta_{eta 5}$ (Temperature in June)	0.8650	0.1877	0.4396	1.2117
$\beta_{eta 6}$ (Temperature in July)	0.3948	0.1377	0.1616	0.7074
$\beta_{eta 7}$ (Cladocerans > 1700 μm in July)	0.4684	0.1799	0.1143	0.8372
σ	0.3677	0.1503	0.1923	0.7769

LL lower limit, UL upper limit

effect of large and medium-sized cladocerans in July was the largest, followed by temperature in April, the

density of large and medium-sized copepods in July and August, and small copepods in July (Table 1,

Fig. S8). For ordinary fingerlings, the positive effect of precipitation and temperature in June was highest, followed by the density of cladocerans in July and temperature in spring (March and May). In addition, the model showed that the abundance of predators had a negative effect (Table 2, Fig. S9). The abiotic environmental conditions during spring and late summer appear to be the most influential factors for the density of ordinary fingerlings, whereas for ES fingerlings, the most crucial factors were the availability of different sized zooplanktons during the summer months (Table 3).

We found that the CPUE of spawning stock did not appear as an important factor affecting the density of both ES and ordinary fingerlings.

We evaluated the predictive ability of our constructed models for the density of ES and ordinary fingerlings by regressing observed values with predicted values. The results showed a strong correlation with R^2 values of 0.91 and 0.93 for ES and ordinary fingerlings, respectively, indicating robust predictive ability of the models (Figs. S10a and b).

Discussion

Understanding and identifying the drivers of variability in the size and density of YOY is crucial for the sustainable management of fish populations. By analyzing of 12 years of data from the Lipno Reservoir using a Bayesian approach, our study has shown that biotic and abiotic factors, particularly food availability for YOY pikeperch in summer, together with abiotic conditions in summer and spring, had the most substantial influence on the density of pikeperch (ES and ordinary fingerlings).

The factors influencing the density of ES fingerlings are studied for the first time. While ordinary

fingerlings had been recognized for many decades, ES fingerlings were only reported in the first years of the new millennium (Juza et al., 2013) and their ecological status is still poorly understood. Appearance of ES fingerlings could be a consequence of climate change, or they have been neglected due to their small size and pelagic occurrence. ES fingerlings can be clearly distinguished from ordinary fingerlings (Fig. 2). ES fingerlings also live shallower than ordinary fingerlings (Juza et al., 2023). However, it is not clear whether variations in spatial environmental conditions in the early life stage or different hatching dates can be important factors for the emergence of ES fingerlings (Persson et al., 2000; Post, 2003; Ginter et al., 2012). The importance of ES fingerlings for the population is also still poorly understood. Our results show that the density of ES fingerlings fluctuates more than the density of ordinary fingerlings. In other words, ES fingerlings only occur in some years. When ordinary fingerlings are abundant, the life expectancy of ES fingerlings may not be high, due to cannibalistic predation (Frankiewicz et al., 1999). Larger and faster growing ordinary fingerlings are more likely to survive the critical period: winter, which is the main bottleneck factor in the transition from juveniles to the adult population (Buijse and Houthuijzen, 1992; van Densen et al., 1996; Lapalainen et al. 2000). ES fingerlings also appear to be one of the factors promoting cannibalism among YOY pikeperch being a suitable prey for the larger conspecifics (Tesfaye et al., unpublished data).

Our results demonstrated a significant influence of the availability of zooplankton during the summer on the density of pikeperch, which is consistent with our initial hypothesis that the food availability positively influences the density of YOY's. These findings are in agreement with many other studies that have identified the availability of suitable-sized zooplankton

Table 3 The summary of selected biotic and abiotic horseshoe covariates along with individual months

YOY's	Months						
	March	April	May	June	July	August	
ES		Temperature				Cladocera > 1700 µm, Copepoda 1001–3000 µm, Copepoda 500–1000 µm	Copepoda 1001– 3000 µm
Ordinary	Temperature		Temperature	Temperature, Precipitation	Cladocera > 1700 µm		

as one of the factors influencing the density of YOY pikeperch (Ginter et al., 2015; Lappalainen & Malinen, 2022). Several studies have underscored the importance of the density of proper-sized zooplankton (cladocerans and copepods) in influencing the growth and transition to a piscivorous diet of juvenile pikeperch, which ultimately plays important role determining the recruitment successes (van Densen, 1985b; Buijse & Houthuijzen, 1992; Frankiewicz et al., 1996). In our study, the density of cladocerans and copepods during the summer months had higher values in 2003, 2017 and 2022, coinciding with high density in 2003, 2017 and 2022. This underlines the central role of prey availability during the summer months in determining the density of YOYs. Ljunggren (2002), pointed out the availability of food during the first months after the spawning period as one of the most important factors that determine the density of pikeperch, ultimately determining the recruitment success, which is in agreement with our findings.

Our results highlighted that it is pivotal for YOY pikeperch to learn timely how to find and ingest prey early on in their life, especially for ES fingerlings. It seems reasonable to believe that juveniles that have managed to capture and ingest their first prey and begun to learn exogenous feeding have a much better chance of growing and surviving than those that have not yet caught their first prey. In the eutrophic Lake Võrtsjärv, Estonia, the food availability for YOY pikeperch was limited and of poor quality due to the low density of large zooplankton. Consequently, this scarcity resulted in a smaller density of pikeperch (Zingel & Haberman, 2008). In contrast, the abundance of planktonic food resources for YOY pikeperch, contributed to high density of pikeperch in Lake IJssel, Netherlands (Buijse & Houthuijzen, 1992).

Similar to our findings, the preys of the YOY pikeperch in the Sulejow reservoir (Poland), consist of large and medium-sized cladocerans, particularly *Leptodora kindtii* and copepods (Frankiewicz et al., 1997). *L. kindtii* dominates the pikeperch diet near the water's surface, while copepods are preferred in deeper waters. *L. kindtii* is an important sources of energy provider for juvenile pikeperch (van Densen, 1985a), which may explain the choice of large and medium-sized cladocerans as an influential variable in determining the density of ES and ordinary fingerling pikeperch.

The results suggest that the recruitment of ordinary fingerlings is more influenced by abiotic conditions while food is limiting ES fingerlings. ES fingerlings pikeperch are likely to originate from later hatching and this is probably why smaller and less profitable, but abundant, copepods influenced their densities especially in July when the size of ES fingerlings pikeperch must have been small. Copepods were found to be important early prey of pikeperch in an earlier survey of Lipno Reservoir (Kratochvil et al., 2010).

According to our results, spring temperature (April temperature for ES fingerlings and March and May temperature for ordinary sized fingerlings) had a strong positive effect on the density of pikeperch. These findings align with many other studies that identified spring temperature as one factor driving the density of pikeperch, which eventually plays a substantial role in determining recruitment successes (Lappalainen et al., 1995; Lehtonen & Lappalainen, 1995; Kjellman et al., 2003). Our findings contradict the results of Blabolil et al. (2016), who reported negative effects of April temperatures on the recruitment of YOY pikeperch from gillnets catches in a riverine Římov reservoir (Czechia). Nonetheless, Blabolil et al. (2016) suggested that recruitment estimates obtained through gillnets might be biased because juvenile pikeperch are not effectively caught with gillnets.

Pikeperch is believed to spawn between late April and May in central Europe (Lappalainen et al., 2003). The positive effect of an early rise in spring temperature could be related to stimulating the spawning of pikeperch, extending the spawning season in general (later spawning giving the birth of ES fingerlings cohorts) and extending the first growing season, allowing them to begin feeding on fish earlier, leading to accelerated growth and fat storage before winter (Frankiewicz et al., 1996). Warmer spring temperatures are associated with earlier spawning and strong year classes, while colder water temperatures are associated with later spawning and weaker year classes (Nyberg et al., 2001). Similar to our study, a positive relationship between temperature during the spawning period (at the end of May and the beginning of June) and the density of YOY have been observed for pikeperch in the northern Baltic Sea (Kjellman et al., 2003).

Our study also found that May–June temperature as most influencing factor of the density of YOY, which is inline with many other studies (Lappalainen et al., 1995; Kjellman et al., 2001, 2003; Pekcan-Hekim et al., 2011). The observed positive effect of summer temperature can be explained by the fact that temperature plays an indispensable role in regulating the physiological processes, including growth and development (Huang et al., 2021). Specifically, warmer temperatures together with food availability can accelerate the growth of juveniles' pikeperch, resulting in higher density of YOY (Ginter et al., 2012). As a result, the direct impact of temperature on the biological processes is responsible for the positive impact of temperature on the density of pikeperch. A general feature throughout the range of pikeperch population is that high summer temperature exert positive effect on the density of YOYs (Buijs & Houthuijzen, 1992; Kjellman et al., 2001; Pekcan-Hekim et al., 2011; Heikinheimo et al., 2014).

According to our study, the amount of precipitation in June proved to be an influential factor for the density of ordinary fingerlings. Precipitation during late spring (June) can have a positive effect on the abundance of closely related yellow perch *Perca flavescens* (Honsey et al., 2016). It can help to maintain the water levels to support successful spawning by increasing the availability of suitable spawning and nursery habitats for pikeperch, leading to higher density of fingerlings (Lehtonen et al., 2006; Blabolil et al., 2016; Roy et al., 2021). High water levels can help the parent stock to find adequate spawning substrates to build nests (Blabolil et al., 2016). Another explanation can be that increased precipitation may increase water turbidity, which can be favorable for the survival of juveniles (Zingel & Paaver, 2010; Veneranta et al., 2011). Lappalainen and Lehtonen (1995), attempted to investigate the effect of late spring precipitation on strong year classes but failed to get any significant effect. In our study, we observed the positive effect of June precipitation on the density of ordinary fingerlings. The amount of precipitation in June during 2016, 2020, and 2022 was higher than in other years, resulting in a more abundant YOY cohorts. We attribute this finding to the fact that wet environmental conditions during the spawning and hatching period trigger to initiate the spawning and increase the survival of larvae and eventually lead to

high density of YOYs (Koonce et al., 1977; Lappalainen, 2001).

Our study showed that predation had a negative impact on the density of ordinary fingerlings, which is in line with hypothesized negative relationship between the abundance of predatory fish and density of YOYs. YOY pikeperch is a potential prey species for several littoral and pelagic predators such as northern pike, adult perch, pikeperch, asp, and European catfish in the study area. Previous studies have also found similar results; however, it depends much on the study site (Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Heikinheimo et al., 2014; Blabolil et al., 2016). According to Frankiewicz et al. (1999), the predation pressure by adult pikeperch substantially influence the relative density of YOY pikeperch. As illustrated in several studies, intra-cohort cannibalism may negatively affect the density of fingerlings, especially small ones (Frankiewicz et al., 1996, 1999; Huss et al., 2010). However, it is very dependent on the size distribution of YOY; in our study, the maximum length observed for ordinary fingerling during the study period was 75 mm; since pikeperch is gape-limited, we did not observe intra-cohort cannibalism between ES and ordinary fingerling (unpublished data). However, our direct stomach content analyses from our gillnet survey confirmed high level of cannibalism in Lipno Reservoir (see also Vašek et al., 2018). Another possible reason for not detecting the predation effect on ES fingerlings was likely due to their reduced vulnerability resulting from their small size. Differently from what we hypothesized, we failed to find a significant correlation between the abundance of parent stock and density of YOY, which is consistent with the results of some other studies (Gröger et al., 2007; Blabolil et al., 2016). However, previous studies from the northern Baltic Sea found a positive relationship between estimated parental biomass and the density of YOY, by fitting Ricker's stock recruitment models (Kjellman et al., 2003; Heikinheimo et al., 2014). In Lipno Reservoir, it looks that the input of eggs from the parent stock is usually sufficient and that other factors influence the density of YOY pikeperch.

The other possible reason that could affect the density of YOY pikeperch is competition; competition plays a crucial role in determining the density of YOY of pikeperch (Lappalainen et al., 2009). Intense inter-specific competition with other YOY fish species can reduce survival and growth rates, leading to

variation in the density of YOYs. For instance, when a particular year class of pikeperch faces intense competition for limited prey items, only the more efficient or competitive individuals, capable of securing food resources, may survive and thrive (Nyberg et al., 2001). Consequently, this can result in a strong year class of relatively larger and healthier individuals.

Conclusion

In summary, our study revealed that ES fingerlings occur occasionally in higher density in recent years. The effect of food availability and climatic condition during the critical period determines the density of ES and ordinary fingerlings. The predicted increase in global temperature during spring and summer may positively influence recruitment success due to the fact that higher temperatures benefit growth rates and body size, increasing the chance of survival. Additionally, we provided evidence on the crucial role of biotic factors during summer in determining the density of YOYs with a much stronger effect as compared with abiotic factors. The occurrence of ES fingerlings more frequently can have positive implications for recruitment success. When ES fingerlings are abundant it may create high conspecific competition and facilitate the transition to piscivory, produces larger and faster-growing individuals within the cohort which are more likely to survive the winter. The findings of our study provide valuable insights into the factors that influence the YOY density of pikeperch. These insights can guide fisheries management, including predicting future catches and informing future research and monitoring efforts focused on the early life stages of pikeperch populations in temperate reservoirs.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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CHAPTER 4

DISENTANGLING THE DRIVERS OF A PISCIVOROUS INTRA-ANNUAL COHORT AND THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF THREE COHORTS TO EARLY-YEAR CLASS STRENGTH IN PIKEPERCH (*SANDER LUCIOPERCA*)

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My share on this work was about 65% (conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, methodology, software, validation, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing)

Disentangling the drivers of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort and the contributions of three cohorts to early-year class strength in pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*)

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Abstract

Using pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) as a model species, we investigated the factors influencing fluctuations in the abundance of piscivorous intra-annual cohorts and assessed the role of three distinct cohorts: extremely small (ES), ordinary fingerlings, and piscivorous in shaping year-class strength. Our analysis is based on 13 years of data (2003–2024) collected in the Lipno Reservoir, Czechia. Our result revealed that a higher abundance of ES conspecifics and YOY perch, coupled with increased densities of large cladocerans in July, positively impacted the abundance of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. The abundance of 1+ pikeperch was positively influenced by the abundance of piscivorous and ordinary cohorts recorded in the preceding year. We concluded that all three intra-annual cohorts contribute to the year-class strength of pikeperch, with piscivorous and ordinary cohorts having a more direct effect, while ES intra-annual cohorts indirectly support a piscivory cohort by serving as prey of pikeperch.

Keywords: *Cladocerans; Density-dependent processes; fry; Piscivory; Recruitment dynamics; Survival*

Introduction

Investigating the drivers of variation in the biological processes is a central goal of population ecology (Allen and Hightower, 2010; Marks et al., 2021). One of the fundamental biological processes determining the status and development of the fish population is recruitment of individuals to a defined part of population. This process often exhibits strong interannual variability and remains challenging to predict for different marine and freshwater fish species

due to the complex interplay of multiple ecological factors (Houde, 2016; Lorenzen and Camp, 2019; Camp et al., 2020). Despite the advancements in mechanistic approaches for understanding and predicting recruitment dynamics, it remains a major challenge in fisheries sciences (Ludsin et al., 2014; Lorenzen and Camp, 2019; Maunder and Thorson, 2019).

The concepts of recruitment and year-class strength (YCS) are often used interchangeably to describe the abundance of the year-class of fish (Maceina and Pereira, 2007). It is very important to make a clear distinction between the two concepts: recruitment quantifies the probability of survival of a given cohort passing over a defined biological or fishery-relevant threshold. Year-class strength measures the relative or absolute abundance of that cohort surviving to a certain life stage (e.g., age 1 and more). For the sake of clarity, in this paper, we use the term recruitment to describe the abundance or density of young-of-year (YOY) fish in the period of surveying (late August) and year-class strength (YCS) to describe the abundance of age-1 and older fish.

Several studies have identified the most important density-dependent and independent processes that regulate recruitment dynamics in fish populations. Density-dependent processes such as food availability (van Densen et al., 1996; Ginter et al., 2012; Blabolil et al., 2019), competition (Claessen et al., 2000; Persson et al., 2000; Heermann et al., 2014), predation (Claramunt and Wahl, 2000; Blabolil et al., 2016), spawning stock biomass (Olin et al., 2022), and disease and parasites (Longshaw et al., 2010). Density-independent processes including temperature (directly; spawning, growth, metabolism and indirectly; prey production, predation risk) (Ludsin et al., 2014; Woods et al., 2022), habitat (Sabetian et al., 2021), and water quality (Nilsson et al., 2004). In fact, the key drivers of recruitment may vary across species, among populations, and even between years in the same locality due to variations in local ecosystem conditions. In fish species that exhibit rapid ontogenetic shifts, especially in gape-limited piscivorous percids, slight differences in environmental conditions, spawning timing or larval growth rate can lead to pronounced differences in the abundance and size asymmetries within weeks, creating hierarchical intra-annual cohort structures.

This phenomenon has been demonstrated in many temperate percid fish, such as pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) (van Densen, 1985; van Densen et al., 1996; Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Huss et al., 2010), European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) (Huss et al., 2010; Heermann et al., 2017), walleye (*Stizostedion vitreum*) (Uphoff et al., 2019), and yellow perch (*Perca flavescens*) (Uphoff et al., 2019), in which large fluctuations in recruitment and the formation of a bimodal size distribution with two distinct intra-annual cohorts in late summer (growing period) were observed over the years. Studies suggest that differences in hatching time, environmental conditions like temperature and prey availability, and interactions among species caused these fluctuations and bimodal size distribution.

Recent studies have revealed a third intra-annual cohort of pikeperch, called extremely small fingerlings, beyond the previously known slow-growing planktivorous (benthivores) and fast-growing piscivorous groups (Jůza et al., 2013; Tesfaye et al., 2024), revealing more complexity of cohort dynamics and recruitment processes. Interestingly, distinct and common biotic and abiotic factors were identified, influencing the density of both pelagic intra-annual cohorts (ES and ordinary fingerlings) separately and jointly, emphasising the need for further studies on piscivorous intra-annual cohorts and their crucial role in determining the year class strength (Teskaye et al., 2024).

Given that, we conceptualized four potential hypothetical scenarios describing how intra-annual dynamics or the size class distribution of pikeperch can exist in its population distribution range (Figure 1). In the first scenario (I), the extremely small intra-annual cohort dominates, while the ordinary intra-annual cohort appears in moderate numbers, and the piscivorous remains least abundant, but have the widest length range. Such a scenario

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was partially observed in Lipno reservoir (Czechia) and De Gijster Reservoir (Netherlands) (Jůza et al., 2013; Tesfaye et al., 2024). In scenario II, the ordinary intra-annual cohort can be most abundant, while the extremely small cohort may occur at a moderate level, and the piscivorous cohort will remain the least represented (Tefsaye et al., 2025). Scenario III illustrates a balanced proportion in which the extremely small and ordinary intra-annual cohorts occur in equal proportions, while the piscivorous cohort remains the least abundant. Finally, in scenario IV, the extremely small intra-annual cohort is absent, resulting in the dominance of the ordinary cohort, while the piscivorous cohort remains the least abundant (Frankiewicz et al., 1996; Jůza et al., 2013) (Figure 1). The structure of the size class distribution and the proportion of each intra-annual cohort may substantially determine the year class strength.

Figure 1. Theoretical illustration of the simultaneous occurrence of two or three intra-annual cohorts of young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) in late summer in freshwater lakes, shown across four different scenarios. **Scenario I** represents the occurrence of three sub-cohorts: extremely small intra-annual cohort dominated the YOY population with a very high proportion; an ordinary intra-annual cohort presented at a moderate proportion; and a piscivorous intra-annual cohort occurred at a low proportion. **Scenario II** represents the YOY population structure where ordinary intra-annual cohorts dominated with a high proportion, extremely small cohorts occurred at a moderate proportion, and piscivorous cohorts remained at a low proportion. **Scenario III** illustrates a population structure where extremely small and ordinary intra-annual cohorts occurred at equal proportions, while piscivorous remained at a low proportion. **Scenario IV** shows a very high proportion of ordinary intra-annual cohorts, the absence of extremely small intra-annual cohorts, and a low proportion of piscivorous intra-annual cohorts. Blue background denotes pelagic habitat while brown background indicates the bottom as a benthic habitat.

In fact, extensive studies have been conducted to understand the factors responsible for inter-annual variation in the recruitment success of pikeperch within its population distribution range (Ginter et al., 2012; Heikinheimo et al., 2014; Blabolil et al., 2016, 2023; Danilov et al., 2018; Kokkonen et al., 2019; Lappalainen and Malinen, 2022; Olin et al., 2022). Yet, to our

knowledge, none of these studies, even on related species, have investigated the drivers for each intra-annual cohort separately and their role in shaping the year class strength. It is certain that larger and faster-growing individuals (piscivorous intra-annual cohort) are more likely to survive winter mortality, which is the main bottleneck factor in transitioning YOY to the adult population and contributes to year class strength (Anderson, 1986; Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Specziár, 2011). However, much less is known about the interplay between the three inter-annual cohorts together and their relative contribution to the year class strength.

In our previous study (Tesfaye et al., 2024), we explored the key biotic and abiotic factors that determine the recruitment of extremely small and ordinary intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch primarily residing in the pelagic zone of water bodies. However, the study did not consider a piscivorous intra-annual cohort due to differences in sampling methods and habitat utilization (Blabolil et al., 2016). The present study is a continuation of our previous study (Tesfaye et al., 2024), which focuses primarily on investigating the drivers of a piscivorous cohort and examining the contribution (role) of the three intra-annual cohorts for the year-class strength of pikeperch.

In this context, we used 13 years of data collected during scientific surveys in the largest Czech riverine reservoir to investigate the factors regulating the piscivorous intra-annual cohort and examine how the potential biotic (food availability, spawning stock abundance, predation pressure, inter and intra-specific competition) and abiotic environmental drivers during relevant periods influence their abundance. We also determined the strength of year classes at the age 1+. Finally, we evaluated the contribution of the three intra-annual cohorts in determining the year class strength of pikeperch.

Materials and methods

Study site and species

The study was carried out in the Lipno Reservoir, a shallow, eutrophic, and large water body in the South Bohemian Region of Czechia (Figure 2). The reservoir was constructed from 1952 to 1959 to serve multifunctional purposes: hydropower generation, flood protection, flow augmentation and recreational activities (Krolová et al., 2012). It has a water volume of 306 million m³, a surface area of 46.5 km², a maximum depth of 22 m, an average depth of 6.6 m, a shoreline length of 115 km, and a mean water residence time of 0.6 yr (Krolová et al., 2012, 2013). Fish community in the reservoir is dominated by cyprinids (white bream *Blicca bjoerkna*, bleak *Alburnus alburnus*, roach *Rutilus rutilus*, and freshwater bream *Abramis brama*). The most abundant predatory species are adult European perch *Perca fluviatilis*, pikeperch, and European catfish *Silurus glanis* (Moraes et al., 2023). The northern pike *Esox lucius* and asp *Leuciscus aspius* also occur, but they are not commonly found.

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Figure 2. The position of the Lipno Reservoir within Europe (a) and Czechia (with a black dot) (b) and four sites along the longitudinal profile (c)

Pikeperch is a temperate percid fish species that occurs in various types of water bodies with notable abundance in shallow eutrophic lakes characterized by low water transparency (Buijse and Houthuijzen, 1992; Freyhof and Kottelat, 2007). It is a top-predator species fulfilling a key ecological role in many water bodies (Kopp et al., 2009). Individuals can live up to 17 years (Freyhof and Kottelat, 2007) and can reach up to 100 cm in length and 10–12 kg of weight (Craig, 2008). They mature between 3 and 4 years at a size of 32–46 cm, but this varies among populations at different latitudes (Lappalainen et al., 2003). Spawning usually starts in February and in June near its southern and northern distribution limit, respectively (Lappalainen et al., 2003).

Dependent and explanatory variables

Dependent variables

The abundance of piscivorous intra-annual cohort

The piscivorous intra-annual cohort inhabits the benthic littoral part of the reservoir and cannot be effectively sampled using pelagic trawling (Symonová et al., 2025). To effectively sample this intra-annual cohort, we employed multimesh gillnets with twelve mesh sizes, following European standard EN 14757 and four additional larger mesh sizes (70, 90, 110 and 135 mm, Šmejkal et al., 2015) at the end of August every sampling year (2003, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2012, 2016–2023). Each year we installed 40 pelagic and 70 benthic nets (see Table S2 for the total effort) in all depths available Kubecka et al., 2022). All gillnets were set before sunset and lifted after sunrise to cover the maximal peaks of fish activity (Prchalová et al., 2010). The fish caught were identified to species level, and their standard length (SL) was measured to the nearest millimeter for fish under 100 mm and to the nearest 5 mm for larger fish. We distinguished the piscivorous intra-annual cohort by identifying and analysing the size distribution, followed by verification through otolith readings. Based on these results, we were able to confirm 80 mm (SL) as the minimum and 160 mm as the maximum size for

the piscivorous cohort. Then, the abundance of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort expressed as individuals per 1,000 m² of the net area, assuming the same area of each of the 16 mesh panels (for details of the gillnet sampling, see Šmejkal et al., 2015; Vašek et al., 2016) and used as one of the dependent variables.

Using an analogical procedure, we sampled and distinguished age 1+ and older pikeperch using otolith readings (for a complete description of the age readings, see Tesfaye et al., 2023) and expressed their abundance as individuals per 1,000 m² of the net area. Due to the limited number of years with available data for older fish, we selected age-1+ pikeperch as the second dependent variable (a proxy for early year class strength-YCS).

Explanatory variables

The covariates hypothesized to explain variation in the abundance of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort included a combination of biotic and abiotic factors (45 in total; Figure S1–S4). These potential covariates included biotic (the abundance of the parent stock size and predatory fish, the density of conspecific and sympatric potential prey species, availability of zooplankton, and chlorophyll-*a*) and abiotic (temperature and transparency).

Biotic explanatory variables

The abundance of spawning stock and predatory fish

Pikeperch spawning stock abundance (gillnet CPUE) was used as a proxy for parental stock size and predatory fish abundance to assess predation pressure. The CPUE values were derived from adult fish sampling conducted during the same study period using the gillnet sampling method described above. The size at maturity of pikeperch was calculated based on the relationship between asymptotic length, length at first maturity, and growth rate (Froese and Binohlan, 2000). This analysis indicated that the size at maturity for pikeperch in the studied area is 330 mm, corresponding to individuals at least three years old (the approximate mean length/age at maturity). The CPUE of mature pikeperch was then calculated and used as a proxy for parental stock size (Figure S1). Likewise, the CPUE of all adult predatory fish (asp, northern pike, pikeperch, perch, and European catfish) was computed using the same procedure described above. Due to their low abundance, all predatory fish were pooled together and used as a proxy for predation pressure (Figure S1).

The abundance of conspecific and sympatric fish prey

The abundance of ES and ordinary intra-annual cohort of pikeperch, along with YOY of other fish species (European perch, ruffe *Gymnocephalus cernua*, roach, and bleak), are believed to be a major prey determining the abundance of piscivorous YOY pikeperch (Dörner et al., 2007). These YOY communities inhabit both the pelagic and littoral parts of the lake. For pelagic sampling, we employed a fixed-frame pelagic trawl with a 3x3=9m² mouth opening (as described in Jůza & Kubečka, 2007; Jůza et al., 2018). The mesh size of the trawl was 6.5 mm knot to knot in the belly and 4 mm in the cod end. The lower part of the frame was equipped with two 15 kg iron slides to keep the trawl weighted down and protect it from potential contact with the bottom. A rowing boat was attached to the upper rim to ensure the trawl remained in the desired depth. For deeper tows, a rope was attached between the boat and the frame, so we sampled the layers of 0–3, 3–6, 6–9 and 9–12 m. The trawl was towed at night 100 m behind the boat at a speed of approximately 1 m s⁻¹. The trawling distance (L)

was recorded using a GPS device (Garmin 60 CSx), and the volume of water sampled was determined by multiplying the distance by the area of the trawling mouth opening (9 m²) (A) using the equation $Vw=LxA$ (where, L is trawling distance and A is the area of the mouth opening of the trawl). The haul lasted 10 minutes, thus giving L of approximately 600 m. 26–53 hauls were done in different years, covering all the available depths at a particular site (see Table S2). The trawl was kept on a slightly curved path during all hauls to avoid disturbing the sampling areas by the towing boat.

The littoral YOY fish community was sampled annually during the same nights at the end of August using a 10 m long, 3 m deep fry beach seine with a 1.4 mm mesh size. Each year, 40 seining sessions were executed along the entire longitudinal shoreline, spanning from the dam to the tributary. The effective sampling area of one seining was assumed as 120 m², and the catch was calculated as abundance per hectare according to Kubečka et al. (2022). To precisely determine the overall density of the YOYs in the reservoir, we considered the volume of each pelagic layer and the littoral habitat (VOST method, Tesfaye et al., 2022) and estimated YOY abundance as the number of individuals per hectare of whole reservoir. The overall abundance of ES and ordinary intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch, along with the abundance of sympatric fish species (European perch, ruffe, roach, and bleak), was calculated per hectare for each year (Figure S2).

Zooplanktons density

To quantify the seasonal dynamics of zooplanktonic food availability and its impact on the piscivorous intra-annual cohort, we analyzed the density of relevant taxonomic groups of zooplankton and their body sizes (Table S1 & Figure S3). For this purpose, samples and data provided by the Vltava River Catchment Authority (organization in charge of the reservoir, www.pvl.cz) were used. The samples were collected near the dam area of the reservoir during daytime once a month from April to October using vertical hauls from the depth of 15 m to the surface, using a 85µm Apstein plankton net. The samples were preserved, sorted, and determined to the species, genus, or higher taxonomic level as far as possible regarding the ontogenetic stage (Table S1). This resulted in a dataset for each of the following five groups and for each sampled month: rotifers, calanoids, cyclopoids, harpacticoids, and cladocerans. Within these groups, for each species, genus and recorded developmental stages, an average size was obtained from the literature (Błądzki and Rybak, 2016). Namely, the size range for females was averaged and rounded to the nearest 100 µm value. Subsequently, the density in individual zooplanktons per decimetre squared of each size class and taxa was calculated for each month during the study period, starting at the assumed pikeperch hatching period and continuing throughout the post-spawning period (May–August) (Figure S3).

Primary productivity

Lake productivity is assumed to influence the abundance of fish (Lester et al., 2004). Accordingly, we collected samples at 2-week intervals from Lipno reservoir (48.658N, 14.163E) during the study period to determine chlorophyll-*a* concentration. The samples were taken from the upper 4 m of the water column (composite samples from layers 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 m with a Mayer bottle), filtered through a 0.2 mm nylon sieve immediately after collection, and stored at -16 °C until analysis. Samples for the determination of chlorophyll-*a* were filtered in duplicate using 0.4-µm glass fibre filters (type GF-5, Macherey Nagel, Germany) and stored frozen on silica gel until analysis by a spectrophotometric method with acetone extraction (Lorenzen, 1967). Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations were calculated for the spring and summer months by averaging monthly values (Figure S4A).

Abiotic explanatory variables

Water temperature and transparency

We included water temperature and transparency as potential abiotic drivers of the abundance of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. Water temperature was recorded in the mornings (at 07.00 h) every day by the Vltava River Authority from the surface water of the dam part of the reservoir using a calibrated thermometer during the study period (Figure S4B). The transparency was also measured by the Secchi disc 40*40 cm (Figure S4C). Mean temperature and transparency for critical periods (pre-spawning, spawning, and post-spawning) was calculated by averaging the daily values of each month.

Water temperature and transparency from March to August were selected as predictors because they cover the pre-spawning, spawning, and post-spawning periods (Jepsen et al., 1999; Saulamo, 2018) and can provide valuable insight into how the environmental predictors vary over time and describe the overall environmental condition of the study site.

Statistical analysis

Variable selection

After centring and scaling all explanatory variables, we used the Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), a regularization variable selection technique, to identify the most influential drivers of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. It is a regression-based approach that improves model prediction by reducing overfitting and selecting the most important predictors. It works by adding a penalty term in the regression equation, forcing some coefficients to shrink to zero, effectively eliminating less important variables. Furthermore, it can handle multicollinearity. This approach has proven successful in preventing overfitting with small data sets (Dahlgren, 2010) and has been successfully applied as a widely applicable variable selection method in general ecology and fisheries sciences (Czaja et al., 2023; Yang and Zhou, 2024).

$$\text{LASSO MSE} = \min_{\beta_0, \beta} \left(\frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \beta_0 - x_i^T \beta) \right)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1, p} |\beta_j|$$

where β and β_0 are the regression coefficients of scalar length p , N is the number of observations, y is the response variable at observation i , x is the predictor variable of vector length p and at observation i and λ is a shrinkage penalty parameter.

Model construction and selection

Following LASSO variable selection, multiple candidate models using linear, quadratic and generalized additive models (GAMs) were constructed separately for the selected variables (see Table S2), due to a high degree of collinearity between the selected variables. Power and curvilinear models were explored but didn't differ from the constructed models with quadratic equations, ultimately excluded from model selection.

To select the best candidate model, AICc (corrected Akaike Information Criterion), BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion), RMSE (Root Mean Square Error), and R-squared values

were calculated and assessed. The best models were selected based on their performance across these criteria (Table S2). Model assumptions and diagnostics were inspected when appropriate. Model construction and assessments were conducted in R version 4.4.2 using 'DHARMA' (Hartig, 2016) and 'performance' (Lüdecke et al., 2021) packages.

Determining the year class strength and quantifying the contribution of each intra-annual cohort

Due to the small number of consecutive-year observations (limited time span), we used the abundance of age-1+ pikeperch as a proxy for year-class strength. Years with higher age-1+ abundance were classified as strong year-classes, whereas years with lower abundance were classified as weak year-classes (Pekcan-Hekim et al., 2011).

It is well established that the abundance of YOY percids fish at the end of the growing season is directly related to their recruitment to age 1+ and older fish in the following year (Kaemingk et al., 2014; Vandevalk et al., 2016; Marschall et al., 2023). Considering this, we applied a robust linear regression to quantify the contributions of intra-annual cohorts to age 1+ fish in the following year. Due to the strong and significant correlation between the extremely small and piscivorous intra-annual cohort, we used the residuals of the extremely small intra-annual sub-cohort (derived from the regression against the piscivorous cohort) and mitigated the collinearity. The intra-annual cohorts with significant effects were identified and presented.

All data processing, visualization, and statistical analyses were conducted using the R software (R Core Team, 2023a). Particularly using 'tidyverse' (Wickham et al., 2019), 'lubridate' (Lüdecke et al., 2021), and 'MASS' (Ripley et al., 2013) packages.

Results

Compared to the two pelagic intra-annual cohorts (ES and ordinary fingerlings), the occurrence of piscivorous individuals was consistently lower across all years and exhibited considerable interannual variability. The piscivorous cohort showed pronounced peaks in 2017, 2019, and 2023 (Figure 3A & B). In comparison, ES fingerlings exhibited peaks in 2016, 2017, 2018, and 2020, while ordinary fingerlings had higher densities in 2003, 2016, 2020, 2022, and 2023 (Figure 3A & B).

Figure 3. Size class distribution of the three intra-annual cohorts of young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*), based on standard length (mm SL) from late summer sampling (bin size=3 mm), with the number of individuals in each intra-annual cohort denoted as *n* in the figures, the light blue shaded area represents the pelagic intra-annual cohorts sampled by trawl (extremely small and ordinary intra-annual cohorts), and the white area represents littoral piscivorous intra-annual cohort sampled by benthic gillnet (A) and the abundance of each intra-annual cohort, with pelagic cohorts expressed

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as individuals per hectare on the primary y-axis, and littoral cohort expressed as Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE) per 1,000 m² on the secondary y-axis, during the study period (2003–2023) in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia. Refer to Table S2 in the supplementary material for details on the effort and the number of tows conducted each year.

Drivers of the abundance of piscivorous intra-annual cohort

The applied LASSO variable selection techniques with cross-validated tuning parameter optimization identified three predictors with non-zero, including the abundance of YOY European perch ($\beta=2.849$), large and medium cladocerans ($>1,700 \mu\text{m}$) in July ($\beta=0.383$), the abundance of ES intra-annual cohort ($\beta=0.060$).

Among the candidate models evaluated, the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) demonstrated better performance for all three selected covariates (Table S3). The selected models revealed significant positive non-linear associations of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort with the abundance of YOY perch (Edf=2.97, F=45.21, $p<0.001$), large and medium cladocerans (Edf=4.1, F=43.59, $p<0.001$), and the abundance of ES intra-annual cohort (Edf=2.50, F=48.73, $p<0.001$) (Table 1 & Figure 4)

Table 1. Summary of GAM modelling showing a non-linear relationship between piscivorous intra-annual cohort and selected three most important variables

Density of Cladocera ($>1,700 \mu\text{m}$) (ind. dm²) in July				
A. Parametric coefficients	Estimate (SE)	SE	t	p
Intercept	5.18	0.49	10.37	<0.001***
B. Smooth terms	Edf	Ref. df	F	p
s(cladocerans)	4.1	4.66	43.59	<0.001***
Adjusted R ²	0.95			
The abundance of young of the year perch (per. ha⁻¹)				
A. Parametric coefficients	Estimate (SE)	SE	t	p
Intercept	5.13	0.55	9.30	<0.001***
B. Smooth terms	Edf	Ref. df	F	p
s(perch)	2.97	3.60	45.21	<0.001***
Adjusted R ²	0.93			
The abundance of ES young of the year pikeperch (per. ha⁻¹)				
A. Parametric coefficients	Estimate (SE)	SE	t	p
Intercept	5.13	0.58	8.88	<0.001***
B. Smooth terms	Edf	Ref. df	F	p
s(ES)	2.50	2.96	48.73	<0.001***
Adjusted R ²	0.92			

Figure 4. Generalized Additive Model (GAM) showing the relationship between the abundance of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort (expressed as Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE)) and the selected covariates: (A) Young-of-the-Year (YOY) perch, (B) abundance of extremely small YOY pikeperch, and (C) density of large and medium-sized cladocerans in July. The fitted curve represents the smooth term, with shaded areas indicating 95% confidence intervals. Observed values are represented by points.

Impact of intra-annual cohorts on year class strength

The evaluation of the contribution of intra-annual cohorts to age 1+ pikeperch (hereafter referred to as early year class strength) revealed a significant positive impact of piscivorous (mean estimate \pm SE=0.98 \pm 0.10, 95% CI: 0.74 to 1.21, $p < 0.001$) and ordinary intra-annual cohorts (mean estimate \pm SE=0.02 \pm 0.0, 95% CI: 0.01 to 0.03, $p < 0.001$). The ES had a non-

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significant positive effect (mean estimate \pm SE=0.01 \pm 0.00, 95% CI: -0.00 to 0.02, $p=0.126$). The results emphasize that piscivorous intra-annual cohorts are the strongest predictors of early-year class strength, followed by ordinary cohorts as the second most important (Figure 5 A & B).

Figure 5. (A) The abundance of age-1+ pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*), expressed as individuals per hectare, in the subsequent year, representing individuals born in the previous year (i.e., the cohort born one year earlier). (B) The contributions of the piscivorous and ordinary intra-annual cohorts to the formation of year-class strength (i.e., the abundance of age-1+ pikeperch in the subsequent year). For clarity in both (A & B), the abundance of age-1+ pikeperch was converted to individuals per hectare using the conversion factor provided by Říha et al. (2023).

The performance of all linear and GAM models was tested and evaluated; All fitted models met the necessary statistical assumptions and requirements. Furthermore, a summary of model quality, including key performance metrics and diagnostic evaluations, is provided (Table S3 & Figure S5).

Discussion

The interannual variability (fluctuations) of all three intra-annual cohorts suggests greater sensitivity to biological and environmental factors. Our earlier study addressed the factors influencing the two pelagic intra-annual cohorts (ES and ordinary fingerlings) (Tesfaye et al., 2024). Our current study attempted to identify key regulating factors influencing piscivorous intra-annual cohorts. We provided evidence on the role of the three intra-annual cohorts in forming the early-year class (age 1+).

Factors influencing the abundance of piscivorous intra-annual cohort

In our study, the abundance of YOY European perch was identified as the most important regulating factor influencing the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. Young of the year perch are well-documented as the preferred prey fish in many pikeperch populations (Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Keskinen and Marjomäki, 2004; Keskinen, 2008). In our study area, European perch was the dominant percid species, making it an abundantly available prey for piscivorous YOY pikeperch individuals (Moraes et al., 2023). This finding is consistent with previous studies showing that the abundance of YOY European perch positively influenced the young and adult populations of pikeperch in temperate lakes and reservoirs (Vehanen et al., 1998; Keskinen, 2008; Ginter et al., 2012; Kokkonen, 2019). A recent study on analysing the gut content of piscivorous intra-annual cohorts reported that YOY European perch comprised more than 30% of the gut contents, further supporting our findings (Tesfaye et al., 2025). Similar results were also reported for the closely related populations of yellow perch (*Perca flavescens*) and walleye (*Stizostedion vitreum*) in the Northern America Lake (Ivan et al., 2011; Gostiaux et al., 2022). Conversely, Vainikka and Hyvärinen (2017) reported an inverse relationship between pikeperch and European perch in Lake Oulujärvi, Finland, potentially indicating strong predation of pikeperch on perch.

The density of large and medium cladocerans in July was the second most important regulating factor determining the abundance of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort. The observed significant positive relationship may be explained by the direct influence of larger cladocerans on ES intra-annual cohorts and YOY perch, which in turn may indirectly affect the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. A previous study by Tesfaye et al. (2024) demonstrated that the density of large cladocerans during summer months substantially determined the ES and ordinary intra-annual cohort of pikeperch. It is well established that YOY pikeperch typically shifts to piscivory during the first summer. Prior to this shift, they rely on large zooplankton and macroinvertebrates as primary sources of food. As a result, the availability of larger zooplankton in the ecosystem can significantly influence their initial growth and the timing of the ontogenetic shift (Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Wysujack et al., 2002). In Bautzen Reservoir (Germany), Mehner et al. (1996) found that the onset of piscivory and, eventually, the abundance of piscivorous YOY pikeperch was influenced by the availability of zooplankton and fish prey during the summer months, which is consistent with our results. Furthermore, in the Sulejow Reservoir (Poland), the availability of large cladocerans played a crucial role in later switching to piscivory (Frankiewicz et al., 1997).

Moreover, our study showed the indispensable role of ES individuals in determining the abundance of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. Our study is the first to verify the positive and direct impact of the ES cohort on the larger and fast-growing piscivorous cohort of pikeperch, clearly supporting the occurs of cannibalism among the conspecific YOY pikeperch (Lappalainen et al., 2006; Dörner et al., 2007). In fact, the ES intra-annual cohort can be very suitable for starting prey for piscivorous YOY pikeperch (Tefaye et al., 2025).

Cannibalism is one of the strongest density dependent processes that stabilize and regulate the population dynamics of a given species (Rosenheim and Schreiber, 2022). For example, in the Lake Peipsi in Estonia, Kangur (2000) reported that a high abundance of adult pikeperch was associated with the occurrence of cannibalism, while conversely, a low abundance correlated with the absence of cannibalism. This can indeed be attributed to the benefits of a fish-based diet, which enables piscivorous individuals to survive even in times of limited prey availability by utilizing the accumulated essential lipid reserves for surviving the winter and contributing to the year class strength. It is important to note that intensive cannibalism can reduce the survival of YOY and eventually lead to weak year-class strength (Persson et al., 2000).

It is well-established that summer temperature positively affects the abundance YOY of percid fish (Pekcan-Hekim et al., 2011; Heikinheimo et al., 2014; Kokkonen et al., 2019). Contrary to our expectation, we failed to find the effect of summer water temperature on the piscivorous intra-annual cohort, similar to a recent study on YOY pikeperch (Lappalainen and Malinen, 2022). This might be attributed to the influence of other strong biotic factors, which could mask the effect of summer temperature on the recruitment of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort. It could also be due to the LASSO selection, which removed highly correlated variables; cladocerans and perch could be linked to temperature as well, but their reaction to temperature is more dramatic and thus better captured by considering them directly rather than temperature alone. Nevertheless, we cannot remove the relevance of temperature, as it is likely related to the biotic factors evaluated. Tefaye et al. (2024) identified summer temperature as the most dominant factor influencing the abundance or recruitment of ES and ordinary intra-annual cohorts. This might indicate the stronger effect of summer temperature on the smaller YOY pikeperch individuals. Even though the role of summer temperature in determining the abundance of piscivorous pikeperch has remained unrecognised to a certain extent, we surely cannot discount its indispensable influence in regulating physiological processes, including growth and development (Lappalainen et al., 1995, 2009).

The role of extremely small, ordinary, and piscivorous intra-annual cohort in structuring the class strength of pikeperch

Our study unveiled weak early-year class strength of pikeperch in earlier years 2009 and 2010 (cohorts of 2008 and 2009), which coincided with the partial collapse of the population and the subsequent implementation of size restrictions in the Lipno reservoir, which remained in force until 2015 (Tefaye et al., 2023). Due to management measures, the pikeperch stock showed signs of recovery, and strong year-classes were observed in 2017 and 2018 (cohorts of 2016 and 2017). However, this recovery was short-lived. Since then, the population has fluctuated, alternating between strong and weak year classes, highlighting the persistent variability in recruitment dynamics. Given these fluctuations, additional regulatory measures may be necessary to ensure the long-term sustainability and viability of the population.

The impact of the piscivorous intra-annual cohort on early-year class strength was stronger and significant, albeit they were least abundant. Conversely, ordinary intra-annual cohorts exhibit the reverse scenario – their impact was much lower, yet they were much more abundant.

On the other hand, the direct impact of the ES intra-annual cohort was negligible. However, as discussed earlier, they were the main driver supporting the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. Our study highlights the important role of the piscivorous and ordinary intra-annual cohorts, as well as the potential indirect influence of extremely small cohorts, in shaping early-year class strength. However, we acknowledge that additional factors, beyond those examined here, may also contribute to this phenomenon. The transition from planktivory or benthivory to piscivory is a gradual process. At the end of the growing season, some individuals from the ordinary intra-annual cohort shift from pelagic to littoral benthic habitats. Individuals able to successfully initiate piscivory are more likely to survive the winter and contribute to the early-year class strength. However, during this shift, they are at increased risk of predation by piscivorous conspecifics and other predators. In addition, the increasing size of the available prey of YOY cyprinids at the end of the growing season further limits the number of individuals that successfully transition to piscivory (Frankiewicz et al., 1996).

Implications of the three intra-annual cohorts for recruitment and population dynamics

The ES, ordinary, and piscivorous intra-annual cohorts play a substantial role in structuring the population and recruitment dynamics of pikeperch. Each intra-annual cohort contributes to the year class strength of the pikeperch, eventually playing an indispensable role in ensuring the viability of the population. The ES cohort likely originated from summer spawning (Jůza et al., 2013), is thought to be eliminated by winter mortality, and its indirect role in enhancing year-class strength has not yet been investigated in detail. The ordinary and piscivorous intra-annual cohort originated from regular spring spawning and plays a direct role in determining year-class strength. As highlighted in our study, when both cohorts occur abundantly, it leads to strong year-class strength.

Overall, the variability in the relative abundance of the three intra-annual cohorts, which largely depends on environmental conditions, prey availability and density-dependent interactions, determines the fluctuations in year-class strength.

Conclusion

Pikeperch populations provided a unique opportunity to study the drivers of recruitment in detail for three distinct intra-annual cohorts and their substantial role in shaping year-class strength. Our approach can serve as a template for applying these approaches to other species when conditions allow. In particular, we emphasise the need to consider a wide range of biotic and abiotic factors to understand recruitment clearly.

From a management perspective, the occurrence of three distinct intra-annual cohorts has profound implications for classical Ricker stock-recruitment models, which assume a uniform response of a single cohort to density-dependent pressures. Our findings challenge this core assumption by revealing that final year-class strength can be determined by the internal dynamics between these cohorts. Therefore, a critical future direction for research is to use this new ecological understanding to build more sophisticated predictive tools.

In summary, our study suggests that the summer abundance of piscivorous intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch in Lipno Reservoir is likely to be strong when an abundance of YOY perch and ES intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch were higher, along with high densities of large cladocerans in July. Piscivorous intra-annual cohorts are far less abundant than the other intra-annual cohorts, but they have the highest probability of survival. When the ordinary intra-annual cohorts occur abundantly, there is still a possibility of the formation of a strong year class. Therefore, the absence of the piscivorous cohort does not automatically mean a poor

year class. The ES intra-annual cohort has no direct influence but indirectly regulates year-class strength. This finding can help managers in setting expectations. For example, strong year classes or good recruitment years should not be expected when the food supply for piscivorous YOY is scarce.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Data availability statement

All the datasets are provided with R code and will be available online upon the acceptance of the manuscript.

Authors' contributions

M. Tesfaye: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. **T. Jůza:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **M. Šmejkal:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **K. Soukalová;** Investigation. **P. Blabolil:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **D. Bartoň,** **M. Čech** and **V. Draščík:** Investigation. **J. Hejzlar:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **L. Kočvara,** **M. Muska** and **M. Prchalová:** Writing – review & editing. Investigation. **M. Říha,** **C. Martinez:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **K. Moraes Ribeiro,** **Z. Sajdllová:** Investigation. **R. Symonová:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **M. Tuser** and **M. Vašek:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **M. Brabec:** Formal analysis, Methodology, writing – review & editing. **J. Kubečka:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **A.T. Souza:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Supplementary material

Table S1. Delimitation of zooplankton size groups and their taxonomic composition.

Size class (group)	Species list
Cladocera 0–499 µm	<i>Alona</i> sp., <i>Chydorus sphaericus</i>
Cladocera 500–999 µm	<i>Bosmina</i> sp., <i>Ceriodaphnia</i> sp., <i>Pleuroxus aduncus</i>
Cladocera ±1,000 µm	<i>Eubosmina coregoni</i> , <i>Diaphanosoma</i> sp., <i>Ceriodaphnia quadrangula</i> , <i>Alona affinis</i>
Cladocera 1,001–1,700 µm	<i>Daphnia cucullata</i> , <i>D. ambigua</i> , <i>Holopedium gibberum</i>
Cladocera >1,700 µm	<i>Daphnia galeata</i> and hybrids, <i>D. longispina</i> gr. <i>Leptodora kindtii</i>
Copepoda 500–1,000 µm	<i>Mesocyclops</i> sp., <i>Thermocyclops</i> sp., <i>Diacyclops</i> sp., all copepoditt stages.
Copepoda 1,000–3,000 µm	Adult stages: <i>Acanthocyclops</i> sp., <i>Cyclops</i> sp.

Table S2. Number of tows conducted per year and total gillnet effort exerted during the study period (2003–2023) in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia.

Year	Number of trawls (NT)	Gill net area covered (GAC)
2003	24	5,580
2008	44	5,580
2009	31	5,580
2010	43	5,580
2012	31	5,220
2016	26	5,400
2017	29	5,400
2018	34	1,260
2019	37	5,400
2020	28	4,860
2021	28	2,040
2022	30	4,500
2023	28	5,100

Table S3. Comparison of model structures for the best-performing covariates (Cladocerans, young-of-the-year (YOY) perch, and extremely small pikeperch). Metrics include Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), corrected AIC (AICC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), coefficient of determination (R^2), and residual standard deviation (Sigma). The best-supported models are highlighted in bold, based on the lowest AIC/AICC/BIC values.

Density of Cladocera (>1,700 μm) (ind. dm^2) in July							
Model structure	Model Type	AIC	AICC	BIC	R^2	RMSE	Sigma
$\alpha_0 + f(\text{cladocerans}) + \epsilon$	GAM	56.82	71.47	60.26	0.95	1.35	1.73
$\beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{cladocerans})^2 + \epsilon$	Quadratic	74.96	77.62	76.65	0.76	3.43	3.73
$\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 * (\text{cladocerans}) + \epsilon$	Linear	85.09	87.76	86.79	0.52	5.07	5.51
The abundance of young of the year perch (per. ha^{-1})							
$\beta_0 + f(\text{perch}) + \epsilon$	GAM	60.03	68.59	62.85	0.93	1.66	1.99
$\beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{perch})^2 + \epsilon$	Quadratic	64.29	66.96	65.99	0.89	2.28	2.48
$\beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{perch}) + \epsilon$	Linear	77.92	80.59	79.62	0.72	3.85	4.18
The abundance of ES young of the year pikeperch (per. ha^{-1})							
$\beta_0 + f(\text{ES}) + \epsilon$	GAM	60.96	67.59	63.51	0.92	1.78	2.09
$\beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{ES})^2 + \epsilon$	Quadratic	76.87	79.54	78.57	0.72	3.69	4.02
$\beta_0 + \beta_1 * (\text{ES}) + \epsilon$	Linear	86.51	89.18	88.21	0.46	5.35	5.82

Note that: α_0 : Intercept $f(\cdot)$: Smooth function, ϵ : Error, β_0 : Intercept β_1 : Curvature term, γ_0 : Intercept γ_1 : Slope

Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Catch Per Unit Effort (CPUE) of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) spawning stock (individuals with a standard length >330 mm) and CPUE of adult predatory fish (European catfish (*Silurus glanis*), Northern pike (*Esox lucius*), pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*), European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*), and asp (*Aspius aspius*), with error bars representing the standard error observed among sampling sites during the study period (2003–2023) in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia.

Figure S2. The abundance of young of the year (YOY) European perch, ruffe, roach and bleak during the study period (2003–2023), Lipno Reservoir, Czechia.

Disentangling the drivers of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort and the contributions of three cohorts to early-year class strength in pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*)

Figure S3. The density of different size groups (in μm) of Cladocera (A), Copepoda and others (Nauplia, and Rotatoria) (B) covering the months relevant to seasonal dynamics of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*), during the study period (2003–2023), Lipno Reservoir, Czechia. Zooplankton species belonging to each size group are listed in Table S1.

Figure S4. The monthly average water temperature, monthly average transparency and monthly average concentration of chlorophyll-a during the study period (2003–2023), Lipno reservoir, Czechia.

Disentangling the drivers of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort and the contributions of three cohorts to early-year class strength in pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*)

Figure S5. Model diagnostics for the linear regression and GAM models assessed using the DHARMA package. The diagnostics include the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test for uniformity, dispersion test, outlier detection, and residuals vs. predicted values plot, comprehensively evaluating model fit and performance. (A) Diagnostic assessment of total YOY abundance against age 1+ fish. (B, C, and D) Diagnostics of the GAM relationships between large cladocerans, YOY perch, and the ES intra-annual cohort with the piscivorous intra-annual cohort.

CHAPTER 5

DISTINCT INTRA-COHORT RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN YOUNG-OF-THE-YEAR PIKEPERCH (*SANDER LUCIOPERCA*): EVIDENCE FROM DIET AND ISOTOPIC ANALYSIS

Tesfaye, M., Souza, A.T., Šmejkal, M., Jůza, T., Sajdlová, Z., Draštík, V., Kočvara, L., Symonová, R., Meador, T.B., Vašek, M., Kubečka, J., 2025. Distinct intra-cohort resource utilization in young-of-the-year pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*): evidence from diet and isotopic analysis. *Ecology and Evolution* 15, e71973. doi.org/10.1002/ece3.71973

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My share on this work was about 65% (Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing)

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Distinct Intra-Cohort Resource Utilization in Young-of-the-Year Pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*): Evidence From Diet and Isotopic Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Intraspecific competition is a fundamental selective force in animals, leading to various specializations that influence ecological interactions. Diet composition and trophic position at the early life stages substantially influence fish growth, survival, and recruitment success. Yet, most studies focus disproportionately on adult stages, leaving critical knowledge gaps in our understanding of early life history. To address this, we used young of the year (YOY) pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) as a model species and investigated the intraspecific interaction and degree of trophic partitioning between three intra-annual cohorts (extremely small (ES), ordinary and piscivorous YOYs) using stable isotope (SI) and gut content analysis (GCA). Analysis of SI metrics unveiled that an ontogenetic diet shift was linked to increasing body size, leading to significant trophic niche variation among intra-annual cohorts. The piscivorous cohort occupied the highest trophic position, followed by the ordinary and ES cohorts. There was no overlap in the isotopic niche between the intra-annual cohorts, considering the 40% standard ellipse area. The GCA showed two distinct feeding patterns: the ES cohort exclusively consumed zooplankton, while the ordinary cohort had a more diverse diet, feeding on zooplankton and benthic macroinvertebrates. The piscivorous cohort (≥ 80 mm) predominantly fed on their conspecifics and YOY perch (*Perca fluviatilis*). Our study demonstrates that YOY pikeperch intra-annual cohorts exhibit a broad size range and unique ontogenetic feeding patterns, with vital implications for population dynamics and ecological interactions. These differences are likely due to different hatching dates, environmental factors, and individual ability to become predatory. Furthermore, this work emphasizes the need for comparative studies to better understand trophic dynamics and uncover the ecological factors shaping the early life stages of fish.

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1 | Introduction

Density-dependent processes regulate individual fitness and population dynamics through intra- and interspecific competition and predation (Travis et al. 2023). These interactions often lead to changes in development, morphology, and habitat utilization and cause variations in trophic position within natural populations (Araújo et al. 2011; Bolnick et al. 2003). These variations may occur at any trophic level within a food web, eventually playing an important role in stabilizing the ecological dynamics (Guimerà et al. 2010). Competition for resources and predation can influence the degree of variation in the trophic niche position among individuals in a given population (Eklöv and Svanbäck 2006; Svanbäck et al. 2015; Svanbäck and Bolnick 2007). Particularly, intraspecific competition for food increases trophic niche variation among individuals by endorsing size-based diet shifts, habitat differentiation, and dietary specialization (Jones and Post 2016). This may reduce dietary and habitat overlaps among conspecifics or sympatric species, potentially alleviating predation pressure (Schirmer et al. 2020; Schoener 1974).

The trophic niche positions vary largely between species and individuals of the same species at different life stages, and this has been especially studied in older age classes in fishes (Costa-Pereira et al. 2018; Ru et al. 2022; Vejřík et al. 2023; Zhao et al. 2014). The extent and nature of these variations in the early life stages of a single species and how this relates to the trophic level of an individual in the food chain are far less well understood (Nunn et al. 2012; Sánchez-Hernández et al. 2022; Westrelin et al. 2023).

As animals grow, body size varies, leading to changes in metabolic needs, resource utilization, and susceptibility to predation (Akin and Winemiller 2008; Bousseba et al. 2024; Guimerà et al. 2010; Uphoff et al. 2019). During the first year of life, most freshwater fish undergo an ontogenetic diet shift, from small-sized zooplankton to other food sources such as plant material, macroinvertebrates, or fish (Huss et al. 2008; Qin et al. 2024; Sánchez-Hernández 2019; Souza et al. 2020). For the latter group of fishes, the switch to piscivory is energetically beneficial for growth and development as it provides energy-rich prey. Larger individuals in the group often make this dietary shift earlier than smaller individuals and achieve significantly faster growth, while smaller individuals that change their diet later may experience delayed growth (Frankiewicz et al. 1999; Persson and Brönmark 2008; van Densen et al. 1996). Small differences in the growth rate during the early phase of life can develop into large differences in the growth of individuals in later phases (Huss et al. 2008; Post 2003). Such differential growth has been observed in many piscivorous fish, including largemouth bass (*Micropterus salmoides*) (Zhao et al. 2014), walleye (*Stizostedion vitreum*) (Paradis et al. 2006; Uphoff et al. 2019), yellow perch (*Perca flavescens*) (Wu and Culver 1992), European perch (Heermann et al. 2007; Urbatzka et al. 2008), and pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) (Frankiewicz et al. 1999; Ginter et al. 2012a; Specziár 2005).

Pikeperch is a commercially valuable and ecologically important predatory fish in Eurasian water bodies; its role as a top

predator is crucial for regulating prey populations and the structure and function of food webs (Jakubavičiūtė et al. 2024; Tesfaye et al. 2023). It is a piscivorous specialist that undergoes one or two distinct ontogenetic diet shifts during its early developmental stages, starting with zooplanktivory, switching to benthivory, and/or ending as piscivory (Specziár 2005; Vašek et al. 2018; Westrelin et al. 2023). This ontogenetic shift is highly dependent on the size of the young of the year (YOY), the availability of suitable prey, and environmental conditions, and could have either a positive or negative effect on the recruitment success of the populations (Galarowicz et al. 2006; Trochine et al. 2022). A better understanding of the processes behind ontogenetic dietary changes is important for identifying and predicting recruitment success. This has implications for overall population and ecological dynamics and demonstrates the importance of understanding the trophic ecology of pikeperch in the early life stages for effective fisheries management and conservation of populations in an ever-changing environment.

Gut content analysis (GCA) and stable isotope analysis (SIA) are the two common methods for determining the structure of the food web, trophic interactions, and essential energy sources of consumers (Davis et al. 2012; Vašek et al. 2018). Gut content analysis (GCA) can provide comprehensive taxonomic information on recently ingested prey with its abundance and diversity (Akin and Winemiller 2008; Cobain et al. 2019; Gutmann Roberts and Britton 2018). At the same time, SIA captures resource utilization and trophic interactions and ultimately reflects feeding behavior and assimilated diet over time (Jackson et al. 2011; McCue et al. 2020; Šmejkal et al. 2024). Integrating these two complementary approaches improves our understanding and provides clearer information about dietary shifts, trophic ecology, and the co-existence of multiple size groups during the early life stages of fish.

The feeding ecology and ontogenetic diet shifts of YOY pikeperch have indeed been extensively studied (Frankiewicz et al. 1999; Ginter et al. 2012a, 2011; Persson and Brönmark 2008). A number of studies also investigated mechanisms beyond the ontogenetic diet shift, resulting in individual size variation in related fish species, such as perch (Heermann et al. 2007; Huss et al. 2008; Urbatzka et al. 2008) and walleye (Galarowicz et al. 2006; Schoenebeck et al. 2024; Uphoff et al. 2019). However, many of these studies lack empirical evidence and are primarily experimental. Furthermore, in addition to the distinct intra-annual cohorts of YOY pikeperch previously identified (ordinary pelagic and littoral piscivorous) (Frankiewicz et al. 1999, 1996; van Densen 1985; van Densen et al. 1996), a newly described extremely small YOY appears to be abundant in freshwater systems (Júza et al. 2013; Tesfaye et al. 2024). This suggests the presence of multiple intra-annual cohorts in some years, highlighting the need for further investigation into their dietary adaptations, ontogenetic diet shifts, and intra-specific interactions among YOY individuals.

Our study aims to explore intraspecific interactions and the degree of trophic partitioning among conspecifics of YOY pikeperch using GCA and SIA. Specifically, we hypothesized that (i) the diet composition of YOY pikeperch differs among intra-annual cohorts, with larger individuals exhibiting a broader

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FIGURE 1 | Map of the study area in the Lipno Reservoir, Czechia. (A) Sampling locations within the reservoir. Light green shaded circles indicate the sites for benthic gillnet sampling, while the black line represents the longitudinal transect for pelagic trawling. (B) Map showing the location of Czechia (highlighted in black) within Europe.

dietary niche and higher trophic positions due to their increased size and access to a broader range of prey. In comparison, smaller individuals are expected to show a narrower dietary niche, reflecting size-related constraints on prey selection, and we expect a certain degree of overlap in the isotopic position. Further, we hypothesized that (ii) intraspecific competition among the YOY individuals drives trophic niche partitioning, facilitating coexistence and promoting individual specialization.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Study Site

Lipno Reservoir is a shallow, eutrophic, and large water body in the South Bohemian region of Czechia (Figure 1). It has a water volume of 306 million m^3 , a surface area of 46.5 km^2 , a maximum depth of 22 m, a mean depth of 6.6 m, a shoreline length of 115 km, and a mean water residence time of 0.6 years (Krolová et al. 2013, 2012). The reservoir was constructed between 1952 and 1959 by damming the Vltava River with the aim of providing multifunctional purposes: hydropower generation, flood protection, flow augmentation, and recreational activities (Krolová et al. 2012). Despite its eutrophic classification, mean water transparency, as measured by Secchi depth, is around 2 m, and mean chlorophyll-a concentration is $18 \mu g L^{-1}$ (Tesfaye et al. 2023). The system is also subject to significant water level fluctuations driven by its management for hydropower and flood control (Krolová et al. 2013). Previous studies have shown that the fish community in the reservoir consists mainly of cyprinids (white bream *Blicca bjoerkna*, bleak *Alburnus alburnus*, roach *Rutilus rutilus* and freshwater bream *Abramis brama*). The most common predatory species include the adult European perch *Perca fluviatilis*, pikeperch, Northern pike *Esox lucius*, and the European catfish *Silurus glanis* (De Moraes et al. 2023).

2.2 | Field Sampling and Sample Processing

Fish were sampled at the end of August 2023 using gillnets and trawling. These two methods were opted to account for the two main habitats of the reservoir, benthic and pelagic. Piscivorous YOY inhabit the benthic part of the reservoir and cannot be effectively sampled using pelagic trawling (Symonová et al. 2024). To sample this intra-annual cohort, we employed multimesh gillnets with 12 mesh sizes, following the European standard EN 14757, supplemented by four additional larger mesh sizes (70, 90, 110, and 135 mm) (for details of the gillnet sampling, see Šmejkal et al. 2015). Gillnets were set before sunset and retrieved after sunrise to capture the peak periods of fish activity (Prchalová et al. 2010). All captured fish were identified to the species level. Their standard length (SL) was measured to the nearest millimeter. Following Symonová et al. (2024), we defined piscivorous YOY as individuals with a standard length (SL) of ≥ 80 mm; the age of these fish (0+) was then further confirmed through otolith readings. These individuals were then selected for further analysis. In addition, their abundance was expressed as catch per unit of effort (CPUE), that is, individuals caught per 1000 m^2 of multimesh gillnets per night. Pelagic trawling with a fixed frame of a $3 \times 3 = 9 m^2$ mouth opening (as described in Jůza and Kubečka 2007) was employed to sample pelagic YOY pikeperch. The mesh size of the trawl was 6.5 mm knot to knot in the belly and 4 mm in the cod end. The lower part of the frame was equipped with two 15 kg iron slides to keep the trawl weighted down and protect it from potential contact with the bottom. An accessory boat was attached to the upper rim to ensure the trawl remained at the desired depth (Jůza et al. 2018). A rope was attached between the boat and the frame for deeper tows, so we sampled the layers of 0–3, 3–6, 6–9, and 9–12 m. The trawl was towed at night 100 m behind the boat at approximately $1 m s^{-1}$. Each haul lasted 10 min.

TABLE 1 | Summary from randomly selected samples of stable isotope and gut content analysis from each of the three intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) from Lipno Reservoir, Czechia, including sample size (*n*) and standard length (SL) statistics (mm).

Intra-annual cohorts	No. of individuals (<i>n</i>)	Mean SL (mm)	SD (mm)	Size range SL (mm)
Extremely small	20	19.60	2.11	13.50–24.00
Ordinary	20	51.90	6.66	38.00–72.00
Piscivorous	20	99.00	11.33	81.00–115.00

Twenty-eight hauls were conducted, covering all available depth strata at a given location. The trawl was kept on a slightly curved path during all hauls to avoid disturbing the sampling areas by the towing vessel. The SL of each fish was measured to the nearest millimeter. A sample of dorsal muscle was taken for fish with an SL above 40 mm. For fish with an SL below 40 mm, the entire gutted body, excluding the head (due to the small size of the sampled individuals), was stored at -20°C until further processing for stable isotope analysis. The digestive tracts of all pikeperch captured were dissected and preserved in a 10% formaldehyde solution for later GCA.

We explored the structure of size distribution of YOY pikeperch sampled using trawling and benthic gillnets and performed a multimodality test following the approach described in Tesfaye et al. (unpublished manuscript). As outlined in Tesfaye et al. (unpublished manuscript), the size distribution of YOY pikeperch can exhibit unimodal, bimodal, or trimodal patterns, with trimodality occurring less frequently. Therefore, a multimodality test was necessary. Initial detection of multimodal size distributions was conducted using the dip.test function from the diptest R package (Maechler 2024). Additionally, trimodality tests were performed using the modetest function from the multimode R package (Ameijeiras-Alonso et al. 2021).

2.3 | Gut Content Analysis

In the laboratory, the digestive tracts of 60 individuals were dissected and examined under a stereomicroscope. Prey items were identified to the lowest practical taxonomic level and counted, and their volumetric contribution to the total stomach content was visually estimated (Hyslop 1980). When possible, characteristic remains (e.g., fish bones and invertebrate exoskeleton fragments) were used to identify partially digested prey items.

2.4 | Stable Isotope Analysis

Sixty YOY pikeperch samples, the same individuals analyzed for gut content analysis (GCA), were also subjected to stable isotope analysis (SIA) (Table 1). The muscle samples or eviscerated bodies without heads in the case of the extremely small intra-annual cohort were dried at 60°C for 48 h, then pulverized into a fine powder, homogenized with a mixer mill MM 200 (Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany), and filled into tin capsules for weighing, which were then packed for isotope analyses. The stable isotopic ratios of carbon and nitrogen in the pikeperch samples were determined at the Soil and Water Research Infrastructure, Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences (České Budějovice, Czechia) using a MAT253 Plus isotope ratio mass

spectrometer coupled to an elemental analyzer (EA Isolink CNSOH) via a Conflo IV interface (all equipment from Thermo Scientific, Bremen, Germany). Samples were analyzed together with the international reference material IAEA-600 and an in-house fish muscle working standard. Results were reported in conventional delta notation, normalized to the international reference scale ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ -VPDB and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -air ‰). Repeated measurements of the reference standards indicated that the precision was $<0.2\text{‰}$ and $<0.3\text{‰}$ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, respectively.

2.5 | Statistical Analyses

To examine differences in the volumetric proportions of prey categories in the digestive tracts of individuals between intra-annual cohorts, we conducted a Permutational Multivariate Analysis of Variance (PERMANOVA) using the adonis2 function from the vegan R package (Oksanen et al. 2007). This was followed by post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA comparisons using the pairwise.adonis function from the pairwiseAdonis R package (Martinez Arbizu 2020) to identify specific differences between the intra-annual cohorts.

For stable isotope analysis, PERMANOVA was also performed to examine whether the occupied isotopic niches differed significantly between the intra-annual cohorts. After confirming significance, post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA comparisons were performed to determine whether the observed differences were due to the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (Balzani et al. 2024).

The isotopic niche size of each intra-annual cohort of YOY pikeperch was estimated in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ – $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ space using standard ellipse areas (40% EA). This metric provides a bivariate measure of the distribution of individuals in isotopic space, with the ellipse including the mean 40% of the data, representing the typical resource utilization of the intra-annual cohort of YOY (Jackson et al. 2011). Additionally, the 95% ellipse area (95% EA) was plotted, serving as a bivariate equivalent of the 95% confidence interval encompassing 95% of the sample (Layman and Allgeier 2012).

The percentage of overlap between intra-annual cohorts was calculated as two overlapping ellipse areas (Bayesian 40% or 95% EA) divided by the sum of the ellipse areas of the two annual cohorts intra-annual cohorts multiplied by 100, based on the equation of Stasko et al. (2015). This percentage was computed for each posterior draw of the Bayesian estimates of overlap and ellipse areas, producing a distribution with 1000 iterative draws using the SIBER package (Jackson et al. 2011). Furthermore, the directional pairwise probability of an individual from one intra-annual cohort falling into the niche of another one was

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estimated at the 95% Bayesian ellipse area. This estimation was performed using the nicheROVER package (Lysy et al. 2023) with a Monte Carlo simulation of 10,000 iterations.

Based on Layman et al. (2007), six isotopic niche metrics were calculated to assess the potential difference between intra-annual cohorts: the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range (NR) and the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ range (CR) as differences between the most enriched and the most depleted individual, the mean Euclidean distance of each individual from the centroid of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (CD), the mean nearest neighbor distance in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ space (NND) and its standard deviation (SDNND). Additional isotopic niche metrics were computed to quantify and compare trophic niche dimensions among the three intra-annual cohorts: Total Area (TA), which represents the total area of the convex hull encompassing all data points in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ isotopic space and provides a measure of the overall niche width; Standard Ellipse Area (SEA), which estimates the core isotopic niche area by excluding outliers and is less sensitive to sample size compared to TA; and Corrected Standard Ellipse Area (SEAc), a bias-corrected version of SEA adjusted for small sample sizes to ensure robust comparisons across groups (Jackson et al. 2011).

All statistical analyses and figures were generated using R version 4.4.2 (R Core Team 2023) with the R packages tidyverse (Wickham et al. 2019), SIBER (Jackson et al. 2011) and nicheROVER (Lysy et al. 2023).

3 | Results

3.1 | Size Distribution of Young of the Year Pikeperch

The size distribution analysis of YOY pikeperch, sampled by trawling and benthic gillnets, revealed a clear trimodal size structure ($D=0.055$, $p<0.001$; Figure 2), providing strong evidence for the presence of three distinct intra-annual cohorts in

FIGURE 2 | Length frequency of all young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) captured by trawl (shaded by light blue) and benthic gillnets (shaded by white) in LipnoReservoir, Czechia. The dotted line indicates the cutoff length among the intra-annual cohorts.

the size distribution. Pelagic intra-annual cohorts, that is, the ES and ordinary fingerlings, were generally more abundant than littoral piscivores in August of their first year of life (Figure 2).

3.2 | Gut Content Analyses

A total of 60 non-empty stomachs were analyzed, and the data showed distinct ontogenetic dietary shifts and differential use of prey resources by YOY pikeperch conspecifics. The statistical results showed a strong significant difference in the prey composition among the three intra-annual cohorts (PERMANOVA: $R^2=0.565$, $F_{3,35}=15.165$, $p<0.001$). Specifically, the extremely small intra-annual cohort differed significantly from the ordinary (post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA: $F=267.57$, $p<0.001$, $R^2=0.87$) and piscivorous intra-annual cohorts (post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA: $F=1033.89$, $p<0.001$, $R^2=0.96$). The ordinary intra-annual cohort differed significantly from the piscivorous intra-annual cohort ($F_{\text{mod}}=15.39$, $p<0.001$, $R^2=0.30$). Extremely small YOY pikeperch (ES, <37.5 mm) fed exclusively on zooplankton such as *Leptodora kindtii*, *Diaphanosoma brachyurum*, *Daphnia* sp., Diaptomidae, and Cyclopidae, whereas the ordinary YOY pikeperch consumed both zooplankton, mainly *L. kindtii*, and benthic macroinvertebrates, such as chironomid larvae. On the other hand, piscivorous YOY pikeperch preyed nearly exclusively on YOY fish, including pikeperch, perch, and other species (Figure 3). The large cladoceran *L. kindtii* was the most important food for ES and ordinary intra-annual cohorts, contributing more than 75% of the diet volume.

3.3 | Stable Isotope Analyses

3.3.1 | Differences in Isotopic Niches Between YOY Intra-Annual Cohorts

The isotopic niches of individuals belonging to the three intra-annual cohorts showed significant differences in their $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (PERMANOVA: $F_{2,57}=130.77$, $R^2=0.82$, $p<0.001$) and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (PERMANOVA: $F_{2,57}=343.65$, $R^2=0.92$, $p<0.001$) values. Individuals from the piscivorous intra-annual cohort had the highest $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, followed by the ordinary and extremely small cohorts, and the three intra-annual cohorts differed significantly in their mean $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (Table 2, Figure 4). In terms of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, extremely small YOY pikeperch had the highest values and differed significantly from individuals belonging to the ordinary (post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA: $F=350.34$, $R^2=0.90$, $p<0.001$) and piscivorous (post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA: $F=1860.03$, $R^2=0.97$, $p<0.001$) intra-annual cohorts, while there was no significant difference observed between piscivorous and ordinary intra-annual cohorts (post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA: $F=2.74$, $R^2=0.067$, $p>0.05$; Table 2, Figure 4).

3.3.2 | Niche Sizes and Overlaps

The niche metrics varied between the three intra-annual cohorts. The isotopic niche size of the extremely small and piscivorous intra-annual cohorts was relatively narrow. In contrast, the ordinary intra-annual cohort exhibited a larger isotopic niche (Figure 5). The niche width (proxied by TA, SEA and

FIGURE 3 | The average number of prey and relative volumetric proportions (%) of major prey items identified in the stomachs of the three intra-annual cohorts of young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) during the study period in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia.

TABLE 2 | Results of post hoc pairwise PERMANOVA analysis.

Comparison between intra-annual cohorts	Isotopic element	F-model	R ²	p
Extremely small—Ordinary	δ ¹⁵ N	70.48	0.65	<0.001****
	δ ¹³ C	350.34	0.90	<0.001****
Extremely small—Piscivorous	δ ¹⁵ N	355.54	0.90	<0.001****
	δ ¹³ C	1860.0	0.98	<0.001****
Ordinary—Piscivorous	δ ¹⁵ N	45.80	0.54	<0.001****
	δ ¹³ C	2.73	0.067	0.108

Note: Significant differences were detected in both δ¹⁵N and δ¹³C values among the intra-annual cohorts (extremely small, ordinary, and piscivorous YOYs). Pairwise comparisons were conducted to evaluate the differences between the three groups. Significance: ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05, = not significant.

FIGURE 4 | Isotopic niches of the three intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia, 40% standard ellipse area for three intra-annual cohorts (darker shading) and 95% ellipse area (lighter shading). Solid lines = ellipse areas.

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FIGURE 5 | Posterior distribution of niche size estimates for the three young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) intra-annual cohorts in Lipno Reservoir, Czechia. Niche size is calculated from Bayesian posterior samples of μ (mean) and Σ (covariance matrix) using a 95% credible interval, modeled with nicheROVER package (Lysy et al. 2023).

TABLE 3 | Summary of isotopic niche metrics for the three intra-annual cohorts of young-of-the-year pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) from Lipno Reservoir, Czechia.

Isotopic niche metrics	Extremely small	Ordinary	Piscivorous
TA	2.19	7.47	1.79
SEA	0.70	2.38	0.76
SEAc	0.74	2.51	0.80

Note: Metrics include TA (Total Area), SEA (Standard Ellipse Area), and SEAc (Corrected Standard Ellipse Area), which quantify and compare trophic niche dimensions in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ - $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ isotopic space.

SEAc) of the ordinary intra-annual cohort is more than three times higher than that of the piscivorous and extremely small intra-annual cohorts (Table 3). The metrics for niche dispersion (i.e., CD, NND and SDNND) also showed similar patterns and were all higher in the ordinary intra-annual cohort (Table 4).

Bayesian overlap analysis (40% of ellipse area) showed no overlap between isotopic niches of intra-annual cohorts. However, a minor overlap in the isotopic niche between the ordinary and piscivorous intra-annual cohorts was observed (1.9% and 0% at 95% and 40% ellipse area, respectively). The Bayesian directional niche overlap analysis results suggested that the probability of individuals ($\alpha=95\%$) of the ordinary intra-annual cohort entering the piscivorous intra-annual cohort niche was 10.3%; vice versa, it was 31.0% (Table 5).

4 | Discussion

Both GCA and SIA suggested a clear ontogenetic dietary shift and isotopic niche segregation between YOY pikeperch in the

TABLE 4 | Layman's metrics for isotopic niches of extremely small, ordinary, and piscivorous young of the year pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) intra-annual cohorts from Lipno Reservoir, Czechia.

Intra-annual cohorts	CR	NR	CD	NND	SDNND
Extremely small	1.70	1.86	0.60	0.22	0.23
Ordinary	5.78	2.96	1.27	0.50	0.46
Piscivorous	1.91	1.53	0.66	0.21	0.17

Abbreviations: CD, mean distance to the centroid; CR, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ range; NND, mean nearest neighbor distance; NR, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ range; SDNND, standard deviation of nearest neighbor distance.

studied reservoir. So far, limited information on resource use and partitioning among YOY pikeperch individuals has been available (Persson and Brönmark 2008; Specziár 2005). The current study is also the first to apply the SIA approach and the conventional GCA method to characterize the dietary niches of the co-existing pikeperch intra-annual cohorts. Thus, the findings of this study provide important insights into the trophic ecology of predatory fish populations and their roles in freshwater food webs.

4.1 | Size Distribution and Ontogenetic Dietary Shift

The distribution of the size of YOY pikeperch showed a clear trimodality. Indeed, previous studies in the same ecosystem found the occurrence of trimodality in the YOY pikeperch in some of the years (Tesfaye et al. unpublished manuscript). Several factors have been suggested by earlier studies that could lead to the formation of a broad size distribution, eventually leading to a multi-modal size distribution: (i) asynchronous hatching or spawning period (Huss et al. 2007; Post 2003; Jůza et al. 2013), (ii) prey availability and suitability (Tesfaye et al. 2024; Zorn et al. 2020), and (iii) environmental variability (climatic conditions during the first growing season) (Deboer et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2017). All these factors together may lead to size-dependent foraging and competition, as well as cannibalism/piscivory (Frankiewicz et al. 1999; Huss et al. 2008).

Our study confirmed the hypothesis (H1) that the development of a broad size distribution was coupled with partitioning in the diet between YOY pikeperch intra-annual cohort and differences in hatching time. Indeed, it is well documented that pikeperch spawns in spring, typically starting in February and ending in June near its southern and northern distribution limits, respectively (Lappalainen et al. 2003). However, our recent investigation of ES fingerlings, using daily otolith ring analysis, revealed that summer spawning also occurs (unpublished data), which could be an additional factor that contributed to the observed broad range of size distribution. We observed two distinct ontogenetic diet shifts in the YOY pikeperch. In the first stage, ES intra-annual cohort (10–34 mm) fed mainly on larger crustaceans such as *L. kindtii*, *D. brachyurum*, *Daphnia* sp., Diaptomidae, and Cyclopidae. Previous studies have made

TABLE 5 | Ellipse areas (EA) and isotopic niche overlaps for 40% and 95% of niche regions.

Intra-annual cohorts	40% EA overlap				95% EA overlap				P of ind. overlap at 95%					
	40% EA		Extremely small		Extremely small		Ordinary		Extremely small		Ordinary		Piscivorous	
	40% EA	Extremely small	Ordinary	Piscivorous	95% EA	Extremely small	Ordinary	Piscivorous	Extremely small	Ordinary	Piscivorous	Extremely small	Ordinary	Piscivorous
Extremely small	0.76	—	0.00	0.00	4.44	—	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	NA	0.00	0.00
Ordinary	0.26	0.00	—	0.00	15.01	0.00	—	1.93	0.00	1.93	0	0	NA	10.28
Piscivorous	0.82	0.00	0.00	—	4.80	0.00	1.93	—	0.00	—	0	0	31.22	NA

Note: The EA and overlaps were calculated using Bayesian posterior probability distributions with the R package SIBER (Jackson et al. 2011). The directional probability of individual overlap at 95% confidence (P of ind. overlap at 95%) into the niche of other intra-annual cohorts was calculated using the R package nicheROVER (Lysy et al. 2023).

similar observations in which similarly sized YOY pikeperch fed exclusively on larger zooplankton (Specziár 2005).

In the second stage, ordinary YOY, with an intermediate size of 37–80 mm, continued feeding on planktonic crustaceans and consumed benthic macroinvertebrates such as Chironomidae. Previous studies have similarly reported relatively high consumption of chironomids by YOY pikeperch of this size class in various water bodies (Araújo et al. 2011; Kakareko 2002; Peterka et al. 2003; Specziár 2011; Verreth and Kleyn 1987). Studies on related species (i.e., walleye) demonstrated that intermediate-size YOY fed on large calanoids and gained an energetic advantage, promoting improved growth and development of sufficient gape size to transition to piscivory (Uphoff et al. 2019). It is important to note that *L. kindtii* accounts for more than 75% of the diet of both pelagic groups (ES and ordinary intra-annual cohorts), which is consistent with earlier reports of pelagic YOY pikeperch feeding predominantly on *L. kindtii* (Ginter et al. 2012b; Peterka et al. 2003; Specziár 2005).

The subsequent ontogenetic diet shift to piscivory was linked with the intra-annual cohort size class ranging from 80 to 160 mm, and GCA revealed that they primarily consumed their conspecifics and YOY perch. Previous studies have also shown that larger YOY pikeperch individuals inhabiting littoral habitats fed mainly on fish prey (Frankiewicz et al. 1999; Ginter et al. 2012a). Prey fish served as the main food resource for this intra-annual cohort and may have contributed to fast growth; this phenomenon was also described for other percid species, such as YOY walleye and perch (Huss et al. 2008; Uphoff et al. 2019). Over one-third of the prey fish ingested by piscivorous YOY pikeperch were unidentifiable at the species level, despite pikeperch swallowing their prey without chewing them. Therefore, it is possible that the contribution of percid fish to the diet of the piscivorous YOY pikeperch intra-annual cohort may be even higher.

The shortage of potential prey fish can delay the dietary shift to piscivory. This ultimately leads to a reduction in the abundance of piscivorous individuals and, in turn, affects the population size of the adult pikeperch because the dietary shift plays a key role in accelerating growth and reducing winter mortality due to starvation and size-related predation (Huss et al. 2008). Based on our GCA result and previous studies, the co-occurrence of the three intra-annual cohorts in the same year was mainly determined by the characteristics and availability of a prey supply of suitable size and optimal environmental conditions (Frankiewicz et al. 1996; van Densen et al. 1996). The size spectra of a potential prey must overlap with the prey window defined by the predator's morphological, physiological, and behavioral capabilities (Galarowicz et al. 2006; Graeb et al. 2005; Persson and Brönmark 2002). If there is a mismatch between the size spectra of the predator and its prey, relatively fewer YOY pikeperch individuals switch to piscivory, and a majority stay either as ES or ordinary YOY (Frankiewicz et al. 1996; Sutela and Hyva 2002; van Densen 1985). Alternatively, there is a high probability that three intra-annual cohorts co-exist if water temperatures in spring and summer are optimal and there is a match in size spectra between predators and their prey (Bopp et al. 2023; Brandt et al. 2022; Sánchez-Hernández 2024).

4.2 | Trophic Interactions Between ES, Ordinary, and Piscivorous Intra-Annual Cohorts

The ES intra-annual cohort had higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values than ordinary and piscivorous intra-annual cohorts. This pronounced difference in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values between ES and ordinary fingerlings is due to the shorter lifetime and feeding period in ES fingerlings. This intra-annual cohort likely originated from later spawning events, and because small organisms have a higher metabolic rate and, thereby, faster isotopic turnover in their tissues, their isotopic composition integrates dietary intake over a relatively shorter time frame compared to larger individuals. Zooplankton $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values typically increase seasonally due to enhanced primary production, which reduces the discrimination against the heavier carbon isotope by algae (Woodland et al. 2012; Yoshioka et al. 1994). The higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values observed in ES fingerlings in the current study likely reflect their reliance on zooplankton during late summer, when the base of the pelagic food chain had very probably elevated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values. In contrast, the lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the earlier plankton bloom are integrated into the diet of the other two intra-annual cohorts (Hobson et al. 2012; Wada 2009).

Relative $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values are an indicator of the trophic position of the species (Post 2002; Westrelin et al. 2023), and these differed significantly between the three intra-annual cohorts. The piscivorous intra-annual cohort had higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, indicating that this group occupied a higher trophic position, followed by the ordinary and ES intra-annual cohorts, which occupied the intermediate and lower trophic positions, respectively. The observed increase in trophic position with size is consistent with previous studies (Linzmaier et al. 2018; Vašek et al. 2018; Westrelin et al. 2023), and corresponds to the dietary shift from zooplanktivores to benthivores and finally to piscivores, which can reduce intraspecific competition between intra-annual cohorts and increase the magnitude of niche partitioning between intra-annual and intra-annual cohorts (Ginter et al. 2011; Svanbäck and Bolnick 2007; Vašek et al. 2018; Westrelin et al. 2023). Similar observations have been reported in YOY northern pike, where the trophic position increased due to a shift towards greater importance of littoral prey, and individuals could differ by up to two trophic levels, reducing intraspecific competition (Beaudoin et al. 1999).

4.3 | Intraspecific Niche Partitioning Between ES, Ordinary, and Piscivorous Intra-Annual Cohorts

Based on our results, the ordinary intra-annual cohort showed a wider isotopic niche area (SEAc 40% and 95%) and increased trophic diversity among individuals (CD) than the ES and piscivorous intra-annual cohorts, which could be related to their high abundance among intra-annual cohorts. As reflected in our GCA result, another possible explanation could be that the ordinary intra-annual cohorts had a more diverse diet, being in a transitional phase from zooplanktivores to piscivores (Symonová et al. 2024), which could have increased the size of the isotopic niche. Similar to our study, a previous study has reported an increase in isotopic niche divergence due to higher densities in YOY pikeperch, indicating a

possible intraspecific competition in which the pikeperch adjusts its trophic niche according to the density of its conspecifics (Westrelin et al. 2023).

The isotopic niches of the three intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch showed no overlap (considering 40% SEAc) or only a moderate degree of overlap, that is, 0%–31% (considering 95% SEAc). The ordinary intra-annual cohort did not overlap with the ES intra-annual cohort but showed moderate overlap with the piscivorous sub-cohort. These results support the hypothesis that intraspecific competition among the three YOY intra-annual cohorts drives trophic niche partitioning, facilitating coexistence and promoting individual specialization.

The foregoing theory suggests that individuals living together might consume different food resources, leading to individual diet variation for several reasons (Araújo et al. 2011; Stephens and Krebs 1986). Our study has shown that ontogenetic diet shifts and body size variation cause the marked differences in diet and isotopic niche between intra-annual cohorts of YOY pikeperch. The ontogenetic dietary shift of YOY pikeperch from zooplankton to macroinvertebrates and then to fish reflects size-dependent changes in prey preferences. Studies have shown that an increase in size due to better growth rates can be caused by a switch to more profitable food resources (Sánchez-Hernández 2019). As demonstrated in our study, individuals that become piscivores are almost three times larger than those of their ES conspecifics and twice as large as those of the ordinary sub-cohort, and individuals of the ordinary intra-annual cohort are also twice as large as those of their ES conspecifics that may not switch to piscivory (Tesfaye et al. unpublished manuscript). Furthermore, differences in habitat utilization and resource competition exacerbate these size differences, with pelagic and littoral groups exploiting distinct prey types (Franz et al. 2002; Trochine et al. 2022). These factors collectively stress the dynamic foraging ecology of YOY pikeperch in their first year of life and have huge implications for population and community ecological dynamics (Nunn et al. 2012).

4.4 | Implications for Recruitment Success, Population and Ecological Dynamics

The recruitment success of many fish species is positively related to their size (growth) and successful dietary shift at an early stage of their life (Fuiman and Higgs 1997; Nunn et al. 2010), which may ultimately influence the lifetime fitness of individual fish, population dynamics, and other size-dependent processes (Huss et al. 2013; Post 2003). Persson and Brönmark (2002) pointed out that the recruitment success of pikeperch depends mainly on the timing of the ontogenetic switch to the piscivorous intra-annual cohort in the first year. A higher density of piscivorous individuals could lead to and contribute to strong year-class strength, as this intra-annual cohort can better cope with winter starvation and size-related predation mortality. On the other hand, a lower density of piscivorous pikeperch could lead to weaker year-class strength and ultimately prevent the potential role of pikeperch in regulating fish density in the food web and influencing ecological dynamics (Leeuwen et al. 2014).

Ontogenetic diet shifts in fish play a crucial role in shaping ecological dynamics by enabling resource partitioning and promoting the coexistence of sympatric predatory species (Huss et al. 2013; Sánchez-Hernández 2019; Westrelin et al. 2023). As previous studies have shown, predatory fishes like YOY pikeperch, perch, and northern pike initially feed on zooplankton, resulting in direct competition with each other and numerous other planktivores. However, as they grow, their diet shifts to macroinvertebrates and fish, leading to a reduction in the overlap between each other. Furthermore, the diet and habitat shift leads to a redistribution of predation pressure across different prey groups and habitats, contributes to an efficient transfer of biomass and energy, increases the stability of the trophic web, and supports the resilience of the ecosystem (Caskenette and Mccann 2017; Sánchez-Hernández 2019).

5 | Conclusion

This study provides empirical evidence for the two distinct ontogenetic dietary shifts and isotopic niche partitioning between YOY pikeperch conspecifics and their crucial role in shaping population and ecological dynamics. Previous studies documented the discontinuous size distribution of YOY pikeperch in some years in temperate lakes or reservoirs and explained the possible mechanisms beyond the occurrence of discontinuous size distribution. However, our study combined the results of GCA and SIA and provided direct evidence that a broad size range of young of the year, driven by the variation in the diet sources, resulted in trophic niche partitioning between intra-annual cohorts as a vital response to intraspecific competition for resources and facilitates coexistence and promotes individual specialization. Finally, it is important to note that there may be variations between years in diet and isotopic position among YOY intra-annual cohorts. Also, the presence of three distinct intra-annual cohorts is not always guaranteed. This particular year provided a unique opportunity to investigate diet and isotopic partitioning among the three intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch.

Author Contributions

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Kubečka: conceptualization (equal), funding acquisition (lead), investigation (lead), methodology (lead), project administration (lead), resources (lead), software (equal), supervision (lead), validation (supporting), writing – review and editing (supporting).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

All the required data are uploaded as Data S1.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Data S1:** ece371973-sup-0001-DataS1.xlsx.

CHAPTER 6

ASSESSING THE CONTRIBUTION OF ARTIFICIALLY STOCKED PIKEPERCH TO THE POPULATION USING OTOLITH MICRO-ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION

Souza, A.T., Tesfaye, M., Soukalová, K., Šmejkal, M., Ďurišová, J., Svojtka, M., Kubečka, J. Assessing the contribution of artificially stocked pikeperch to the population using otolith micro-elemental composition. (manuscript)

My share on this work was about 40% (Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, writing—writing, review and editing)

Assessing the contribution of artificially stocked pikeperch to the population using otolith micro-elemental composition

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Abstract

Fish stocking is a common management practice used to mitigate the effects of overfishing and other threats to wild fish populations. It is mainly employed in freshwater ecosystems with complex and variable strategies (different timings, fish lengths, and origins), making its effectiveness challenging to assess. To assess the prevalence of artificially stocked individuals in a population with a complex management history (pikeperch – *Stizostedion lucioperca* – from Lipno reservoir, Czechia), laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) was used to measure the micro-elemental composition at the core of otoliths to verify the natal origin of fish (wild and stocked individuals) and more specifically, to confirm the origin of the fish sources (facilities). Nine out of the ten elements investigated: Ba/Ca, Cu/Ca, K/Ca, Li/Ca, Mg/Ca, Mn/Ca, Na/Ca, Rb/Ca, and Sr/Ca showed significant differences between wild pikeperch and those sourced from different hatchery facilities. A machine learning classification algorithm, trained with data from 100 fish of known origin, was used to classify 70 fish of unknown origin captured in the lake. The five most relevant variables for correctly classifying the fish origins were Rb/Ca, Li/Ca, Sr/Ca, Ba/Ca, and Mg/Ca. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 99%, with 97% accuracy for wild fish and 100% for introduced fish. Regarding identifying the exact origin or sources of the fish, the overall accuracy for stocking facilities was approximately 89%, with individual facility accuracy ranging from 28% to 100%. The model determined that most of the fish of unknown origin as autochthonous (57 individuals, 81.4%), with a smaller proportion being stocked fish (13 individuals, 18.6%). Due to the relatively small contribution of stocked fish to the pikeperch population, the efficiency of the stocking program should be further scrutinized to avoid pursuing management strategies that are neither efficient nor beneficial for the fish stock.

Key-words: LA-ICP-MS, freshwater, lake, metapopulation, mixed-stock, restocking, *Stizostedion lucioperca*

1. Introduction

In ecology, a population is a group of individuals of the same species that inhabit a defined geographical area at a given time and interact via biological processes (Mittelbach and McGill, 2019; Begon and Townsend, 2020; Cadrin, 2020). However, populations are rarely homogenous; they exhibit heterogeneity in traits such as habitat use, genetic diversity, and migratory behaviour, driven by ecological gradients or localized adaptation (Hanski and Simberloff, 1997; Laikre et al., 2005; Schtickzelle and Quinn, 2007; Lindley et al., 2011; Nevado et al., 2013; Ferri and Matic-Skoko, 2021). This heterogeneity can divide populations into semi-independent sub-units known as local populations (biological populations), and through interaction, the sub-units form a metapopulation (Cadrin et al., 2013; Hanski and Simberloff, 1997). In open ecosystems, multiple ecological and environmental processes can trigger ecological interaction and genetic connectivity among local populations, thereby enhancing resilience (Hawkins et al., 2016).

In fisheries science, the term “stock” is widely used, and this term refers to a biological population or metapopulations, a portion of a population, or multiple populations (Cadrin et al., 2013). Fish stock identification is a cornerstone of effective fisheries management and conservation and has multifaceted benefits (Begg and Waldman, 1999; Hammer and Zimmermann, 2004; Begg and Cadrin, 2016). It provides information about the stock structure and dynamics, geographic boundaries, and migration patterns, which can serve as input for sustainable fisheries management (Secor, 2013).

Globally, fish stocking, also known as supplementation, propagation, culture-based fisheries, or aquaculture-aided enhancements (Lorenzen et al., 2021), has been taking place in different inland water bodies with multiple objectives, from maintaining the natural population or increasing catches to the conservation and restoration of a particular species (Cowx, 1994; Arlinghaus et al., 2016). Several fish stocking programs have been implemented in many countries, spending hundreds of millions of dollars and euros to satisfy the angler’s demands and/or prevent over-exploitation (Cowx., 1994; Lorenzen et al., 2012). However, introducing fish from exogenous sources into a wild stock (natural population) can alter the stock structure, given that stocked fish can be from single or multiple sources, being introduced at varying ages and sizes, reared under different conditions, and released in other locations and at various times (Specziár and Turcsányi, 2014, 2017; Barrow et al., 2021; Guillerault et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2021). This situation can generate complex and not easily comprehended consequences for the fish stock both in terms of ecological and socio-economic aspects (Holmlund and Hammer, 2004; Jonsson and Jonsson, 2006; Trippel et al., 2018; Turek et al., 2018; Molnár et al., 2020; Morissette et al., 2020-).

For effective and sustainable fisheries management, it is important to monitor stocking programs to check whether they meet the intended goal. Many recreational anglers and fisheries managers believe in the stock-enhancement (increasing abundance and catches of the fish stock) effect of stocking and exert regulatory pressure on decision-makers to consistently stock the fish (Von Lindern and Mosler, 2014; Arlinghaus et al., 2017). Indeed, stocking can support fisheries and populations or help to establish a self-sustaining population (Boukal et al., 2012; Amoroso et al., 2017). On the other hand, many fish stocking programs fail (Kitada, 2020; Hühn et al., 2023; Matern et al., 2024) and are often unrealized by fisheries managers due to inefficient or poor monitoring programs (Anderson et al., 2014; Daupagne et al., 2021; Matern et al., 2024). An important empirical question is whether stocking produces positive results on stock size and catches.

To address this question, over the last century, different stock discrimination techniques and tools have been applied to identify and differentiate fish stocks of different species, such

as genetic analysis (Utter and Ryman, 1993; Gilbey et al., 2017; Dahle et al., 2018; Euclide et al., 2021; Jensen et al., 2021), otolith shape analysis (Mérigot et al., 2007; Leguá et al., 2013; Paul et al., 2013; Libungan et al., 2015; Canty et al., 2018; Souza et al., 2020; Milošević et al., 2021), otolith microchemical composition analysis (Campana, 1999; Campana and Thorrold, 2001; Pangle et al., 2010; Wright et al., 2018; Mikheev et al., 2023), tagging (Goulette and Lipsky, 2016; LeCheminant et al., 2021; Schloesser et al., 2021), and even the presence and composition of parasites (MacKenzie and Abaunza, 2013; Klapper et al., 2016; Marengo et al., 2017). It is important to note that each stock discrimination technique has its own limitations and advantages.

Otolith micro-chemical composition analysis has been becoming the most popular and widely used technique to discriminate fish stock because of their ability to classify with high levels of accuracy, particularly using the micro-chemical composition of the core part of the otolith, which reflects the elemental signature of the natal environment (e.g., hatchery or spawning grounds) (Walther et al., 2017; Walther, 2019). These signatures are “locked in” and serve as a natal tag of origin even if the fish translocated or migrated to different water bodies (Campana, 1999).

Pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) (Bruner, 2021) is a large-bodied fish native to Eurasian waters (Froese and Pauly, 2024) and is considered one of the most important targets for recreational and commercial fishermen in Europe (Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024). Due to its ecological role as one of the top predators in many water bodies and its economic relevance, this species has been the focus of population enhancement programs in many areas (Wysujack et al., 2002b; Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024). The present study aims to assess the prevalence of stocked individuals in the adult population in a system with a complex stocking enhancement program (multiple sources) and natural reproduction. Towards this end, the micro-chemical composition of sagitta otoliths of wild and stocked pikeperch individuals were investigated i) to develop a classification algorithm capable of identifying the natal origin of the fish based on the chemical composition of their otoliths and ii) to understand the contribution of stocked fish into the local population.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Otolith sampling

Pikeperch individuals were obtained either from the Lipno reservoir (104 individuals) or directly from the rearing facilities (66 individuals) before being released into the lake. The reservoir fish were captured using extended European standard multimesh gillnets (CEN – Comité Européen de Normalisation, 2005; Šmejkal et al., 2015) during the last week of August 2019–2022 in the Lipno reservoir. Only young-of-the-year (YOY) fish from reservoir sampling were used for training classification, as no stocking activities happened before the end of September. Thus, it is evident that the August samples of YOY fish consist solely of fish from natural reproduction. Larger pikeperch individuals (412 ± 70.60 mm, average \pm standard deviation of 70 individuals), ranging from 205 to 550 mm in standard length (SL) captured in the reservoir by gillnets, were classified as having an unknown origin and were subsequently used to assess the contribution of stocked fish to the population. Known wild pikeperch individuals consisted exclusively of YOY fish (106 ± 20.6 mm, average of 34 individuals) ranging from 53 to 140 mm (SL). The data of yearly stocking of YOY pikeperch were provided by the South Bohemian union of Czech Anglers Union and recalculated to one hectare of reservoir area. Comparable densities of YOY pikeperch from natural spawning were taken from the estimates of Tesfaye et al. 2025, submitted.

Stocked fish were sampled during the fish stocking campaign just before being released into Lipno in mid-October 2019 (with the exception of a few fish from the recirculation aquaculture system stocked in April 2020). The fish were randomly sampled using a scoop net and immediately euthanized by thermal shock. The standard length (SL) of all fish were measured to the nearest 5 mm using a ruler. A total of 66 pikeperch individuals from stocking facilities were used in the analysis, with an average length of 157 ± 62.2 mm (SL) and a range of 85 to 285 mm (SL).

The stocked fish came from five different sources located up to 150 km away from Lipno reservoir (Figure 1). A total of seven individuals were from Velké Rozběhlo, 18 from Humpolec, 12 from Vodňany, 16 from Košetice, and 13 from Nové Hradý.

Figure 1. Map showing the sources of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) stocking present in Lipno reservoir.

Pikeperch were hatched at Pohořelice fishery facilities and, upon reaching 4 cm in total length, were transported to the shallow rearing pond at Velké Rozběhlo (area=13.2 ha). The fish were kept under semi-natural conditions, exposed to intra- and interspecific competition, and faced predation from intracohort cannibalism and terrestrial predators such as birds and small mammals. They had access to natural food sources, primarily zooplankton and benthos, and later, young-of-the-year topmouth gudgeon (*Pseudorasbora parva*). In the shallow rearing pond, the pikeperch were accompanied by adult common carps (*Cyprinus carpio*), which were maintained at relatively high densities (400 kg/ha) (Souza et al., 2020). The length of stocked pikeperch individuals from this source ranged from 195 to 210 mm (SL) (Table 1). The pikeperch fry from the Košetice and Humpolec areas were semi-artificially bred on nests and hatched in local fishponds. They were initially fed on zooplankton and later on cyprinid fish fry, including tench (*Tinca tinca*), roach (*Rutilus rutilus*), and rudd (*Scardinius erythrophthalmus*). The stocking size of pikeperch individuals from these two facilities ranged

from 85 to 135 mm (SL). Fish from the Vodňany region were produced under an intensive recirculation aquaculture system, as described by (Blecha et al., 2016), with artificial pellet feed (BioMar, INICIO plus 2 mm) as the main diet. They were stocked in April 2020 at the age of one year, with sizes ranging from 145 to 220 mm.

Table 1. Number of individual pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) individuals analyzed from each origin and their average, minimum and maximum standard length (SL).

Origin	Number of fish	SL range (mm)	SL \pm SD (mm)
Lipno (wild)	34	53–140	106 \pm 20.60
Lipno (unknown)	70	205–550	412 \pm 70.60
Humpolec	18	85–105	91.8 \pm 4.75
Košetice	16	102–135	120.0 \pm 11.70
Nové Hradý	13	163–285	242.0 \pm 47.50
Velké Rozběhlo	7	195–210	201.0 \pm 5.80
Vodňany	12	145–220	187.0 \pm 20.10

The pikeperch fry from the Nové Hradý area were sourced from three fish ponds: Jakulský, Smrček, and Štůtv Malý. The fish were two years old at the time of stocking in Lipno. Large fry were purchased in Tábor and initially fed on zooplankton, followed by cyprinid fish fry, including topmouth gudgeon and roach.

In the laboratory, all otoliths were mechanically cleaned, air-dried and stored inside individual paper envelopes. Subsequently, the otoliths were embedded in epoxy resin (Epoxy G20) using silicon bullet molds. Once the resin was fully cured, the otoliths were removed from the silicone molds and sectioned in a cross-section using a low-speed saw (Buehler Isomet low-speed saw) equipped with a diamond wafering blade. The cut sections were then glued onto glass slides with thermoplastic resin (Crystalbond 509) and prepared for laser ablation technique as 1-inch resin blocks. Subsequently, these blocks were polished using 6 and 3 μ m polishing pasta. Finally, resin blocks were cleaned in ultrasonic bath with distilled water.

2.2. Laser ablation mass spectrometry analyses (LA-ICP-MS) and electron probe microanalysis (EPMA)

The samples for the laser ablation analyses were taken from cross-section cuts of the sagittal otoliths at their core. This area was selected because it represents the time when the fish were born and the first growth season (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Microphotograph by digital microscope Keyence VHX-700 of the sagittae otolith of the pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) in a transversal cut, the whitish area bounds the core of otolith location, and a fine oscillating banding shows age growth. Dashed white circles are laser ablation ICP-MS spots of 50 μ m diameter located in the core of testing otoliths (more spots are for data quality control purpose).

Trace elements analyses were performed on polished resin blocks using a 193-nm excimer laser microprobe (Analyte Excite, Teledyne) coupled to an Element2 magnetic sector ICP-MS (Thermo Fisher Scientific) at the Institute of Geology of the Czech Academy of Sciences (Inst. Geol.) in Prague. Samples were ablated in spots of 50 μm diameter. Laser was fired at the repetition rate of 10 Hz and the fluence of 3.5 J/cm^2 . Ablation was carried out in a pure He atmosphere in a two-volume ablation cell. Helium carrier gas was mixed with argon and makeup nitrogen before introduction into the ICP-MS. The isotopes ^{25}Mg , ^{43}Ca , ^{63}Cu , ^{85}Rb , ^{88}Sr and ^{137}Ba were acquired in low mass resolution ($m/\Delta m = 300$), the isotopes ^{39}K , ^{44}Ca and ^{55}Mn , and ^{66}Zn were acquired in medium mass resolution ($m/\Delta m = 4,000$). Calcium and its concentrations obtained by electron microprobe was used as the internal standard. The external calibration was performed using NIST SRM 610, which was analyzed before and after each set of 10 unknowns. The time-resolved signal data, consisting of 15 s background and 20 s ablation, were processed using the Glitter software (Van Achterbergh et al., 2001). The typical precision of the laser ablation analyses (expressed as a relative 1 sigma error) ranges between 5 and 15% for most of the detected elements. The carbonate standard reference material MACS-3 (U.S. Geological Survey) was used to monitor accuracy of the measured elements at the start and end of each analytical sequence. Accuracy of each element is shown in ESM Table S1 (reference values taken from Certificate of analysis, USGS). Calcium concentrations were measured using an electron probe microanalyzer JEOL JXA-8230 equipped with five wave-dispersive X-ray spectrometers (WDS) housed at the Inst. Geol. The accelerating voltage of 15 kV, the sample current of 2 nA, and an electron beam of 5 μm diameter were applied for all analyses. The analyzed elements included (used spectrum line, spectrometer crystal, standard, average of detection limit in ppm are given in parentheses): Mg (K α , TAPL, periclase, 115), K (K α , PETH, sanidine, 114), Ca (K α , PETJ, diopside, 630). The content of carbon respectively of CO_2 was calculated using the procedure based on atomic ratio recommended for carbonates in JEOL software.

2.3. Statistical analysis

Prior to conducting statistical analysis, the ratio of each studied chemical element to Ca was calculated. Micro-elemental comparisons between fish origins were conducted using generalized linear models (GLMs) and Tukey's post-hoc test. The GLMs were applied using the `glm` function from the `stats` package, while the Tukey post-hoc tests were performed using the `glht` function from the `multcomp` package (Hothorn et al., 2008; R Core Team, 2023). Outliers were identified using the functions `check_outliers` from `performance` package (Lüdecke et al., 2021) and `identify_outliers` from `rstatix` package (Kassambara, 2023) and removed from the analysis. Data was subsequently winsorized to reduce the potential effects of extreme values using the function `winsorize` from the `datawizard` package (Patil et al., 2022).

The differences in the micro-elemental composition of wild fish and those sourced from different facilities were compared, followed by a machine-learning classification algorithm. The models were run using the `random Forest` package on R (Cutler and Wiener, 2018). Random forests are an ensemble learning method for classification. This type of supervised machine learning analysis constructs a multitude of decision trees and then averages them into one functional final model (Ho, 1995). Each decision tree is created using a different sub-sample of the original dataset and only after the algorithm is trained by 2/3 of the dataset. The left-out cases are used to estimate the error as the trees are added to the forest. The method is not compromised by over-fitting and there is no need for cross-validation given that the analysis is run internally in constructing the final model (Hastie et al., 2009). The random forest model consisted of 100,000 trees. The mean decreased accuracy index and the mean Gini coefficient

were used to evaluate the contribution of each variable input in the model, with the former index expressing how much the model accuracy is impacted by the specific variables and the latter indicating how much each variable contributes to the homogeneity of the nodes. For both indices, higher values indicate higher relevance to the classification algorithm.

Afterwards, the machine learning classification algorithm was applied in a batch of pikeperch individuals captured in Lipno reservoir with unknown natal origin, with the aim to determine their natal origin. Finally, a non-metric multidimensional scaling plot was applied to visualize the relationships among fish origins of the training dataset using the function `MSDplot` from the `randomForest` package in R (Cutler and Wiener, 2018).

3. Results

A total of 170 sagittae otoliths were analyzed from fish ranging from 53 to 550 mm in standard length (SL) (mean \pm SD: 252.0 \pm 148.0 mm) (Table 1). Differences in the micro-elemental composition in otoliths were detected among pikeperch individuals from different origins. Nine out of the ten elements investigated: Ba/Ca, Cu/Ca, K/Ca, Li/Ca, Mg/Ca, Mn/Ca, Na/Ca, Rb/Ca, and Sr/Ca had showed significant differences between wild fish and those sourced from different hatchery facilities with varying natal origins. The Ba/Ca ratio was significantly higher in Nové Hradý compared to other rearing sources. For Cu/Ca, pikeperch from Vodňany exhibited higher ratios than those from Lipno and Košetice. In terms of K/Ca, fish from Nové Hradý had smaller ratios than those from Lipno, Humpolec, and Košetice. The Li/Ca ratio was significantly higher in Nové Hradý and Košetice compared to the remainder localities, with the values found in Vodňany being significantly smaller than all other localities. The Mg/Ca ratio was significantly higher in Košetice compared to Lipno, Nové Hradý and Velké Rozběhlo. While values from Humpolec also significantly differed from Nové Hradý and Velké Rozběhlo. The Mn/Ca ratio was significantly higher in Vodňany and Humpolec compared to Lipno and Nové Hradý and Košetice. The Na/Ca ratio was significantly lower in fish from Vodňany compared to Lipno, Humpolec and Košetice. Rb/Ca ratio in Lipno and Nové Hradý were significantly higher than elsewhere, and for Sr/Ca, Lipno and Vodňany fish had significantly higher values in their otolith cores than fish from Košetice, and Velké Rozběhlo (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Comparison on the fish origin based on the samples collected in the core of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) otoliths using the micro-elemental ratios between different chemical elements and calcium. Statistical comparisons were performed using generalized linear models, with post-hoc (Tukey's honest significance test) differences denoted by different letters.

A total of 100 otoliths from different individuals were used to train the random forest model, utilizing pikeperch individuals from six distinct sources: Lipno (wild)=34, Velké Rozběhlo=7, Humpolec=18, Vodňany=12, Košetice=16, and Nové Hrady=13. The model achieved high accuracy in identifying and classifying wild and stocked fish (OOB estimate of an error rate of 1%) by analyzing the micro-elemental composition in the core of the otoliths. Additionally, the model effectively determined their origin or localities (OOB estimate of an error rate of 11%). The classification accuracy was 100% for Nové Hrady, 97.1% for Lipno (wild), 91.7% for Vodňany, 88.9% for Humpolec, 87.5% for Košetice, and 28.6% for Velké Rozběhlo. The top five most relevant variables for correctly classifying the fish origins were Rb/Ca, Li/Ca, Sr/Ca, Ba/Ca, and Mg/Ca (Table 2).

Table 2. *Relative importance of micro-elemental ratios between different chemical elements and Calcium in the random forests model to classify the uncertain fish from the facilities. Superscript numbers refer to the ranked relative importance of each micro-elemental ratio to the model.*

Variable	Mean Decrease Accuracy	Mean Decrease Gini
Ba/Ca	167.08 ^{4th}	4.67 ^{3rd}
Cu/Ca	59.01 ^{8th}	1.47 ^{8th}
K/Ca	78.73 ^{7th}	1.54 ^{7th}
Li/Ca	653.98 ^{2nd}	22.06 ^{2nd}
Mg/Ca	161.38 ^{5th}	3.92 ^{5th}
Mn/Ca	53.86 ^{9th}	1.11 ^{9th}
Na/Ca	123.26 ^{6th}	2.70 ^{6th}
Rb/Ca	1,349.33 ^{1st}	36.27 ^{1st}
Sr/Ca	183.69 ^{3rd}	3.97 ^{4th}
Zn/Ca	10.03 ^{10th}	0.52 ^{10th}

The classification model was subsequently applied to a pool of samples from Lipno, where the origin of pikeperch individuals was unknown. Seventy individuals had their micro-elemental composition measured (Table S2), and the results were used to feed the machine learning algorithm to classify the fish of unknown origin into one of the six known sources. The model classified 81.4% (n=57) of the fish as being born in Lipno, while the remaining 18.6 % (n=13) were classified as stocked fish originating from Humpolec (17.1%, n=12) and Nové Hradý (1.4%, n=1). Overall, the density of young-of-the-year pikeperch from natural reproduction in the reservoir varied much more than stocked (Table 3). In general fish from natural reproduction are significantly more abundant. For nine years for which we have data, the share of fish from the natural reproduction was about 90% while the proportion of stocked fish was about 10% (ranging from 60 to 97%).

Table 3. The density (individuals per hectare) of young-of-year (YOY) pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) from natural reproduction (Tesfaye et al. submitted), from stocking by the Angling Union and the percentual proportion of the YOY from stocking on the total YOY cohort. Note that for some years, the estimates of YOY pikeperch from natural reproduction are not available.

Year	YOY density (ind./ha)		% of stocked YOY
	wild	stocked	
2008	64	37.28	36.81
2009	49	35.71	42.16
2010	–	20.25	–
2011	–	21.71	–
2012	–	13.06	–
2013	–	12.53	–
2014	–	17.47	–
2015	–	25.80	–
2016	234	13.78	5.56
2017	163	12.96	7.36
2018	8	5.27	39.73
2019	40	8.23	17.07
2020	126	15.33	10.84
2021	62	11.70	15.87
2022	694	18.94	2.66

The PPM ratios of K/Ca, Mn/Ca, and Rb/Ca in fish originating from Lipno were higher than those classified as sourced from Humpolec and Nové Hradý. Additionally, the individual classified as originating from Nové Hradý exhibited much higher PPM values of Ba/Ca, Mg/Ca, and Sr/Ca compared to the fish from Lipno and Humpolec (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Micro-elemental composition of the elements that were significantly different among sources in the core of Pikeperch's (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) otoliths of individuals of unknown origin that had their natal origin computed by the random forest model.

The non-metric multidimensional scaling ordination plot illustrates the ordination of different fish origins based on their microchemical composition. The spatial separation suggests that fish from various sources have unique elemental compositions in their otoliths, with individuals from Lipno and Nové Hrady being strongly differentiated from the other origins by forming distinct clusters. Humpolec and Košetice individuals were also clearly different from others. Velké Rozběhlo and Vodňany individuals were somewhat grouped near each other, suggesting that fish from these areas had a more similar micro-elemental signature but were still distinct enough to allow for proper differentiation among fish origins (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) plot showing the relationships between the pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) natal origin based on the similarity of micro-elemental ratio (Ba/Ca, Cu/Ca, K/Ca, Li/Ca, Mg/Ca, Mn/Ca, Na/Ca, Rb/Ca, Sr/Ca and Zn/Ca) on the core of their sagittae otoliths.

4. Discussion

Our results indicated that the micro-elemental composition of pikeperch otoliths is a very accurate tool to assess the natal origin of fishes, even in areas subjected to multiple stocking sources. The machine learning model was accurate enough to distinguish the fish origin from different rearing facilities, which can be a useful tool to estimate the efficiency of different stocking sources and programs.

Nine chemical elements were found to differ between stocked and wild pikeperch. Wild pikeperch had a significantly higher concentration of rubidium than stocked fish from all sources (with the exception of Nové Hrady), highlighting that this chemical element is an important marker for the wild population in Lipno reservoir. Rubidium is especially abundant in the area where both Lipno and Nové Hrady are located (Rene and Hajek, 2010), which nicely explains the observed pattern. In fact, in areas rich in rubidium, this element is easily weathered and released into the water, making this element a good marker of fish origin (Friedrich and Halden, 2008), and this seems to be the case in our study.

The second most important chemical element that distinguishes wild pikeperch from individuals reared in different facilities was lithium. The concentration of lithium in pikeperch individuals from Lipno was significantly different from those in Nové Hrady and Košetice but not substantially different from those in Velké Rozběhlo, Vodňany, and Humpolec. The observed high lithium concentrations in the fish from Košetice are comparable in content with Cínovec and Homolka lithium deposits in Czechia, but they have a different geological evolution. The local enrichment in lithium content is presumably associated with the occurrence of small

veins of fractionated orthogenesis in the northeastern part of Molanubicum, which may evidence local enrichment in Rb (Breiter et al., 2005). Weathering of these rock formations likely releases lithium into the water, resulting in fish sourced from Košetice having high concentrations of lithium in their otoliths. Various factors contribute to the variability in lithium (Li) concentrations in fish otoliths, including environmental conditions, dietary sources, and physiological processes (Avigliano et al., 2020; Martinho et al., 2020). It is possible for fish to have different lithium levels due to differences in water chemistry, especially when the environment has a high or low lithium concentration.

The concentrations of other chemical elements, such as strontium, barium, and magnesium, were also important in discriminating the natal origin of pikeperch, but they were much less relevant compared to rubidium and lithium. Several studies report that strontium concentration in fish otoliths is a good marker of their origin (Engstedt et al., 2010; Chen et al., 2020; Fitzpatrick et al., 2021; Mikheev et al., 2023). In our study, strontium concentration was also an important predictor, showing significant differences between wild fish and those from stocking facilities and among the stocking facilities. Additionally, a wide range of strontium values was encountered in the wild fish. Strontium concentration in otoliths usually does not display inter-annual variation (Fitzpatrick et al., 2021). Thus, even though the pool of wild unknown origin fish analyzed could be from different cohorts, the observed strontium variations are probably caused by a different environmental driver. Another possible explanation for this result might be a heterogeneous concentration of strontium in the pikeperch nursery areas in Lipno, which can indicate that the wild population structure is composed of individuals with distinct philopatry, highlighting the potential truth of both natural and human-driven metapopulation structure for pikeperch in the studied area.

Studies have shown that barium concentration in otoliths almost exclusively reflects the concentrations found in the water, but food intake quantity can also have an effect on the Ba/Ca in fish otoliths (Hüssy et al., 2021), with slow growth leading to higher barium concentration in fish otoliths (Sturrock et al., 2013). Growth may account for 20% of Ba variation in otoliths (Hüssy et al., 2021). This might suggest that fish from Nové Hradý rearing facility had a significantly poorer feeding condition than all other rearing facilities and the wild population.

Magnesium incorporation in fish otoliths is related to metabolic activity and not necessarily to the concentration in the water (Woodcock et al., 2012; Limburg et al., 2018), and it can provide information about the health of the fish. Studies indicated that fish possess a physiological system for controlling magnesium levels. The magnesium concentrations in otoliths can stay relatively constant despite changes in the amount of magnesium present in food or water, indicating that fish actively control the intake of magnesium. Consequently, Mg concentrations in the otoliths may not directly reflect environmental conditions but rather physiological processes related to fish health (Woodcock et al., 2012). In our study, we detected significant differences in magnesium concentration between Košetice and the other areas, which might indicate that the fish from this origin had some metabolic difference compared to the other localities (including the wild population). Interestingly, the machine learning model did not classify any fish of unknown origin as being from Košetice, which can suggest that fish from this rearing facility are not persisting in the lake, and it could be related to different physiological conditions during the rearing phase. However, more studies are needed to determine if magnesium can be used as a proxy for the survival of stocked fish.

The fact that fish from different sources live in the same area forming a single mixed fish stock can introduce important bias in assessing several biological parameters in the population. For instance, stocked lake trout have different thermal preferences than local wild fish, preferring to inhabit substantially warmer waters than autochthonous fish (Morissette et al., 2020).

Therefore, the assessment of Lipno pikeperch stock parameters influenced by temperature such as somatic growth, fecundity and spawning are likely influenced by the origin of the captured fish. Our results suggested that approximately 18% of adult pikeperch in Lipno are coming from rearing facilities. This number, even though it is not the majority, accounts for a substantial portion of the local population, and therefore, one should assume that the population is influenced by the stocked individuals to some degree. However, estimating the percentage of stocked fish in Lipno's pikeperch population does not consider the differences in catchability between wild and stocked fish. Normally stocked fish have a lower survival rate than local wild fish (Sparrevojn and Stottrup, 2007; Trippel et al., 2018; Larocque et al., 2020), meaning that the estimated percentage of stocked pikeperch in Lipno could be low due to higher mortality of stocked individuals. On the other hand, the naivety of fish from aquaculture could also have influenced the estimation of stocked fish in Lipno population, given that fish coming from rearing facilities are usually more naive (Klefoth et al., 2013; Hessenauer et al., 2016) and hence more easily captured, which in theory contributes to an overestimation of stocked fish in the population. So, it is possible that the percentage of fish coming from stocking facilities living in the lake can be both slightly higher or smaller than what was detected in this study.

A comparison between the density of YOY pikeperch from natural reproduction and stocking origin in Lipno reservoir (Table 3) shows a roughly similar proportion of stocked individuals in the pikeperch population as estimated by our model. It is necessary to consider that the estimates of fish from natural reproduction (Tesfaye et al., submitted) are from the end of August while the stocked fish numbers come from direct stocking occasions in October–December. Then we should assume that the densities of YOY from natural reproduction will be lower due to the natural mortality at the date of stocking. Thus, in a long run, the proportion of stocked fish may be similar to 18% of YOY fish and the survival rate of fish from natural spawning and from the stocking can be similar. Comparison of the densities of YOY from natural reproduction and from spawning show that the stocking is generally not essential, but it may be a feasible option when natural reproduction fails for any reason. Considering that only 18% of the fish in the reservoir comes from rearing facilities, and the financial costs allocated to stocking, this management approach might not be a good management solution for the pikeperch stock in Lipno reservoir, not to mention that this activity can carry substantial ecological consequences for the stock. In fact, in a recent study it was observed that fish stocking did not contribute to the populations in five out of six species in French lakes (Daupagne et al., 2021), highlighting that stocking efficiency should be monitored to avoid the implementation of financially costly management strategies that are not effective.

Both large (Wu et al., 2021) and small-scale (Molnár et al., 2020), traditional or modern methods of stocking programs can modify the genetic diversity and the population structure of fish stocks. Therefore, the pikeperch stocking program in Lipno reservoir probably contributes to the decrease of stock genetic diversity, which can be reflected in other parameters such as morphological changes in the population as well as smaller body size at age. Due to the continuous stocking of individuals coming from localities up to 150 km away from the reservoir, the pikeperch population in Lipno must be facing an unnecessary pressure that can be detrimental to the stability of the local stock. To better comprehend the effects of stocking on pikeperch population, the activity should be periodically evaluated to ascertain its efficacy and the consequences for genetic diversity.

In conclusion, our study demonstrated that the pikeperch population in Lipno reservoir is largely dominated by autochthonous individuals and that the contribution of stocked fish to the population is limited. The use of multiple micro-elemental tracers in the discrimination of pikeperch natal origin was highly effective, with fish born in the reservoir displaying a much

higher ratio of Rb/Ca than all stocked sources, with the exception from Nové Hradý, which is located near the same mountainous region (Šumava), but it is easily differentiated from autochthonous fish by the Li/Ca ratio. In the future, the use of otolith microchemistry analysis can be helpful to monitor the stocking efficiency and evaluate the success rate of different rearing facilities, which can improve the stocking efficiency.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Data availability statement

The dataset used for the analysis is deposited in the Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10001132>). The R code containing the analysis will be available online on GitHub upon the acceptance of the manuscript.

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Supplementary materials

Table S1. Measurement accuracy for Micro-elemental composition in the core of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) otoliths collected in Lipno Reservoir

Element	Li	Mg	Cu	Zn	Rb	Sr	Ba	Na	Mg	K	Mn
Reference values (ppm)	62	1,756	120	111	–	6,760	59	5,900	1,756	–	536
Mean measured values (n=55)	63	1,627	114	86	<DL	6,350	58	6,603	1,868	<DL	557
Accuracy (%)	1	-7	-5	-23		-6	-2	12	6		4

Table S2. Micro-elemental composition in the core of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) otoliths collected in Lipno Reservoir.

Variable	Mean ± SD
Ba/Ca	0.43±0.12
Mg/Ca	1.12± 0.25
Li/Ca	0.012±0.0036
Mn/Ca	0.30±0.21
Rb/Ca	0.018±0.007
Sr/Ca	12.13±2.51
Na/Ca	94.13±9.49
Cu/Ca	0.0086±0.012
K/Ca	15.4±2.81
Zn/Ca	0.066±0.070

Table S3. The relative importance of micro-elemental ratios between different chemical elements and Calcium in the random forests model to classify the stocked and wild fish. Superscript numbers refer to the ranked relative importance of each micro-elemental ratio to the model.

Variable	Mean decrease accuracy	Mean decrease Gini
Ba/Ca	163.04 ^{3rd}	4.12 ^{3rd}
Cu/Ca	82.11 ^{4th}	1.81 ^{4th}
K/Ca	24.93 ^{8th}	0.26 ^{9th}
Li/Ca	436.32 ^{2nd}	12.01 ^{2nd}
Mg/Ca	20.76 ^{9th}	0.24 ^{10th}
Mn/Ca	32.77 ^{7th}	0.52 ^{7th}
Na/Ca	40.89 ^{6th}	0.81 ^{5th}
Rb/Ca	1,010.29 ^{1st}	23.60 ^{1st}
Sr/Ca	42.57 ^{5th}	0.76 ^{6th}
Zn/Ca	9.81 ^{10th}	0.26 ^{8th}

CHAPTER 7

GENERAL DISCUSSION

ENGLISH SUMMARY

CZECH SUMMARY

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

TRAINING AND SUPERVISION PLAN DURING THE STUDY

CURRICULUM VITAE

General discussion

The indispensable role of pikeperch, as one of the large predatory fish species, in regulating the aquatic ecosystem and providing socio-economic benefits has long been recognized in its native and introduced ranges (Lehtonen et al., 1996; Jakubavičiūtė et al., 2024). However, anthropogenic impacts such as, overfishing, habitat degradation, alteration of spawning and nursery grounds posed a serious threat to the viability of the population in many temperate water bodies (Arlinghaus and Mehner, 2004; Jeppesen et al., 2012; Mustamäki et al., 2014; Olsson, 2019), urging scientifically sound conservation strategies and sustainable management approaches to protect pikeperch populations. This cannot be done without a deep understanding of the population dynamics of the species in relation to various environmental and ecological factors. It is also important to note that the management implications for pikeperch are complex and highly context-dependent, reflecting the species' dual role in European freshwaters. While this dissertation thesis has focused on the factors supporting pikeperch populations in systems where they are a valued resource, it is crucial to acknowledge that pikeperch are a successful invader in other contexts. Their tolerance for warmer, more eutrophic conditions has allowed them to expand their range, often at the expense of native cold-water species like salmonids. This dissertation thesis aims at contributing to a better understanding of the population dynamics of the species, specifically focusing on the somatic growth and recruitment in relation to various biotic and abiotic factors (Chapters 2–4), the trophic ecology of young of the year pikeperch (Chapter 5), and evaluate the contribution of stocking for the overall local population of pikeperch (Chapter 6), and finally proposes effective fisheries management approaches and future perspectives for pikeperch populations in Central Europe.

1. Intrinsic and extrinsic drivers of somatic growth of pikeperch

The somatic growth of fish can be influenced by a number of intrinsic and extrinsic factors; in this regard, many studies have investigated and reported the drivers of somatic growth using long-term data on individual growth patterns for various freshwater and marine fish species (Pereira, 1995; Rypel, 2009; Black et al., 2013; Spurgeon et al., 2020; Tao et al., 2023).

Chapter two identified and investigated the most crucial factors that promote and/or impede the somatic growth of pikeperch. Temperature showed the strongest positive effect on the somatic growth of pikeperch (Chapter two). Indeed, previous studies also showed an increase in the growth rates of pikeperch as temperatures increase, showing generally that pikeperch populations in southern Europe grew faster than in northern Europe (Lappalainen et al., 2003, 2009; Nolan and Britton, 2019). Climate models predict that climate change will increase air and water temperature (IPCC, 2023). Thus, higher somatic growth response and reduced maximum attainable size are likely expected for the pikeperch population in Central Europe.

Additionally, chapter two described the negative effects of transparency and the positive effect of Chl-*a* on the somatic growth of pikeperch, which could be due to the fact that the foraging success of pikeperch is better in waters with low transparency (high primary productivity) since they have visual adaptations enhancing their foraging capacity in turbid environments (Jokela-Määttä et al., 2019). The positive effect of nutrient enrichment on pikeperch growth is evident, but it appears to have limits. In fact, hyper-eutrophication (extreme level of eutrophication) can have a negative impact on the pikeperch population, as evidenced in Lake Balaton (Hungary), where extreme levels of nutrient loading from sewage and agriculture decreased the catch of pikeperch substantially (Biró, 1985). On the

other hand, decreasing in nutrient loading (phosphorus concentrations by 25%), together with other factors, caused a sharp decline in the catch of pikeperch in our study area (Lipno reservoir) (Jůza et al., 2023). Our study showed that the decrease in the growth rate can explain most of the observed drop in pikeperch catches at Lipno. This example shows that the decreasing nutrient loading associated with efforts to curb eutrophication in Central Europe may negatively affect the pikeperch population.

2. Key regulating factors of pikeperch recruitment

Understanding and predicting recruitment has long been a goal of fisheries science and ecology. However, variations in the importance of environmental and biological drivers and the dynamic nature of individual ecosystems have complicated the comprehension of these demographic characteristics in most freshwater fish species (Ludsin et al., 2014). The situation is even more difficult for predatory fish such as pikeperch, which has high intra-annual variation in recruitment (Blabolil et al., 2016). The problem is further exacerbated by the limited availability of long-term ecological and biological datasets, often essential for disentangling the complex factors that govern the recruitment of young-of-the-year fish. Despite this, several studies reported the biomass of spawning stock (Lappalainen et al., 2003; Heikinheimo et al., 2014) together with summer temperature during the first year of life (Lappalainen et al., 1997; Kjellman et al., 2003; Pekcan-Hekim and Lappalainen, 2006; Heikinheimo et al., 2014) and the availability of food (van Densen, 1985; Specziár, 2005; Ginter et al., 2012; Blabolil et al., 2019), as the main factor influencing the recruitment of pikeperch (reproductive success).

The demic structure of intra-annual cohorts appears to be a crucial phenomenon in the early life history of pikeperch (Chapter 4). Earlier studies analysing pikeperch year class formation tended to follow just one cohort or considered a mixture of cohorts without distinguishing them. Intra-annual cohorts differ by size, habitat, diet, trophic level, and even in hatching date, so they behave like separate intra-annual cohorts and are influenced by different ecological factors. Chapter three showed that higher temperatures in spring and summer and increased density of large cladocerans positively influence the extremely small (ES) and ordinary fingerlings intra-annual cohorts. Additionally, an increase in copepod density during summer benefited the ES cohort, while summer precipitation and low abundance of predators favoured the ordinary intra-annual cohorts. Interestingly, a higher abundance of ES conspecifics and YOY perch and higher densities of large cladocerans in summer positively influence the piscivorous intra-annual cohort (Chapter four). As expected and evident from previous studies (Lehtonen et al., 1996; Frankiewicz et al., 1999; Lappalainen et al., 2006), the piscivorous intra-annual cohort substantially contributes to the formation of a strong early-year class. The ordinary intra-annual cohorts also contribute significantly to the formation of a strong year class when they occur abundantly (Chapter four). Furthermore, chapter four revealed a strong indirect positive effect of a ES cohort on the formation of a strong year class through density-dependent processes (cannibalism, intra-specific competition) that enhance a piscivorous intra-annual cohort.

3. Trophic ecology of young of the year's pikeperch

A clear ontogenetic dietary shift and isotopic niche segregation between YOY pikeperch was observed in the studied reservoir (Tefaye et al., submitted). ES intra-annual cohort (10-34 mm) fed mainly on larger crustaceans such as *L. kindtii*, *D. brachyurum*, *Daphnia* sp., Diaptomidae and Cyclopididae and occupied the lowest trophic position. Ordinary YOY, with an

intermediate size of 37–80 mm, continued feeding on planktonic crustaceans, and consumed benthic macroinvertebrates such as Chironomidae, and occupied the intermediate trophic position. The subsequent ontogenetic diet shift to piscivory was linked with the intra-annual cohort size class ranging from 80 to 160 mm and primarily consumed their conspecifics and YOY perch and occupied higher trophic positions.

The increase in trophic position with size corresponds to the dietary shift from zooplanktivores to benthivores and finally to piscivores (Chapter five). The observed variation in trophic position among intra-annual cohorts of YOY pikeperch may be linked to the development of a broad size distribution, driven by differences in hatching time. These size-related differences likely promoted diet partitioning, leading to variation in trophic niches among cohorts. Such niche differentiation may represent an adaptive response to intraspecific competition for resources and could facilitate the coexistence of multiple intra-annual cohorts.

4. The contribution of stocking to the overall local population of pikeperch

The micro-elemental composition of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) otoliths is a highly effective tool for determining the natal origin of the fish, even in systems influenced by multiple stocking sources (Chapter six). The applied machine learning model proved to be sufficiently accurate to distinguish individuals originating from wild and different hatchery facilities, with fish born in the reservoir displaying a much higher ratio of Rb/Ca, indicating its potential as a robust method for evaluating the effectiveness of different stocking programs. Similar previous studies reported the effectiveness of the micro-elemental composition of otolith of freshwater fish to accurately discriminate the hatchery-reared fish from wild fish (Curtis et al., 2014; Perrion et al., 2020; Fitzpatrick et al., 2021; Vaisvil et al., 2023).

Previous chapters showed that Lipno pikeperch represents a strong self-reproducing population. Stocked fish thus contributed just approximately 18% of the adult pikeperch population (Chapter six). Although not the majority, this proportion represents a substantial portion of the population, suggesting that stocked fish can influence population dynamics to a measurable degree. Nevertheless, this estimate does not account for potential differences in catchability between wild and hatchery-reared fish, which could bias the observed contribution of stocked individuals. Normally stocked fish have a lower survival rate than local wild fish (Sparrevohn and Støttrup, 2007; Trippel et al., 2018; Larocque et al., 2020), meaning that the estimated percentage of stocked pikeperch in Lipno could be low due to higher mortality of stocked individuals. On the other hand, the naivety of fish from aquaculture could also have influenced the estimation of stocked fish in Lipno population, given that fish coming from rearing facilities are usually more naïve (Heermann et al., 2007; Klefoth et al., 2013) and hence more easily captured, which in theory contributes to an overestimation of stocked fish in the population. So, the behavioural driven uncertainty in the estimate suggests that it is possible that the percentage of fish coming from stocking facilities living in the reservoir can be both slightly higher or smaller than what was detected in this study, but it is a good proxy to understand the role of stocking to pikeperch population in Lipno.

All in all, due to the relatively small contribution of stocked fish to the pikeperch population, the efficiency of the stocking program should be further scrutinized to avoid pursuing management strategies that are neither efficient nor beneficial for the fish stock.

5. Future perspectives for the research and sustainable fisheries management of pikeperch

Pikeperch fishery in Lipno Reservoir is managed by the Czech Anglers Union through a combination of regulations designed to ensure the sustainability fish population. For pikeperch, these measures include a minimum legal size (TL) of 45 cm to protect juvenile fish from harvest. Angler effort is further controlled by a daily bag limit of two pikeperch (as part of a two-piece limit on all predators) and a total daily catch weight limit of 7 kg. Crucially, to protect the spawning stock, there is also a closed season for pikeperch from January 1st to June 15th, during which fishing is prohibited.

For effective and sound fisheries management, future research should aim to refine the understanding of pikeperch population dynamics by filling the main gaps identified in the current work (Chapter 2–6). In particular, the somatic growth study of pikeperch did not consider fishing mortality (recreational fishing), as there was no good proxy for fishing mortality and should be considered in follow-up studies. Furthermore, a comparison of growth trajectories between wild and stocked individuals would provide valuable insights into how the origin influences the somatic growth of pikeperch, which is essential for evaluating the ecological integration, fitness, and long-term contribution of stocked individuals to the population while also informing more sustainable and adaptive fisheries management strategies. Additionally, it would be interesting to examine the somatic growth variability of pikeperch in later years of life. Our study did not focus on sexual differences in pikeperch growth, which may also offer valuable insights (Argillier et al., 2004). Using otolith readings and back-calculations, it would be possible to reconstruct the life history trajectories of individuals from different interannual cohorts. The impact of different management strategies, such as legal size, catch quotas, and closed periods (so far, January 1st to June 15th) on the overall recruitment process (survival and formation of year class strength) needs to be addressed in future studies.

The recent rise in the population of European catfish (*Silurus glanis*) in Central Europe (Lyach and Remr, 2019; Lyach, 2023) poses a challenge for the effective management of the pikeperch population. Being an apex predator, European catfish directly feed on pikeperch, but also exert substantial competitive pressure by consuming common food resources (Britton et al., 2018; Vejřík et al., 2023). Given the nature of the pikeperch as a somewhat relatively inflexible mesopredator compared to the European catfish as a generalist and opportunistic feeder, this trophic interaction may further limit the stability and resilience of the pikeperch population.

Young of the year pikeperch monitoring can guide stocking: stocking of fish from aquaculture seems more feasible when the year class strength (abundance) of YOY is weak. The observed multiple intra-annual cohorts of YOY pikeperch showed that the recruitment process is more complex than previously assumed. Indeed, it provides a unique opportunity to study cohort-specific responses to environmental drivers and biotic interactions. Future studies should also explore the interspecific competition between multiple intra-annual cohorts of YOY pikeperch and other sympatric species, which may provide further insight into ecological interspecific interaction. Expanding this work to other temperate lakes and reservoirs would help reveal potential spatial variability in the trophic and reproductive ecology of YOY pikeperch, revealing whether the observed pattern is system-specific or more generalizable.

Last but not least, increasing the number of sampled fish for discriminating wild and hatchery-origin pikeperch would significantly enhance the performance of otolith micro-elemental analyses and could provide better insight into the variability of elemental signatures, cohort-specific differences and the overall contribution of stocking programs to natural populations.

6. Conclusion

The main conclusions of the dissertation thesis are:

- The somatic growth of pikeperch increases with temperature and Chl-*a* concentration and decreases with water clarity, suggesting potential growth benefits under future warming scenarios. On the other hand, the efforts to curb eutrophication in Central Europe by increasing the clarity of the water in the future may offset these benefits.
- Higher spring and summer temperatures and the availability of cladocerans and copepods positively influence extremely small and ordinary YOY intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch. At the same time, the piscivorous intra-annual cohort benefits from a higher abundance of extremely small cohorts and YOY perch.
- Piscivorous and ordinary intra-annual cohorts contribute directly to the formation of a strong year class. On the other hand, the contribution of extremely small is indirect through density-dependent processes (supporting the development of piscivory).
- YOY pikeperch exhibited distinct feeding patterns, transitioning from zooplanktivory to benthivory and piscivory. These feeding patterns were consistent with their isotopic signatures, with the piscivorous intra-annual cohort occupying the highest trophic position, followed by the ordinary and ES cohorts.
- The pikeperch population in Lipno Reservoir is largely dominated by autochthonous individuals, with the contribution of stocked fish estimated at 18.0%. This suggests the efficiency of the stocking program should be further evaluated to ensure resources are not allocated to ineffective management strategies. The use of multiple micro-elemental tracers was highly effective for discriminating natal origin, with fish born in the reservoir displaying a much higher Rb/Ca ratio.

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English summary**Environmental drivers of pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) population dynamics in a changing climate**

Today, the ongoing climate change, overfishing, habitat degradation, eutrophication, and alteration of spawning and nursery grounds pose a serious threat to the viability of the pikeperch population in many temperate water bodies. This thesis aims to overview some aspects of the population dynamics of pikeperch and propose some approaches that help for effective and sustainable fisheries management. Specifically, the research findings herein address (1) the somatic growth of pikeperch in relation to temperature and other environmental factors, (2) the main drivers of abundance (recruitment) of young-of-the-year (YOY) pikeperch, (3) the trophic ecology of YOY pikeperch and (4) evaluate the contribution of stocking for the overall local population of pikeperch.

An increase in water temperature and Chl-a concentration positively influences the somatic growth of pikeperch, highlighting the potential benefits of warming and turbid water. Conversely, efforts to curb eutrophication in Central Europe by increasing the clarity of the water in the future may offset these benefits. Additionally, biochronological archives were found to be valuable tools for identifying the environmental drivers of somatic growth.

YOY pikeperch consist of three intra annual cohorts differing by size, habitat, diet, trophic level, survival rate and even in hatching date. The increasing spring and summer temperatures and the availability of large cladocerans positively influence extremely small and ordinary YOY intra-annual cohorts of pikeperch. Additionally, an increase in copepod density during summer benefits the extremely small cohort, while summer precipitation and low abundance of predators favour the ordinary intra-annual cohort. Interestingly, a higher abundance of extremely small conspecifics and YOY perch and higher densities of large cladocerans in summer positively influence the piscivorous intra-annual cohort. Piscivorous and ordinary intra-annual cohorts contribute directly to the formation of a new year class at age 1+ and further. On the other hand, the contribution of extremely small is indirect by supporting the development of piscivory.

Young of the year, pikeperch exhibited distinct feeding patterns, transitioning from zooplanktivory to benthivory and piscivory. These feeding patterns were consistent with their stable isotopic signatures, with the piscivorous intra-annual cohort occupying the highest trophic position, followed by the ordinary and extremely small cohorts.

Microchemistry analysis of otolith cores revealed that the pikeperch stocking contributes approximately about 18 % of the overall local population in Lipno reservoir suggesting the efficiency of the stocking program should be further evaluated. The use of multiple microelemental tracers in the discrimination of pikeperch natal origin was found highly effective, with fish born in the reservoir displaying a much higher ratio of Rb/Ca.

Czech summary

Environmentální faktory ovlivňující populační dynamiku candáta obecného (*Sander lucioperca*) v měnícím se klimatu

Probíhající změna klimatu, nadměrný rybolov, degradace stanovišť, eutrofizace a změny trdlišť a míst odchovu ryb dnes představují vážnou hrozbu pro životaschopnost populace candáta v mnoha vodních plochách mírného pásma. Tato práce si klade za cíl shrnout některé aspekty populační dynamiky candáta a navrhnout přístupy, které pomáhají k efektivnímu a udržitelnému řízení rybolovu. Konkrétně se zde uvedené výzkumné poznatky zabývají (1) somatickým růstem candáta ve vztahu k teplotě a dalším faktorům prostředí, (2) hlavními faktory ovlivňujícími sílu nového ročníku candáta, (3) potravní ekologií tohoročků candáta a (4) hodnocením přínosu zarybňování pro celkovou místní populaci candáta.

Zvýšení teploty vody a koncentrace Chlorofylu-a pozitivně ovlivňuje somatický růst candáta a zdůrazňuje potenciální přínosy oteplování a zakalené vody. Naopak úsilí o omezení eutrofizaci ve střední Evropě zvýšením průhlednosti v budoucnu může mít na rychlost růstu negativní vliv. Biochronologické archivy se ukazují jako cenné nástroje pro identifikaci vnějších faktorů somatického růstu.

Plůdek candáta se vyskytuje ve třech kohortách, které se liší velikostí, prostorovým výskytem potravou, přežíváním a datem líhnutí. Rostoucí jarní a letní teploty a dostupnost velkých perlooček pozitivně ovlivňují dvě kohorty plůdku candáta: extrémně malý, trpasličí plůdek a běžný planktonožravý plůdek. Navíc zvýšení hustoty veslonžců během léta prospívá extrémně malé kohortě, zatímco letní srážky a nízká početnost predátorů podporují běžný planktonožravý plůdek. Je zajímavé, že vyšší početnost extrémně malých jedinců a plůdku okouna a vyšší hustota velkých perlooček v létě pozitivně ovlivňují rybožravou kohortu. Rybožravá a běžná kohorty přímo přispívají k tvorbě nového ročníku ve věku 1+ a dále. Na druhou stranu, příspěvek extrémně malých jedinců je nepřímý (podporuje rozvoj rybožravosti rybožravé kohorty).

Plůdek candáta v prvním roce vykazoval dva odlišné vzorce příjmu potravy, přechod od zooplanktivorie k benthivorii a rybožravost. Tyto vzorce příjmu potravy byly v souladu se signálem stabilních izotopů, přičemž rybožravá kohorta zaujímalá nejvyšší trofickou pozici, následovaná běžnou a extrémně malou kohortami.

Mikrochemická analýza jader otolitů ukázala, že uměle vysazovaní candáti tvoří přibližně 18 % celkové místní populace v nádrži Lipno, což naznačuje, že by měla být dále sledována účinnost programu nasazování. Použití většího počtu stopových prvků při rozlišení původu candáta bylo vysoce účinné, přičemž ryby narozené v nádrži vykazovaly mnohem vyšší poměr Rb/Ca.

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List of publications

Peer-reviewed journals with IF

- Getachew, Y., **Tesfaye, M.**, Kifle, D., Hailu, M., Fetahi, T., 2025. Trophic status and ecosystem functioning of tropical Lake Tinsu Abaya, Ethiopia: A mass-balance modeling approach. *International Review of Hydrobiology* (IF 2024 = 2.3) (in press)
- Symonová, R., Jůza, T., **Tesfaye, M.**, Brabec, M., Bartoň, D., Blabolil, P., ... Kubečka, J., 2025. Transition to piscivory seen through brain transcriptomics in a juvenile percid fish: complex interplay of differential gene transcription, alternative splicing, and ncRNA Activity. *Journal of Experimental Zoology Part A: Ecological and Integrative Physiology* 343, 257–277. doi:10.1002/jez.2886 (IF 2024 = 1.4)
- Tesfaye, M.**, Kumkar, P., Hailu, M., Verma, C.R., Tesfaye, G., Petrýl, M., ... Kalous, L., 2025. Discovery of Japanese gengorobuna *Carassius cuvieri* Temminck & Schlegel, 1846 in Ethiopia: implications for fisheries governance. *BioInvasions Records* 14, 155–167. doi:10.3391/bir.2025.14.1.13 (IF 2024 = 1.4)
- Tesfaye, M.**, Souza, A.T., Šmejkal, M., Jůza, T., Sajdlova, Z., Draštík, V., Kočvara, L., Symonova, R., Meador, T.B., Vašek, M., Kubečka, J., 2025. Distinct intra-cohort resource utilization in young-of-the-year pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*): evidence from diet and isotopic analysis. *Ecology and Evolution* 15, e71973. doi.org/10.1002/ece3.71973 (IF 2024 = 2.3) (in press)
- Tesfaye, M.**, Jůza, T., Šmejkal, M., Hejzlar, J., Čech, M., Prchalová, M., Muška, M., Tušer, M., Kočvara, L., Sajdlová, Z., Draštík, V., Říha, M., Vašek, M., Blabolil, P., Symonová, R., Brabec, M., Kubečka, J., Souza, A.T., 2024. The impact of climatic conditions and food availability on bimodality size structure and density of YOY pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*). *Hydrobiologia* 851, 3665–3681. doi.org/10.1007/s10750-024-05527-0 (IF 2023 = 2.2)
- Šmejkal, M., Bartoň, D., Duras, J., Horký, P., Muška, M., Kubečka, J., Pfauserová, N., **Tesfaye, M.**, Slavík, O., 2023. Living on the edge: Reservoirs facilitate enhanced interactions among generalist and rheophilic fish species in tributaries. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 11, 1099030. doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1099030 (IF 2023 = 4.6)
- Tesfaye, M.**, Souza, A.T., Soukalová, K., Šmejkal, M., Hejzlar, J., Prchalová, M., ... Kubečka, J., 2023. Somatic growth of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) in relation to variation in temperature and eutrophication in a Central Europe Lake. *Fisheries Research* 267, 106824. doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2023.106824 (IF 2022 = 2.4)
- Oppel, S., Ruffo, A.D., Bakari, S., **Tesfaye, M.**, Mengistu, S., Wondafrash, M., ... Nikolov, S.C., 2022. Pursuit of 'sustainable' development may contribute to the vulture crisis in East Africa. *Bird Conservation International* 32, 173–187. doi.org/10.1017/S0959270921000307 (IF 2021 = 2.7)
- Oppel, S., Arkumarev, V., Bakari, S., Dobrev, V., Saravia-Mullin, V., Adefolu, S., Sözüer, L.A., Apeverga, P.T., Arslan, Ş., **Tesfaye, M.**, Barshep, Y., Bino, T., Bounas, A., Çetin, T., Dayyoub, M., Dobrev, D., Duro, K., El-Moghrabi, L., ElSafoury, H., Endris, A., Ghazal Asswad, N., ... Nikolov, S.C., 2021. Major threats to a migratory raptor vary geographically along the eastern Mediterranean flyway. *Biological Conservation* 262, 109277. doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2021.109277 (IF 2020= 7)

Peer-reviewed journals without IF

Tesfaye, M., Tesfaye, G., Getahun, A., 2021. Growth and status of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus* L.) stock in Lake Chamo, Ethiopia. *Lakes & Reservoirs: Research & Management*, 26, e12375.

Manuscripts

Souza, A.T., **Tesfaye, M.**, Soukalová, K., Šmejkal, M., Ďurišová, J., Svojtka, M., Kubečka, J., 2025. Assessing the contribution of artificially stocked pikeperch to the population using otolith micro-elemental composition.

Tesfaye, M., Jůza, T., Šmejkal, M., Soukalová, K., Bartoň, D., Blabolil, P., Čech, M., Hejzlar, J., Prchalová, M., Muška, M., Tušer, M., Kočvara, L., Sajdlová, Z., Draštík, V., Martinez, C., Ribeiro de Moraes, K., Říha, M., Vašek, M., Symonová, R., Brabec, M., Kubečka, J., Souza, A.T., 2025. Disentangling the drivers of a piscivorous intra-annual cohort in pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) and their role in shaping early-year class strength.

Abstracts and conference proceedings

Kubečka, J., **Tesfaye, M.**, Boukal, D., Jůza, T., Vejřík, L., Souza, A.T., 2025. Reservoir fisheries in the changing world: Will the angler's paradise come back? In FAO (Ed.), *Proceedings of the EIFAAC Symposium on Building a Sustainable Future for Inland Fisheries and Aquaculture in a Time of Multiple Stressors*, (EIFAAC Occasional Paper No. 55), Pula, Croatia, 7–9 October 2024. (oral presentation)

Symonová, R., **Tesfaye, M.**, Boukal, D., Jůza, T., Kubečka, J., 2025. The onset of a predator: Ecological and molecular mechanisms for the formation of successful pikeperch year class. In FAO (Ed.), *Proceedings of the EIFAAC Symposium on Building a Sustainable Future for Inland Fisheries and Aquaculture in a Time of Multiple Stressors*, (EIFAAC Occasional Paper No. 55), Pula, Croatia, 7–9 October 2024. (oral presentation)

Tesfaye, M., Šmejkal, M., Temesgen, M., Verma, C.R., Kumkar, P., Getahun, A., Kalous, L., 2023. Gengoro-buna (*Carassius cuvieri* Temminck & Schlegel, 1846): New record from Ethiopia. In: Kalous, L., Šmejkal, M. (Eds), *Book of Abstracts – XVII European Congress of Ichthyology*, 130–131. Prague, Czech Republic, 4–8 September 2023. (oral presentation)

Tesfaye, M., Souza, A.T., Jůza, T., Blabolil, P., Čech, M., Draštík, V., Hejzlar, J., Kočvara, L., Muška, M., Peterka, J., Sajdlová, Z., Seda, J., Tušer, M., Vašek, M., Kubečka, J., 2023. Combined effect of climate and food availability on year class strength of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) in temperate reservoirs. In: Kalous, L., Šmejkal, M. (Eds), *Book of Abstracts – XVII European Congress of Ichthyology*, 129–130. Prague, Czech Republic, 4–8 September 2023. (oral presentation)

Tesfaye, M., Souza, A. T., Jůza, T., Blabolil, P., Čech, M., Draštík, V., Hejzlar, J., Kočvara, L., Muška, M., Peterka, J., Sajdlová, Z., Tušer, M., Vašek, M., Kubečka, J., 2022. Somatic growth of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*) in relation to climate change in Central Europe. In FAO (Ed.), *EIFAAC Symposium on Building a Sustainable Future for Inland Fisheries and Aquaculture in a Time of Multiple Stressors*, Killarney, Ireland, 20–21 June 2022. (oral presentation)

Tesfaye, M., Souza, A. T., Vašek, M., Šmejkal, M., Jůza, T., Sajdlová, Z., Draštík, V., Symonová, R., Meador, T., Kubečka, J., 2022. Biological parameters of an imperilled pikeperch (*Sander lucioperca*) cohort: insights into early piscivory and recruitment dynamics. In: Kubečka, J., Šmejkal, M. (Eds), Percis V – 5th Percid Fish International Symposium, Book of Abstracts: 54–55. České Budějovice, Czech Republic, 18–23 September 2022. (oral presentation)

Training and supervision plan during the study

Name	Million Tesfaye Godana	
Research Department	2021–2025 Institute of Hydrobiology, Department of Fish and Zooplankton Ecology (DFZE)	
Supervisors	Prof. Jan Kubečka, & Allan T. Souza, Ph.D.	
Period	25 th October 2021 until 18 th September 2025	
Ph.D. courses		Year
Sustainable fishery management in open water		2022
Bioinformatics		2022
Ecology of still and running waters		2022
Basic of scientific communication		2023
Outdoor aquaculture systems		2023
Biology and taxonomy of fish vertebrates		2023
Czech language		2023
English language		2024
Scientific seminars		Year
Seminar days of RIFCH and FFPW		2022–2025
International conferences		
Percis V Percid Fish International Symposium, 18–23 September 2022, České Budějovice, Czech Republic (oral presentation)		2022
EIFAAC Symposium on Building a Sustainable Future for Inland Fisheries and Aquaculture in a Time of Multiple Stressors, 20–21 June 2022, Killarney, Ireland (oral presentation)		2022
XVII European Congress of Ichthyology, Prague, Czech Republic, 4–8 September 2023 (oral presentation)		2023
XVII European Congress of Ichthyology, Prague, Czech Republic, 4–8 September 2023 (oral presentation)		2023
Foreign stays during Ph.D. study at FFPW, USB		Year
A one-month stay at LUKE, Helsinki, Finland, under the supervision of Dr. Mikko Olin, to advance my skills in understanding the population dynamics of pikeperch in its northern distribution range and to gain knowledge of various sampling techniques.		2024
A two-month stay at IGB, the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, with Prof. Robert Arlinghaus, to deepen my understanding of advanced population dynamics in closed systems and to evaluate the fisheries and conservation outcomes of various fisheries management strategies.		2024
Pedagogical activities		
Lectures about the ageing of fish		2022–2023
Assisted with and provided training in various fishing and fish sampling methods.		2022
Assisted in developing software for pikeperch fisheries management targeted at anglers in the Lipno Reservoir, Czech Republic.		2022–2024
Extracted data from SQL databases and conducted R analyses and graphical design for various projects at FishECU, HBU, BC.		2022–2024

Curriculum vitae

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name Million Tesfaye
Surname: Godana
Title M.Sc.
Born 5th April 1993, Arba Minch, Ethiopia
Nationality Ethiopian
Languages English (B2 level – IELTS certificate),
 Amharic, Ge'ez
Contact: godana@frov.jcu.cz,
 milliontesfaye510@gmail.com

EDUCATION AND WORK EXPERIENCE

2021–2025 Ph.D. student, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters,
 University of South Bohemia, České Budějovice, Czech Republic
2020–2021 Higher Diploma License as a Certified Professional Teacher,
 Hawassa University, Hawassa, Ethiopia
2016–2019 M.Sc., in Aquatic Ecosystem and Environmental Management, AAU, BDU,
 Ethiopia, in collaboration with BOKU University, Austria
2012–2014 B.Sc., in Wildlife, Wetland, Fishery Management: Hawassa University,
 Hawassa, Ethiopia
2020–2021 Lecturer & Researcher, Hawassa University, Wondo Genet College of
 Forestry & Natural Resources, Ethiopia
2018–2020 Conservation External Officer, EV–New LIFE Project, BirdLife
 International Africa Partner (EWNHS), Nairobi (Kenya) & Addis Ababa
 (Ethiopia)
2014–2016 Assistant Lecturer & Researcher, Hawassa University, Wondo Genet
 College of Forestry & Natural Resources, Ethiopia

REWARDS AND GRANTS

Best presentation at the Ph.D. seminars on Wednesday, 20th June 2023: Impact of climate conditions and food availability on bimodal size structure of pikeperch (*Stizostedion lucioperca*)

Grant Programme Biology Centre Grant Programme – Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences (BC CAS) – Winner, 2024.

Tropical Biology & Conservation Training Scholarship – Tropical Biology Association, Nairobi, Kenya – Scholarship holder (one-month program).

Master's Scholarship – Austrian Development Cooperation (ADC) – Scholarship holder, 2016.

DAAD (German Academic Exchange Service) In-Country Scholarship holder, 2016.